

Evaluating the significance of the learning work culture in UK's retail industry for long term business sustainability. Case study of PRIMARK UK

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By

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Abstract

Nowadays, the competition of the retail industry has significantly increased in the UK; the majority of firms focus on maintaining the long-term sustainability by providing accurate solutions to the most common issues which are faced in the Human Resource Management department such as the creation of a competitive advantage. In order to develop a better understanding of the research topic, the case study of Primark UK is taken. The reason behind this choice of company is the presence of employees from different backgrounds and the global presence of the company in more than 370 countries (Statistica, 2019). This internationalization of the firm provides the need of development of a learning work culture. The research problem of this study is the evaluation of the relationship between the implementation of learning work culture in firms and the long-term business sustainability in the context of Primark UK. This problem is based on contemporary issue and the findings of this research can be used for managerial as well as academic implications. In addition, this study developed an understanding of the implementation of learning work culture as a factor that encourages employees and labourers to enhance their performance, increase the competition in the market, and so on. For this study, the researcher used primary as well as secondary data collection methods. Under primary data, survey questionnaire and interview methods are used for collecting fresh and first-hand data. For survey purposes, 150 employees were selected through the non-probability sampling technique who is the employees of Primark UK. For the interview, 6 managers and 6 senior employees of Primark UK were selected through the probability sampling method. Moreover, the literature review method is used as a secondary data collection. These methods have both supported to increase reliability and relevancy of the research finding. The utilization of both quantitative and qualitative data collection and data analysis methods has increased the trustworthiness of the overall research outcome. From the finding of this study, it is reflected that for creating a sustainable

competitive market, the firm needs to have a learning work culture as it helps in targeting the customers as well as making an effective working environment too which includes the development of a technological environment within the organization that affects the performance of employees. The learning work culture has a major affect on firms as it helps in managing the work activities efficiently. In addition, other factors which effects the working environment have been identified such as the firm's location, facilities, etc., and they effect significantly on the decisions and operational functions of the company. The key finding of this study is that Primark UK needs to focus on implementing the learning work culture in the international market segment and the development of market orientation behaviour as it helps the company reach its organizational goals and objectives. This study also helped in identifying the issues and challenges which affect the implementation of a learning work culture such as the change in customer needs, the innovation in technology and the changing market scenario etc. The overall outcome of the study is how the successful implementation of learning work culture will lead to the development of workplace sustainability and long-term sustainability of the company. However, this study also identified some research limitation which restricted researcher such as the size of the sample of the primary data collection. Thus, the overall study outcome is very effective for the researcher for achieving the valid outcome and future use.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this dissertation is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contain no material previously published or produced by another party in fulfilment, partial or otherwise, of my other degree or diploma at another university or institute of higher learning, except where due acknowledgment is made in the text.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION TO DISSERTATION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter highlights the significant perspectives about all major aspects of the research. Moreover, it provides a background understanding of the research along with comprehensive discussion which highlights the importance of the selected research topic that is also discussed to generate valid and reliable outcomes and timely completion of the research. Finally, the complete research structure that is mandatory for the easy and valuable execution of the research is also discussed in this introductory part of the research study.

1.1 Research Background

Nowadays, every business sector is experiencing high competition in the industry because of globalization and free trade policies by the government. Free trades represent engaging selling and buying procedures of products and services between countries where there are no restrictions attached to the tariffs, quotas and the duties. The rising competition in the industry is one of the primary issues as faced by the companies in their growth and to create and retain a good consumer base. Besides this progressively increasing competition, the consumer demand for products and services offered by different companies is also continuously changing. It is creating difficulties for the companies to effectively plan their marketing/promotion strategies and devise business policies to build a large consumer base and grab market opportunities (Eraut and Hirsh, 2010). Additionally, the UK retail sector is one of the major industry segments that is playing an important role in the GDP growth of the country by providing unique and usable products for the customers.

However, the companies at the same time, operating in the retail sector are taking considerable measures to bring more productive variations in their internal and external procedures to manage the working condition of the organisations and bring consistency in business operations to cope with a competitive marketplace. In this internal and external change, most

of the firms focus on changing the external working environment like open the new outlets, increase the customer base by providing different benefits and advantages for the customers, change the marketing strategies, etc. All these changes are helpful for organizations to handle and manage the continually growing competition. But, alongside there are certain limitations of using external changes and these are effective for a particular time-period (McAllister and McKinnon, 2009). So, there are also different firms who have an understanding about the effect of external changes and because of this, they focus on having the internal changes within the companies for managing the customer base and sustain in this competitive environment.

In the internal change, firms try to develop the learning work culture. The reason behind this is that the learning work cultures makes easy to the organization, as well as the employees for easily sustaining the changes reacted to the market, consumers and to have consistency when it comes to business operations (Bratton and Gold, 2012). At the same time, developing the learning work culture makes positive work environment of the firm, motivates the employees to perform their duties with more devotion to the workplace sustainability and increased the consumer base. Additionally, to build a strong learning work culture, firms conduct different programs and also provide different advantages to the firm's employees for developing a learning work culture and to sustain in this competitive environment (Škerlavaj et al., 2010). Because of this development of the learning work culture rather than doing the external changes is the best way possible for the companies to sustain their position in this competitive environment and grow their business progressively.

1.2 Background of the Company Primark

Primark is leading market company in the retail industry of UK which provides different ranges of products including accessories, footwear, children's wear, men's attire, women's apparels, homeware, beauty products etc. that makes it popular in the market. As well as, the main reason behind its popularity in the UK retail market is the low-priced products and the best quality in the products. Primark always keeps low its prices from its competitors such as ZARA, H&M, etc., which provides a competitive advantage to the company for increasing its consumer base (Primark, 2017). As well as, providing the products according to the change in the fashion and always trying to address the customer requirements is also one of the primary objectives of the retail companies to make a loyal customer base, the same is followed by Primark to grab the market opportunities. Moreover, about the history of this firm, Primark opened its first store in June 1969 by Arthur Ryan. Basically, the firm operates its business in Ireland and most of the outlets of this firm are in Ireland. But due to continuously increasing demand for products and need of increased consumer base, Primark tends to open its stores in the UK's other cities for getting more competitive advantages and to increase the customer base.

1.3 Study Contribution and Justification

In the present-day working environment, most of the companies, especially retail firms are facing so many problems in their business operations to sustain and to have a valuable customer base because of the rising competition in the retail industry and the changing consumer demands. It is also creating difficulties for the firms to successfully operate their business and the employees' engagement towards a better working environment. As well as, it can also be said that perception of the people and the need towards using the clothes is now totally different. They like to wear new and fashionable clothes and try to avoid the old clothes that make an issue for the retail companies to formulate their production process accordingly and address the daily changing needs of the customers. So, the companies are using different ways

to deal with factors affecting the internal and external business processes to manage the changing consumer demands and sustain in an extremely competitive environment (Marsick and Watkins, 2015). So, this study is quite relevant and help the retail companies to know the significance of internal changes and external changes. But majorly, this research is aimed to give a clear understanding of the learning work culture to get sustainability in the competitive working conditions besides building a strong and growing customer base. This research work is also helpful to determine the major factors of the work environment that can surely contribute to the success of an organization. Additionally, the major importance of using this research is that it provides the basic relationship between the learning work culture and workplace sustainability (Deal and Peterson, 2016).

The completion of this research work is also quite important in currently prevailing business environment where the competition level is continually rising in the retail industry. It is also important to develop an understanding regarding customer satisfaction for being sustainable. This research will be beneficial to bring improvement in the retail industry and helps firms to enhance customer satisfaction by the help of the various ways and techniques. It is also found at the same time that to increase customer satisfaction in the retail industry the completion of this research will also be helpful to learn the various ways that can be helpful. Furthermore, it is also found that this research will also help determine the effective technologies that can give the retail firm a competitive advantage over the competitors. There are various past researches which are concerned towards discussing the significance of the learning work culture towards organisational success. However, there are only a few studies that have taken place to develop the understanding of the significance of learning work culture towards creating long term business sustainability especially in the context of the retail industry. So, this research is focused on discussing the research problem that how long-term business sustainability can be

created in the retail industry while focusing on learning work culture. To solve the research problem in a better way, a case study of Primark UK is taken by the researcher.

Additionally, the researcher through this research study will also communicate different ways that will assist the retail companies for improving their overall performance in the competitive business environment. As the primary goal of this research work is the assessment of the importance of the learning work culture on long-term business permanence as this study determines a relationship between workplace sustainability and the learning work culture.

Furthermore, this research work will also help to comprehend the importance of learning work culture and workplace sustainability in the organizations. In this, the researcher will explain the significance of the learning environment in improving the efficiency of the employees. Moreover, this research study will also provide a discussion on different factors affecting workplace sustainability and learning work culture when implemented in retail companies. For this, the researcher will analyze various academic sources that will provide more insight into the subject matter along with increasing the theoretical knowledge of the researcher regarding this work-study. It will also be a support for the researcher in the academic and the professional career. The completion of the research study will be helpful for the researcher to achieve a degree in the relevant course. Along with this, it will also enhance the knowledge of the researcher that will help to get a good job and achieve the growth in the professional career.

1.4 Research Main Question

As demonstrated below, the main questions of the research are enlisted and they are answered throughout the research paper in the literature review and the data analysis of the research:

- What is the importance of learning work culture in enhancing the performance of the workplace within the retail organizations?
- What is the relationship between the learning work culture and the performance of the workplace?
- What are the factors which affect the learning work culture's implementation in order to attain a sustainable performance of the workplace in the retail companies?
- How can the management of Human Resources improve the learning work culture within retail organizations in the UK?

1.5 Research Aim and Objectives

1.5.1 Research Aim

One of the major aims of this research project is the successful accomplishment the study conducted and to achieve results based on collected data for this research work. The main objective of this research study is to calculate the importance of the learning work culture on the long-term business permanence of Primark. At the same time, below are some objectives of the research that are accomplished to successfully carry out and complete this research study with valid and helpful outcomes.

1.5.2 Research Objectives

- To acquire a complete understanding of the concrete role of learning work culture implementation in the retail organization (Primark UK).
- To provide an identification of the factors which improves the implementation of a successful learning work culture in the retail organization.

- To provide an evaluation of the relationship between the workplace productivity and the learning work culture in the context of Primark UK.
- To provide the necessary recommendations of a successful implementation of the learning work culture of the retail organization of the UK.

Above are the major research objectives that are achieved in this study to find the importance of the implementation of learning work culture for workplace sustainability. Firstly, the research study focuses on providing an understanding of the importance of learning work culture in the retail organization and specifically within the UK retail industry (Primark). Secondly, the determination of the relationship between the learning work culture and the sustainability of the workplace which provides a better understanding for the researcher to know the importance of a learning work culture in retail firms. As a third objective, this study focuses on the identification of the major factors which contribute to the success of the companies by using the learning work culture.

Additionally, after reaching the importance and the factors of success, the researcher also analyzed some important recommendations that can be used by Primark UK for improving the learning work culture in the last objective. As the successful implementation of a learning work culture is a difficult task for UK retail companies, the researcher has included these helpful recommendations which will ease the challenges and problems which the organizations are facing during the implementation of the learning work culture. Due to this reason, the researcher evaluated the different factors that affect the learning work culture aspects in the firms. Similarly, some frameworks that ensure competitive advantage are also evaluated by the research in this research. So, these all objectives played an important part in this research.

1.7 Research Problem

The main problem of the research is to identify the following:

- The significant impact of the learning work culture on retail organisations within the UK.
- The relationship between the learning work culture and the efficiency of the employees at the organization.
- The identification of the factors which will affect the implementations of the learning work culture within retail industry in the UK.

1.6 Research Approach

In this research study, primary and secondary both methods of data collection have been used. It is because the use of both data collection methods was quite necessary for the researcher to know the importance of the learning work culture to the retail firms and to successfully produce the positive research outcomes (Corbetta, 2009). Furthermore, in this research, the researcher collected secondary data from different online and offline resources such as academic journals, books, and annual reports of companies, etc., in the aim of having a better and clear understanding of the relationship between learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. Another source for collecting the data used for this study is the visit of the researcher to Primark firm and gets the research survey questionnaire filled by the employees working there. Furthermore, the researcher used both qualitative and quantitative methods for relating all the primary and secondary discoveries to generate the effective and reliable research results as well as in the successful research accomplishment (Crouch and Pearce, 2012). In the same way, in this research, the researcher also used the inductive approach instead of the deductive approach. The use of inductive approach helps the researcher to create his own theories, instead of working on already available theories developed by others. It assisted the individual in doing this research work to achieve the aim of its successful completion on time and predefined the cost (Crouch and Pearce, 2012). As well as, in order to get the clear and detailed knowledge about the relation among the learning work culture and the workplace

permanence, the interpretivism philosophy is used and it is not possible for the researcher by using the other research study philosophy (McNabb, 2013).

1.7 Scope of the work

Scope of the Work (SOW) describes the area where the work needs to be performed. It represents milestones, reports, deliverables and end products of the research that is expected to be achieved through the research outcome (Nabong, 2015). In this context, this research is based on evaluating the significance of the learning work culture (LWC) and the research findings of this study will help to develop an understanding about how LWC remains supportive to improve employee and organisational performance and how it assists the firm to achieve long term business sustainability. To improve the scope of the research finding, the UK retail industry is selected in this research and the case study of Primark UK is taken to analyse how LWC is assisting the firm. The scope of this research is not limited to only international businesses as the research findings can also be implemented by SMEs too. Learning culture involves a collection of organisational agreements, values, practices and processes that are followed by the management and employees (Buckingham, 2013). It helps to encourage employees to develop better knowledge and competence and effective organizational learning culture helps to develop continuous learning and believes that allows influencing each other. So, in the contemporary highly competitive industry, there is significant scope of this research.

1.8 Thesis Outline/ Synopsis

The thesis structure determines various chapters of the study conducted to accomplish the predetermined aim and primary objective. In the general meaning, the thesis outlines providing the blueprint of the main heading and subheading in the research study that is prepared for completion of the thesis effectively. The reader can understand the main point of the research study easily with the help of this outline. In addition, an effective format of the thesis is helpful

to present the summary of the thesis. The section below represents the main headings and chapters of this thesis that are prepared in order to completion and achievement of the research aim and objective:

Chapter 1 Introduction: This chapter represents the first and main heading of any research work that develops a basic understanding of the topic of research. In order to start the thesis, it is essential to plan this chapter in an effective manner. In the perspective of this research work, it is found that all information about the different topics of the research provided in this chapter, such as research significance, research background, research aim and objectives, company background etc. and made it easy for individual conducting this study to complete it successfully and generate valid results (Crowther and Lancaster, 2012). This chapter provides the clearness about the research topic, aim and objectives that are essential to analyse the various theories and models.

Chapter 2 Literature Review: It is the second chapter providing an understanding of the research elements that play an important role in the research study. Along with this, for the completion of the research work effectively and validly, it is also important to have sufficient understanding and content on the research issue and conceptual term of the research. In this context, this chapter is very significant in this research study. It is because of the completion of this chapter in the research study, the researcher analysed the research provided by previous researchers and other relevant theories related to this research. This chapter contains the information which researcher used to obtain the key purposes of the study conducted by using the different sources like journals, and academic articles, etc., for having a deep understating about the subject matters of this research (Muster, 2011).

Chapter 3 Research Methodology: This chapter is also very significant in the research study that determines key methods used to carry out this research. It is necessary to have sufficient

information and data on the research work issue to obtain the primary aim of the research. This information and data are collected with the help of data collection methods. Using this section of research study under consideration, the researcher provided a clear and conceptual understanding of all the research techniques, approaches, methodologies, and processes, etc., that assist the researcher in the successful research accomplishment and to achieve the aim of the research (Corbetta, 2009). The selection of the different research techniques, approaches, methods, ways, in the research study depends on the nature of the research study. In this, it is found that the role of this chapter is very significant to improve reliability, validity and accuracy levels of the research study.

Chapter 4 Data Analysis and Findings: The accuracy and excellence of the research study depend on the impartial analysis of data collected and the principal outcomes and findings mentioned in this chapter of the research project. It allows the researcher to examine the collected data using different tools and techniques. It also allows the investigator to improve the quality of the information and data collected with the help of various data collection methods. This chapter of the research is helpful for the researcher to present the findings of the research. In the representation of the research findings, secondary & primary source for data collection used by the researcher (Crowther and Lancaster, 2012). The researcher focuses on effectively presenting the findings so that readers can easily understand the conclusion of the research. Moreover, by the help of this chapter, the researcher also prepared the basis for the next chapter such as conclusion and recommendation.

Chapter 5 Findings: This chapter of the research is focused towards offering the results of data analysis and has supported to offer the findings that have taken place from the data of survey questionnaire, interview and literature review.

Chapter 6 Conclusion and Recommendations: It is the final part or chapter of this research study that represents the overall summary of the research study. It can also be said that if the

reader wants to know the findings of the research study, then they can directly move on to conclusions. The researcher provides all the results in this chapter. At the same time, there are also some suggestions or some recommendations that are also provided by the researcher in this chapter of the research for enhanced further research. Hence, the researcher provides an improvement suggestion based on its experience in the research study. By the adoption of this suggestion, the future researcher can efficiently conduct the researcher study.

1.9 Chapter Summary

The previous chapter demonstrates the research background aspects which highlights academic research regarding the importance of the learning work culture and its necessity in the current business world in the aim of acquiring success and an increase performance of employees. In addition, the chapter explains the background of Primark company which includes their objectives and the study contribution which explains in depth how learning work culture enhances the competitive advantage of organisations. Furthermore, developing the research's main question and sub questions which aims towards reaching a better understanding of importance of learning work culture, the relationship between workplace permanence and learning work culture, the factors that affect the learning work culture, and how to improve the learning work culture which is adopted in retail companies such as Primark. Moreover, this chapter illustrates the research aim, objectives, and approach, in addition to the scope of work and where it needs to be performed and how learning work culture will assist the firm to enhance its performance. Finally, this chapter demonstrates a synopsis of the thesis where each chapter is shortly explained and how it does contribute to the research.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Work Culture and Learning Work Culture:

In the views of Carmeli and Gittell (2009) and Jackson et al. (2011), the amplified rivalry level in the market causes challenges for the firms doing business there. Moreover, it has also been stated in the research project of Carmeli et al. (2010) and Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015) that the way of business has been changed through globalization, free business trades, etc., in order to sustain in the working environment and to increase the customer base it is easy to the firms to do the business across the boundaries. In the same concern of this, Closs et al. (2011), Buckingham (2013) and Kinman et al. (2011) illustrated that due to the level of the competition increased and limited market growth in any particular region. Another perspective to this, is mentioned in the research study of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) and Wilderom et al. (2011), which states that although due to increasing level of the competition and the market base, looking beyond and making some new and unique business policies are good ways, but concurrently there occurs numerous other problems and challenges faced by firms when it comes to their business operations and strengthening their consumer base. So, to overwhelm these challenges, there are also many business and marketing strategies which are made by the company.

Regarding this, Evans and Waite (2010) and Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015) point out that there is an importance of using a different marketing and business plans so that firms can increase their customer base and stand in the competitive marketplace. But, the use of these strategies is limited and after a specific time period, firms look for another plan to stand in the market and to get the best advantage. According to Eteokleous-Grigoriou (2009) and Sackmann (2011), several firms have changed their focus concerning their marketing techniques and business strategies to sustain in the market. It is because due to globalization and free trades, managing the work and customer base is not a single issue because the employee engagement

and making a positive working environment are also the major business issues for the firms. In support of this, Evans and Waite (2010) and Kinman et al. (2011) defined that nowadays, there are different cultures of people working in an organization due to the globalization that creates issues for the firm to manage the culture difference and workplace sustainability. In support of this, it is defined in the research of Hager and Hodkinson (2009) and Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015) that not giving the focus on the skilled and dedicated employees are also big issues which are also affecting the firm's business and also creating the issue for business. It is because, in this competitive environment, every employee wants to get growth opportunities and to learn different things from the existing firms. So, it is also an issue for the firm to provide continuously the chances to grow for the employees to sustain them in the competitive environment for a long time. Jackson et al. (2011) and Sackmann (2011) supported this statement and they stated that workers are the main assets of the company that helps the firm to manage the whole work of the firm and to increase the profit of the firm. In this concern, most of the firms use different ways of increasing employee engagement through reward, appraisal, etc. In opposition to this, Hsu and Fang (2009) and Carmeli and Gittell (2009) said that the use of different ways of employees' engagement is not enough and it isn't effective because the need of the employees towards the firm and the engagement in the firm has been changed. It is because now most of the employees want to learn different things from the organization that can help them to improve their knowledge along with enhanced expertise so that they can build a better future and remarkable career growth.

In regard to this statement, Jackson et al. (2011) and Carmeli and Gittell (2009) illustrated that because of so many issues with the employees' engagement, most of the firms are now trying to make the learning work culture in the professional environment. The primary reason for this initiative is the difficulty of providing continuous change within the company's strategy. It takes so much time and cost and it also affects the firm's other business operation. Therefore,

creating the learning work culture overcomes the possibilities of raising the issue such as change strategy, market plan, etc. In addition, it increases the effectiveness of the firm with workplace sustainability. In like manner, in support of Jackson et al. (2011) and Carmeli and Gittel (2009) findings, it is researched in the research of Jones and Martens (2009) that the learning work culture assists the firm to effectively achieve its business goals and objectives. The reason in this is also detailed in the research of Kinman et al. (2011) and Satchin (2010) by stating that the learning work culture inspires the workers working hard and to provide their entire potential in the growth of the firm. The learning work culture improves the skills of the employees that increase their working efficiency and makes it easy for the firm to achieve the goals and objectives of the firm. This perspective gets affirmation from the research of Longoni et al. (2014) and Carmeli et al. (2010) which states that the learning work culture is helpful for the firm in the employees' engagement and to achieve the organization goals and objectives. According to Singh (2001), Hager and Hodkinson (2009) and Satchin (2010), work culture is the composition of norms, shared values, and rules which affect the work-related activities that are studied in an organization. Work culture is the collective and personal acceptance of the meaning of the work for a given time. In support of this, Sackmann (2011) and Carmeli et al. (2010) stated that work culture is the system in which work values are shared in the organization, which in return recovers the output and efficiency of the organization. Work culture is the sum of the forces from different levels around the work.

Work culture is the study of the beliefs, perception, attitudes, and thought process of the employees with the principles of the organization. As stated by Singh (2001) and Jackson et al. (2011), the work culture is the way of interaction among the employees and the way an organization functions. Moreover, it can be termed as the study of the mentality of the people at the workplace in the organization towards the work that creates a positive or negative environment in the organization.

According to Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015) and Jackson et al. (2011), strong work culture is found where the employees in the organization comply with the rules and regulations of the organization without opposing them. Every firm has its aims and objectives, technology, and HR (human resources). The organizational and individual factors interact and set up rules and norms which are relevant to the work. According to Sachein (2010) and Hager and Hodkinson (2009), there are various kinds of work culture like hierarchical culture, market-driven culture, clan culture, and flexible culture. Each type of work culture affects the performance of the organization differently. Along with this, teamwork culture, task culture, process culture, learning culture, performance culture, customer-focused culture, and work culture affect organizational performance.

Yeo and Pang (2017), Aasen et al. (2012) and Buckingham (2013) found that British is a country accommodates people from multicultural and regional backgrounds. Organizations in Britain have employees from a different cultural and social background that describe their mentality differently. This affects the work culture in the organization. Diverse workforces are there in the British organization. In the retail industry of the UK, employees from a different culture are provided with flexible working hours and grouped to work in managing workforce diversity. This helps in ensuring equality to advance organization performance.

According to Wilderom et al. (2011), Longoni et al. (2014) and Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015), healthy work culture is there only, where employees work in the coordination and cooperation and they are treated equally at the workplace. It means they should be dealt with based on their work and performance at the workplace. Apart from this, one of the important characteristics of the strong work culture is that it depends on the policies and guidelines of the firm towards work and tasks. In the words of Buckingham (2013) and Carmeli et al. (2010), learning work culture is the study of the values, system, practices, and principles the organization develops the competency and skills of both the individual and organization.

Learning work culture fosters the learning among the employees about the work, colleagues, management, and others. This helps in improving performance and productivity. A learning work culture is the type of work culture that is composed of the conventions, values and practices and processes in an organization.

2.1 Importance of Learning Work Culture and Workplace Sustainability in the Organizations

In the views of Aasen et al. (2012) and Çakar and Ertürk (2010) in the business environment, the term learning culture represents the organizational value, system and practices that help encourage the employees and overall organization to adopt the change in the business process. However, it influences the ongoing system of the company negatively but still, there has expectation of something good after the change. A learning work culture at the workplace helps the company to involve all the employees in the change & helps them adapt to something new. In the support of this, the research study findings of Chen and Tseng (2012) and Hager & Hodkinson (2009) show that the learning culture at the workplace leads to sustainable engagement of the overall organization. It also determined that most of the companies in the business environment do not face the issue in retaining the critical skills or employees in the workplace. In addition, most of the companies also face the issue in retaining the potential people at the workplace. The main reason behind these events is the lack of the company to manage the employees and retaining them for a long time.

In other words of Longoni et al. (2014) and Aasen et al. (2012), it is mentioned that learning work culture is not only important for employees but also for the organization. A learning work culture of the organization allows the employees to share their vision as well as increase the sense of collective commitment that will be helpful to reduce the conflicts within the organization at the workplace. At the same concern of this, a fair learning work culture also provides the ability to employees to challenge their present condition and think critically so

that they can grow and go beyond the limit of skill set. Furthermore, from the research of Landy and Conte (2016), Alvesson and Sveningsson (2015) and Singh (2001), it could be defined that a (learning work culture) gives various benefits to the organization like increased productivity, profitability, decreased employee's turnover, development of leadership as well as creating adaptive environment within the organization.

Moreover, the research study finding of Wambui et al. (2013) and Škerlavaj et al. (2010) determined that sustainable engagement of the employee in the company is related with quality and nature of the company. At the same time, in proving the quality in the service or product, there is a significant role in the experience of the employee in the relevant field. The positive behaviour of the employee and worker at the workplace create the organizational culture and develop a positive working culture. A positive working culture is able to develop a sustainable workplace for the employees. Joo and Shim (2010) and McAllister and McKinnon (2009) also confirmed that the main benefit of the learning culture is that it is helpful to encourage and develop a problem-solving behavior at the office or workplace. The learning attitude of workers at the office provides the solution of the various critical problems at the workplace. It allows them to use their skills and ability in solving the issue and problem.

In the same concern of this, workplace sustainability is also important for the company in the different manner. In this context, the research study of Singh (2001), Argote (2012) and Thomas and Brown (2011) determined that the sustainable working environment is helpful for the company to reduce the overall cost of the company. It is because the sustainable workplace allows the company to make the effective use of the organizational resources. It reduces the various costs of the company such as the maintenance cost of the equipment. Hence, it can be said that the sustainable working environment minimizes the organizational cost. Moreover, it is also found in the research study of Wolf (2013) and Trevarthen (2011), it is found a sustainable workplace place provides the competitive advantage to the company in the

competitive business environment. It is helpful for the company to improve the market reputation and goodwill of the company. It directly provides the benefit in the sales of the company.

Figure 1: Importance of LWC

(Source: Created by the researcher- November, 2019)

2.1.1 Learning work culture and employee's productivity:

In the words of Marsick and Watkins (2015) and Boso, et al. (2013) a healthy and strong learning work culture can satisfy the employees and improve their productivity and performance. So, learning the work culture helps in accommodating the diversity and in the adjustment that may lead to the strong performance from the individual and the organization as well. According to Wilderom et al. (2011) and Ones and Dilchert (2012) employees are the core competency of any organization therefore they should be managed effectively and should

be in cordial with each other at workplace. The effective coordination between employees leads towards good teamwork. The effective co-ordination leads towards effective and positive work culture at workplace.

Marsick and Watkins (2015), Nussbaum (2016) and Aasen et al. (2012) stated that there is tough competition in the market in the modern era as organizations are focusing on the value of people in the organization to motivate them and to increase their morals. This is because satisfied and motivated employees represent strong work culture that affects the organizational performance and helps the organization in achieving aims and objectives in competitive environment. In a research conducted by Podsiadlowski et al. (2013), it is found that because of the globalization, organizations have diversified staff that gives organizations tough challenges in managing workforce diversity and establishing the unity and an effective team. In support of this, Wambui et al. (2013) and Ahmad and Omar (2010) stated that the multinational organizations have a large number of employees in different economy from different cultural backgrounds. They have different perception, thought processes, attitudes and beliefs that are very challenging job to manage this diversity. The effective management of the diversity leads to the effective work culture. The learning work culture supports in managing the workforce diversity effectively.

According to the research study of Awan and Tahir (2015), Pandey and Rishi (2016) and Wilderom et al. (2011), it can be explained that a learning work culture is linked to employee's productivity directly or indirectly because organizational culture impacts the employees' views and performance unfortunately. That is why a high performance within organizational culture leads to the high performing team members. As per this competitive environment, organizations need more productivity which can be achieved through a high-performance work culture. At the same time, Jones et al. (2016) and Podsiadlowski et al. (2013) states that to sustain in this competitive environment, productivity is not enough. Organizations need

something new, innovative and this can only happen by the learning work culture. Learning work culture helps employees to motivate for accepting new challenges, adapting to innovation, embracing new skills and then directing these learning opportunities into the talent pool.

2.1.2 Learning work culture and organizational performance:

According to Joo and Lim (2009) and Jormanainen and Koveshnikov (2012), the strong learning work culture helps in improving the performance and productivity of the organization that leads it towards achieving sustainable development in the competitive market. In support of this, Škerlavaj et al. (2010) and Kassens-Noor (2012) stated that effective learning of the notions of the work culture is necessary for achieving the competitive advantage during the changes in environment. The positive work culture leads the organization towards success and sustainable development in the competitive market. Through the strong work culture, the organization or management can be in position to have effective relation with employees, as work culture is based on the social interactions.

As stated by Ahmad and Omar (2010) and Kim and McLean (2014), some organizations provide flexible working facility while other organizations provide strict working time for the employees. Flexible working system helps employees to establish good balance between their personal and work life and reduce the work-life stress. This fosters better learning culture at workplace and reduces the turnover and absenteeism of the employees. In the words of Joo and Shim (2010) and Longoni et al. (2014) learning work culture aids the organization in designing the workplace strategies and policies to motivate the employees for exploiting their potential towards the achievement of the organizational mission and objectives. In support of this, Scheeres et al. (2010) and Joo and Lim (2009) researched that learning work culture helps in gaining the knowledge about perception and beliefs of the employees that can be used in design of the work-related policies and strategies in a manner which motivates employees.

Cooper et al. (2010) and APSC (2016) stated that learning work culture leads towards the development of the employees and the development of the organization. The development of employees improves the efficiency and skills of employees that can be exploited in achieving the organizational goals and objectives. It is supported by the research of Joo (2010) and McAllister and McKinnon (2009) in which he found that learning work culture helps in identifying and managing the risk and uncertainties at workplace. This may improve the performance and productivity of the employees and organizations as well. In contrast to this, Carmeli and Gittel (2009) and Bhattacharjee (2013) stated that though learning work culture leads improvement in the performance and productivity but on the other hand it increases the cost of firm and affects the operation and process of firm. It is because management has to run different programs and workshops for the learning and development of the employees at workplace.

2.1.3 Learning work culture and change implementation in the organization:

In the words of Joo and Shim (2010) and Palinkas, et al. (2015) the learning work culture fosters the continuous learning of the employees which helps improve their work performance and quality of productivity. This can help in changing the mindset and behaviour of the employees towards their organization, the job they do there and towards other employees. As stated by Thomas and Brown (2011) and Parvin and Kabir (2011), learning work culture helps in being updated with the changes in the market that helps in adopting changes in the organization. The learning work culture motivates the employees to accept the challenges and changes. The adaption to the market ensures the sustainability of the organization in a competitive environment.

As mentioned by Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011), learning work culture leads towards the innovation and creativity in the organization that is very necessary for the sustainable development of an organization and competitive advantage. Today, organizations are

competing based on the innovative products, processes, technologies, and work style that helps them in increasing the efficiency of the organization. In support of this, Szczepańska-Woszczyńska (2014) and Joo and Shim (2010) argued that the learning work culture develops the knowledge and skills of employees that helps in getting innovative ideas and thoughts from them, which can be used towards the achievement of the organizational goals. Learning work culture provides the employees with good environment to learn new things and experiencing new things that lead them to do innovative work. According to García-Morales et al. (2012) and Bloom et al. (2012) continuous innovation and creativity is required in the organization for winning over the competitors in the market. The learning work culture nurtures the learning of technology, economic factors, political risks, customer behavior and purchase pattern, and competitors' actions and behavior. Based on the learning of these factors, an organization can design its marketing strategies accordingly to compete in the market effectively. The learning of these factors provides the organization with new ideas and new ways to achieve the desired creativity. This puts effect on the sustainability of the organization.

Along with this, Aasen et al. (2012) and Joo and Shim (2010) pointed out that every employee at workplace occupies the knowledge, skills and potential for the creativity and innovation and can contribute in the development of innovative policies and strategies for the organization. Therefore, the people working with any firm should be involved in company's organizational and decision-making processes or at least take their opinion for the same. In this way, they will be in a better position of learning and contributing in making positive changes in the workplace. This can motivate the employees as they are provided value by involving in the organizational practices. In support of this, Chesbrough (2003) and Buckingham (2013) stated that there is a close link between learning and innovation. Learning from the environment and workplace leads towards innovation. In the open innovation system, exploration and exploitation increase the value of internal expertise and capabilities.

2.1.4 Learning work culture and risk management:

At the same time, Wiernik et al. (2013) and Sachien (2010) affirmed that the learning work culture assists the firm in terms of by reducing the risks and issue within the firm that creates the business challenges for the firm and make hurdle in the growth of the firm. By supporting this statement, McAllister and McKinnon (2009) and Peng and Lai (2012) depicted that there is so many problems related to the work of staff members, and work culture, etc., which affect the business operations of the firm. Therefore, it becomes important to induce learning work culture in an organization to manage all such issues and develop a remarkable market value. It is because it increases the understanding power of the employees and makes them easy to evaluate between right and wrong things.

It assists the firm to overcome the issue and make a strong and effective work culture. But at the same time, there are also different authors those thinking that there is not any vital role of the learning work culture to manage the issues and to create an effective work culture. In regard to this, Ones and Dilchert (2012) and Carmeli and Gittell (2009) illustrated that there are also different ways instead of learning work culture that can be used to manage the issues and the working environment. It is because although learning work culture is one of the major and important aspects of the firm that can be used to bring improvement at different levels, but this learning work culture could be one of the reasons of firm's increasing cost that affect the other business operations of the firm. Due to this matter, there are different findings that are given by the different authors and in all the findings, it becomes clear that there exists a lot of ways and different solutions using which the firms can manage better working conditions and develop an incredible consumer base instead of developing the learning work culture.

Wiernik et al. (2013) and Rai et al. (2009) supported this perspective and defined that by using the cultural diversity management programs and other motivational lectures, there are high possibilities to manage these issues and to create the effective work environment. The reason

of this is that due to increasing the level of the competition and the globalization, free trades, etc., it is easy for the firm to do the business across the boundary as well as it is also easy now for the people to work anywhere across the world. So, due to this, there are high possibilities in the firms to create the issue related to culture management. Additionally, cultural management issues like communication issue, language issue, etc., that make the hurdle for a company to successfully manage different business operation besides developing a good consumer base. In regard to this, from the research of Sachien (2010), it is determined that in order to manage all the issues and to have a good flow in the business, conducting the culture diversity program is one of the best ways for over developing the learning work culture.

Besides from this, Rai et al. (2009) and Carmeli et al. (2010) exhibited that developing the learning work culture is also helpful for the firms to encourage the problem solving within the firm. It is because in order to increase the employees' problem-solving skills and to manage the problem within the firm, there are different programs related to learning work culture which was conducted by the firm. In this, different skills test, providing the solution test etc. are conducted by the firms that increase the problem-solving skills of the employees and it also limits the chances of occurring any issue and problem within the firm. At the same time, this statement is also supported by the research of Schroeder (2013) and Chesbrough (2003) by stating that due to increasing percentage of different culture people work, raising the problem and the issues at the work place is the normal issue that makes hurdle in the growth of the firm. Because of this most of the firms look to use the learning work culture in the firm which makes it possible & easy to manage the problems and to create the effective working environment.

At the same concern, Duffield and Whitty (2015) and Sachien (2010) mentions that learning work culture supports the risk and issues management through its learning that makes the employees capable to face various risks and issues as well as it helps to manage risk and issue management within the organization. Learning work culture makes it efficient to the employees

so that they can overcome or reduce the risk and go beyond the limits in order to achieve organizational goals with corporate social responsibilities. Moreover, Kim and McLean (2014) and Schroeder (2013) state that learning work culture helps the organization to manage its values in this competitive environment as well as to manage its employees' learning in respect to behave ethically within the organization. These activities lead the resolutions of risks and issues that are assessed by the risk and issues management.

In support of this statement, it is researched in the research of Škerlavaj et al. (2010) and Rai et al. (2009) that there are different MNC (Multinational Companies) which are using the concept of learning work culture in its business practices. At the same time, Google, Squarespace, Twitter, Facebook, Adobe etc. are the major firms that use the learning work culture in its business and it helps these firms to achieve the workplace sustainability. In the same concern of this, Trevarthen (2011) and Closs et al. (2011) defined that the reason behind using the learning work culture is that these are the international firms and employees working in these companies belong to different backgrounds. So, any issue related to employees and the working environment affects the overall business of the firm and creates the profit issue to the firm. Therefore, these companies always try to implement and make the best possible use of learning work culture in their business practices that makes it easy for them to deal with all such issues and increase their consumer base.

2.1.5 Learning work culture and CSR

In the research of, Rai et al. (2009) and Škerlavaj, et al. (2010), it is illustrated that the learning work culture also helps the firm to successfully implement CSR (corporate social responsibilities). The reason behind this is that the learning work culture enables the employees to think beyond and effectively for managing the CSR activities. As well as, through learning work culture, employees are also enabled to manage the cost of CSR activities that can provide the extra benefits to the firm and also increase the image of the firm in the market. Likewise,

managing the CSR activities with the better management of the business is one of the major challenges nearly all firms are facing nowadays. It is because of the high involvement of CSR activities in the firms that affects the other business operations as well as the employees' involvement also, while low focus on the CSR activities also affects the image of the firm in the market and the customers' mind (Du et al., 2010). So, in order to manage this issue and to engage a better implementation of CSR activities in the firm, there are different firms which create the learning work culture in its business. The learning work culture assists the firm to achieve a better management of CSR and the other business operations of the firm as well. It is because the learning work culture increases the ability of employees to make better CSR strategies of the firm by minimizing the wastages and increasing the effectiveness. Because of this it can be stated that the use of learning work culture is quite effective for the firm to successfully implement the CSR activities and the other business operations of the firm simultaneously that is quite vital for the firm to reach better workplace sustainability.

From the research of Gosling et al. (2017) and So, et al. (2013), it can be mentioned that a learning work culture creates values within the organizations and few values are related to the corporate social responsibilities which is a must for organizations to force them to work ethically. A learning work culture motivates the organizational employees to behave ethically within the organization and work culture also helps employees to change their mind set as per organizational ethics. These learnings are leading the corporate social responsibilities in the organization. Apart from this, in the other words of Lozano (2015) and Rai et al. (2009), it can be determined that learning work culture helps to reduce the cost of CSR in the organization because after creating learning work culture within the organizations, they do not need to organize additional training or other activities for employees to learn that what the CSR is and How to behave according to CSR activities. Furthermore, CSR activities within the organization are developed with the help of the learning work culture which is helpful to reduce

employees' turnover and organizational commitment so that the organization does not face issues in respect to employees' turnover or employees' retention. Pandey and Rishi (2016) and Thomas and Brown (2011) also describes that learning work culture leads the CSR in order to reach a better employees' performance and engagement and in addition, CSR maintains an organizational reputation to attract prospective employees towards the organization.

Developing leaders at all levels:

In the research of Bloom et al. (2012), it is determined that learning work culture is quite helpful for the firms to get the success in the market and to perform well in the market as well. But at the same time, it can also be stated that different factors help in the success of the firm and to make an effective learning work culture. In support of this, from the research of Çakar and Ertürk (2010), and Conrad & Poole (2012) it is illustrated that there are lots of advantages for the firm to develop the learning work culture and to follow the workplace sustainability and develop the leaders at all levels is one of the primary benefits for a company with learning work culture. It is because due to the learning work culture, there are different things that are also learnt by the employees and helps to develop the different skills and the knowledge of the employees. It increases the possibilities of raising the different leaders in the firm. Because of this, it can be determined that developing the learning work culture helps the firms to develop the leaders at a different level.

The research conducted by Carmeli and Gittell (2009), also strengthen this perspective and determined that learning the work culture also helps the firm in the workplace sustainability because developing the leader in different departments of the firm assists the firm to have a clear and thorough understanding of issues related to the internal and external environment of the firm that directly assists the firm in the workplace sustainability. In oppose of this, from the research of Carmeli et al. (2010), and Costello et al. (2011) it is determined that however developing the learning work culture assists the firm to develop the leaders in the different

department of the firm but at the same time, it is also determined that it also makes the cause of raising different issues and challenges in terms of employees' engagement, finance, etc., that affect the other business operations of the firm. That is why another perspective can be established that there exist numerous other issues that firms usually face in the successful accomplishment of learning work culture.

In other words of Bolman and Deal (2017), and Trevarthen (2011) it can be defined that a learning work culture of the organizations directly or indirectly leads the leadership because the learning work culture is a motivational factor for the employees within the organization in order to encourage them to learn new skills and face new challenges. These day to day challenges and new skills change the mindset of employees from staying at the same level to achieve the next level. Due to these learning opportunities, the employees are capable to work with more efficiency and also learn leadership skills to lead the organizational operations. In the research of Northouse (2018) and Costello et al. (2011), it is mentioned that the learning work culture makes employees efficient as well as proficient to take their decisions by their own and also make confident so that they can take the responsibilities of leaders and also provide the guidance to other employees. These activities make the employees satisfied with respect to handling the team as well as operations in the organizations. Furthermore, it is also determined that employees feel more valuable for the organization because of taking part in decision making and handling the leader's activities. With the help of the learning work culture, employees learn to work with rules and regulations as well as within the set time frame. All these activities come under leadership.

2.1.6 Developing a positive mindset

From the research of Chirico and Nordqvist (2010) and Wilton, et al. (2011), it is determined that learning work culture plays a major role in the success of the firm and to have the consistency in the business. The reason in this is that learning work culture provides a lot of

career opportunities at the internal and external level. It is quite necessary for the firm to perform better and to increase the trust among the employees regarding sustainability in the job. Because of this, it can be determined that developing a learning work culture helps the firms to develop a positive mindset of the employees. Regarding this, from the research of Closs et al. (2011) and Jormanainen and Koveshnikov (2012), it is illustrated that due to the maximum workload and continues change in the work and work environment affects the motivational level of the employees. Because of this, the employees look towards changing for another job that affects the work and the work environment of the firm as well. So, in this concern of this, it is determined that if a firm follows the learning work culture then it motivates the employees and helps them sustain in the firm for a long-time period. Apart from this, from the research findings of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) and Closs et al. (2011), it is determined that developing the learning work culture makes a positive image of the firm in the employees' mind as well as in the market. The positive image of the firm in the employees' mindset helps to generate the new ideas and the strategies that can play a major role in the success of a company along with substantial growth in firm's customer base. So, it can be defined that in order to generate new ideas and strategies, there is a vital role in the positive mind set of the people. In the favor of these statements, from the research study of Costello et al. (2011) and Bennette and Vickers (2012), it is determined that there are different companies that use this concept in their business prices and now they are effectively operating in the international market. In this, Tesco, Apple, etc. are the major firms that also try to develop a good learning work culture and it helps to make the positive mindset of the people. Due to this, all employees of these firms perform well and put their full efforts in the success and the growth of the firm. That is why; all these firms have a large consumer base and significant market value as compared to other firms at an international level. In like manner, there is also a lot of companies like Woolworth etc., that are facing different problems within the organization due to the

absence of an effective learning work environment. So, eventually, it can be determined that developing the learning work culture is quite effective for the firms.

On the other hand, in the research of Bloom et al. (2012) and Chirico and Nordqvist (2010), it illustrated that learning work culture is not only help to develop a positive mindset of the people but also it is helpful to decrease the employees' turnover rate and to increase the satisfaction level of the employees along with the customer base. It is necessary for the firm to get success in the market and to overcome the different business and marketing issues. The reason in this is that there is an increasing level of the competition that creates problems for the companies to sustain their position in the industry and the customer. So, if the firm successfully provides the satisfaction for the employees then it helps to provide effective products and services for the customers which enhances the customer base of the firm. The learning work culture also helps the employees by providing them with promotion in the firm as well as by learning different things related to the business and the market. It helps to reduce the employees' turnover rate and helps in the workplace sustainability.

At the same concern, Fullan (2014) and Buckingham (2013) defines that a positive mindset can overcome the organizational issues which are helpful to make the organization successful in this competitive environment. Lack of learning work environment can make the employees less productive as well as the organization less profitable so it is necessary for every organization to create a learning work culture within the organization in respect to set the positive mind of employees so that they can believe in themselves to face every challenge or issue during their work. This positive mindset can give various benefits to the organization like employees' career success, increase the productivity, build leadership skills, increase the teamwork, build decision making power as well as motivating the employees in respect to their work. These entire activities lead towards the success of the organizations & the employees within the organization. Furthermore, Frese and Keith (2015), Fullan (2014) and Chirico and

Nordqvist (2010) also describe that the learning work culture is core in the organization to create interpersonal relations with the help of positive mindset. Positive mindset reduces the stress that arises due to difficult challenges and workload within the organization. There are various ways by which a positive mindset is beneficial for the organizations. That is why the organization must create a learning work culture to increase positivity among the employees within the organization.

2.2 Learning work culture and workplace sustainability

In a similar way, in the views of Wolf (2013), Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) and Blok et al. (2015), it is determined that to increase the productivity of employees and the profit of the firm, it is quite necessary for the workplace to create the learning work culture as one of the effective and best solutions for the firms. The reason behind this is that the learning work culture makes a positive attitude of the employees towards the work and the working condition of the firm that encourages them to work hard and to show their full potential in the growth of the firm. Because of this, the learning work culture has its great worth in the growth of the firm as well as in the workplace sustainability. But at the same time, it is illustrated in the research of Zheng et al. (2010) and Cummings and Worley (2014) that developing a learning work culture within the firm is quite a time and cost consuming which creates the financial issue for the firm and also affect the market value of the firm. It is because in order to develop the learning work culture, there are different steps and changes that are done by the firm and they increase the cost of the firm. Because of this, it is stated in the research of developing the learning work culture in the firm and the workplace sustainability is time and cost consuming for the firms. This statement is supported by the research of Carmeli and Gittell (2009) and Çakar and Ertürk (2010) they stated that there is a vital importance of the learning work culture for the firm as well as they also stated that along with learning work culture, the workplace suitability also plays an essential role in the growth of the firm and to have a good customer base.

In the same concern of this, Closs et al. (2011) and Blok et al. (2015) defined that in order to manage the workplace sustainability; most of the international firms always support the innovation in the firm and also try to get the new ideas from the employees. The reason behind doing this is that it assists the firm to sustain the changes in the workplace and also increases the working efficiency of the firm as well as of the employees. At the same time, in support of this, it is also stated in the research of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) and Zheng et al. (2010) that firms prefer the innovation and the new ideas which assist the firm to grab more market opportunities and to increase the customer base. As well as, they also stated these ways of developing workplace sustainability are also helpful to make a unique image of the firm in the market and also suggest the ways of better CSR implementation. Because of this, it can be stated that the steps used by firms to develop workplace sustainability are the best ways to survive in this competitive working environment.

In favour of this statement, in the research of Evans and Waite (2010) and Chesbrough (2003), it is determined that most of the firms especially automobile and food-producing firms try to reduce energy and fuel costs. The reason in this is that the low investment in the fuel and energy helps to make an effective and eco-friendly working environment. In support of this statement Hager and Hodkinson (2009) and Costello et al. (2011) illustrated that increasing the use of fuel costs becomes a serious cause for the protection of the environment and the human health as well. It is because it releases harmful gas and affects the human health of those who work in the production process. So, in order to overcome this issue and to increase workplace sustainability, firms try to reduce energy and fuel costs. Because of this, it can be stated that along with the learning work culture the ways for workplace sustainability are also quite essential and helpful for the firm in order to sustain in the market and to have a good customer base.

Figure 2: Developing Learning Culture

(Source: Tjulin et al., 2010)

But at the same time, Tjulin et al. (2010) and Zheng et al. (2010), defined that although the use of the learning work culture at the workplace is quite essential to the firm but there are also different issues and challenges that firms face at the time of developing the learning work culture in terms of cost, employees' engagement, etc. Because of this, instead of developing the learning work culture, companies need to use the training development program in order to increase the employees' productivity. In opposite of this, from the research of Blok et al. (2015) and Csikszentmihalyi and Larson (2014), it is determined that the workplace sustainability also has its significant impact on the performance of the firm. Because of this most of the firms such as Primark use different ways and tools in order to increase workplace sustainability. It is because Primark is one of the leading international clothing retailers that provide its products in different countries. So, for workplace sustainability, the firms always try to have skilled and knowledgeable employees because it assists the firm to overcome the social impact and also provide a competitive advantage to the firm. Due to this, the workplace sustainability is one of the major aspects of the firm to survive in the market and to have a good customer base.

In like manner, from the research of Ones and Dilchert (2012) and Closs et al. (2011), it is illustrated that the learning work culture has its highest contribution to the success of the firms and also assist the firm to survive in the market. The reason behind this is that learning work culture increases the problem-solving skills of the employees that overcome the possibilities of rising any issue and conflict among employees within the firm. Additionally, the learning work culture also increases the sustainability power of the employees that makes easy the employees to handle the issues and conflict easily. Because of this, the learning work culture has a significant impact on the performance of the firm and also provides a competitive advantage for the firm as well. In the same context of this, in the research of Henning et al. (2009) and DuFour and DuFour (2013) it is defined that learning work culture makes an effective communication among the employees as well as the management department of the firm. It is because, in the learning work culture, employees are free to express their views and to do conversation with other employees, it increases the communication power of the employees and also increases the way of working of the employees. Because of this, the learning work culture has huge significance in a firm in order to make an effective and productive working environment.

Likewise, in the research of M. Wiernik et al. (2013) and Zheng et al. (2010), it is determined that nowadays, the competition has become very tough in the market that poses issues and challenges before the firm to sustain in the market and to have large market share. Because of this concern, it is crucial for the firms to have some change in the firm to increase sustainability at the workplace and to achieve the growth in the business. By concerning this aspect, Evans and Waite (2010) and De Mooij (2013) defined in their research by illustrating that developing the learning work culture is one solution for all problems that are ever used by the firm in its working practices. In addition, they also stated that most of the firms are using the learning work culture ways that are operating their business at the international level. The reason behind

this is that it manages all issues and also increases the employees' self-morale that assists the firm to successfully manage their business at an international level.

For instance, Primark is one of the major examples of this because this firm operates the business in most of the countries like UK, Spain, Italy, the USA, etc. So, in order to operate the business successfully and to have a growth in the business, firms use the learning work culture that can assist to successfully manage and control the business operation over the globe. Therefore, the learning work culture is quite important for the firm to survive in a competitive working environment and to increase the sales of the firm also.

Apart from this, as mentioned by Costello et al. (2011) and Hager and Hodkinson (2009), it is illustrated that decreased turnover of employees can also be said as one of the most issues that the firms face in the current working environment and affect the business of the firm. Therefore, firms would develop a learning work culture at the workplace to manage and control this issue and reduce the risks. Firms can develop the training and development programs for improving the skills of employees and motivating them. This can aid in improving the competency of firms and maintaining business consistency of firms.

Furthermore, from the findings of Skerlavaj et al. (2010), and Eteokleous-Grigoriou (2009) it is observed that workplace sustainability is also a great challenge before the firms, which causes issues in sustainability in the competitive market. For workplace sustainability, firms focus on the analysis of the internal and external business environment and decide their marketing and business strategies that can help the firms in managing the business and to enjoy large market share. Therefore, it can be said that apart from the learning work culture, the workplace sustainability plays a very important role in ensuring the survival of the firms in the competitive environment.

In contrast to this, from the findings of research of Gould (2009) and Du et al. (2010), it is defined that the focus on workplace sustainability and the learning work culture are two ways

that a firm can use to manage the business but at the same time, and all these ways affect the other business and marketing operation of the firm. As well as, they also increase the cost of the firm that eventually creates a financial problem that could be difficult to manage. For this reason, there is no wide use of developing the learning work culture, and the workplace sustainability practices within the firm. In contrast to this, Zheng et al. (2010) defined that developing the learning work culture provides an advantage for the firm by identifying the strengths of the firm and to determine the future opportunities for the firm. So, on the basis of this, it is easy for the firm to grab more market opportunities and to increase the customer base. Because of this, Zheng et al. (2010), in his research determined that the implementation of learning work culture, and workplace sustainability is important for the companies.

In the research of Chirico & Nordqvist (2010) and Hager and Hodkinson (2009), it is stated that the learning work culture increases the accountability of the employees that provides the advantage for the companies when it comes to increasing the profit by minimizing the risk and challenges. The reason behind this is that developing the learning work culture increases the knowledge of the employees and provides a better future platform for the employees. Because of this, it increases the accountability of the employees and increases the productivity of the employees also. That is why, Hager and Hodkinson (2009) stated that in the current business environment, the learning work culture plays a remarkably vital role in the success of the firm.

In support of this, from the research of Blok et al. (2015), it is determined that various alternative ways are available that a firm can use to develop a strong work culture and in this, formalized training and development plans are the best methods that a firm can use in order to develop the learning work culture. In the same concern of this, M. Wiernik et al. (2013) and Duffield and Whitty (2015) defined that in this way; firms provide training and development to employees in order to increase the skills and knowledge of the employees as well as to

minimize the risks at the workplace. Due to this, it can be reckoned as the best way in developing the learning work culture at the workplace within the firms.

Comparatively, in the research of Costello et al. (2011) and Wiernik et al. (2013), it is illustrated that giving recognition to the learning is away, which most of the firms use for developing the learning work culture. The reason behind this is that in this way, a firm encourages employees who have high skills and always try to learn new things within the firm. Because of this, in order to get encouragement and to get a reputed position in the firm, employees try to learn a new thing that makes a learning work culture within the firm. Due to this, a firm encourages employees is one of the major ways to develop the learning work culture within the firm. Correspondingly, in the views of Gould (2009), and Evans & Waite (2010) getting feedback on a regular basis from the employees is also a good way to develop the learning work culture. In the same concern of this, Hager and Hodkinson (2009) point out that the learning work culture also helps the firm to increase the reputation of the firm in the market. It is because the learning work culture increases the productivity of the firm as well as the motivation level of the employees that make the result of the high performance of the firm in the market. Because of this, the learning work culture is one of the best ways for the firms to increase the market share to get a competitive advantage in the market.

In addition to this, Blok et al. (2015) defined that the learning work culture in the organization plays a vital role in ensuring the sustainability in the competitive environment and in gaining the competitive advantage. The reason in this is that the increasing level of the competition in the market bound the firm to have some continuous change in technology as well as in the employees' capability. Because of this concern, the development of learning work culture within the firm increases the technology adoption capability of the firm and makes it easy for the firm to sustain in the competitive environment. But at the same time, this statement is not supported by the research of McAllister and McKinnon (2009) because in the research of

Wiernik et al. (2013) and Eraut and Hirsh (2010), it is determined that the learning work culture creates feelings of the irritation among the employees and also affects their capability to do their work. In support of this, from the research of Ones and Dilchert (2012) and Farndale et al. (2010), different surveys are conducted on the employees' learning behaviour within the firm and based on the analysis of the results found through all the surveys, it is determined that there is no more interest of the employees to learn different things within the firm. Because they considered that after getting the education and the learning, they got the job and after they got the job, they had to learn something in the firm which created a negative feeling and affected their working behaviour. Because of this, it can be stated that there is not any importance of the learning work culture for the firm as well as for the employees also. On the other hand, from the research of Rai et al. (2009), it is stated that workplace sustainability is provided with great importance within the firms for ensuring the market sustainability of the firms.

In this regard, a firm can use various methods and ways of ensuring workplace sustainability. Thus, firms can use tasks about their competitors, which can help in ensuring great sustainability at the workplace. The reason in this is making it easy for the firms to know the competitors' strategy and the ways that they use to sustain in the market. So, on the basis of this, firms can manage their businesses and working practices. Due to this, it can be interpreted that workplace sustainability plays a significant part in the market sustainability of the firms. In like manner, from the research of Škerlavaj et al. (2010) and Chirico and Nordqvist (2010), it is also determined that creating the workplace sustainability and the learning work culture are the same aspects, which assist the firms to flow with changes in an environment that in turn ensures the survival of the firms in a competitive market.

Moreover, it is also found in the research of Tjulin et al. (2010) and Frese and Keith (2015) that the learning work culture always helps the firm to stay updated and to keep their working

process as well as providing the strength of the firm in the competitive market. Due to this, there is a significant impact on the learning work culture on the working process of the firm. Furthermore, based on the results and finding in the research of Wang et al. (2009) and Goldin (2014), it is determined that stop being negative; be positive is also one of the effective ways that are also used by firms to increase the workplace sustainability. It is because this way helps in overcoming the possibilities of raising any issue and the conflict among the employees and also helps in increasing the productivity of the employees. Due to this concern, the workplace sustainability is quite helpful for the firm to increase the market value and the customer base. In addition to this, from the research of Wolf (2013) and Freeman (2010), it is illustrated that learning work is one of the major and only ways that can be helpful for the firm in increasing competitive market to sustain and to develop the consumer base. The primary reason behind is that without a learning work culture, it is not possible for the firm to increase the growth opportunities and to increase the employees' sustainability. It is because the leaning work culture helps the firm by increasing the feeling among the employees to share the idea. Sharing the idea provides the chance for the firms to make a more effective and achievable marketing strategy and also increases the productivity of the firm. Because of this, it can be determined that developing the learning work culture is quite significant for the firms.

Overcome the conflict and develop a long-term relationship:

In the research findings of Podsiadlowski et al. (2013), it is determined that to sustain in the working environment and to perform well in the market, the workplace sustainability plays a crucial role. In workplace sustainability, firms always try to have the fair policy and rules in the working environment that overcomes the possibilities of arising the issues and the conflict. It helps the firm to develop a good base of the customers and to have consistency in the business as well. In the same concern of this, from the research of Rai et al. (2009) and Henning et al. (2009), it is illustrated that for better workplace sustainability, there are different programs

related to the cultural management and the employees' motivations that are also conducted by the firms that help it enhance the business and to manage the unexpected risks. But at the same time, from the research of Sackmann (2011) and Goldin (2014), it is also stated that there are also different issues related to the cost, time, culture, issues that affect the work and working environment of the firm as well as it also affects the customer base of the firm. So, it can be determined that although workplace sustainability is quite effective

In the research of Folger et al. (2017), it can be defined that workplace sustainability leads towards the solutions to resolve the conflicts as well as it is helpful to create long term relationship between organization and employees as well as the relationship between organization and customers. This workplace sustainability provides the surety to the employees that their jobs are secured and they are valuable for the organization so they do not need to worry. These things increase the trust between employees and organization and the conflicts at the workplace are reduced related to employees. Furthermore, Pearsall and Venkataramani (2015) and Podsiadlowski et al. (2013) it is determined that this workplace sustainability creates a long-term relationship. Thus, workplace sustainability is essential so that conflicts can be reduced and increase the employees' satisfaction. For maintaining a long-term relationship, workplace sustainability is also necessary. Due to sustainability at the workplace, employees' turnover is reduced and employees think to stay with the current organization for a long time.

2.3 Challenges in Implementation of Learning Work Culture

Besides from this, in the research of Longoni et al. (2014) and Hsu and Fang (2009), it is identified that developing the learning work culture is effective for the firm, but at the same time, managing the cost and the other working operations are the key problems that create difficulties for an organization to develop a learning work culture. As well as, the effectiveness of developing the learning work culture is also limited and there is not any wide use within the

firm due to requiring lots of changes in the firms and lots of efforts to develop the learning work culture. Because of this, it can be interpreted that developing the learning work culture is effective but for a limited time and also affect the other working operations of the firm.

In opposite of this, from the research of Evans and Waite (2010), it is interpreted that instead of developing learning work culture, there are also different cultures such as controlled culture, competitive culture, creative culture, etc. that can also be used by the firm to make more effective working environment and to increase the customer base as well. The reason behind this is that the creative culture increases the creativity of the firm in terms of working operations, production, supply chain, etc. that provide the competitive advantage for the firms and increase the market value and reputation of the firm in the stiffly competitive market. Hence, there is an important role in the creative culture of the firm instead of learning work culture.

2.3.1 Gaps in the Learning Cycle

More than 90% of the nonprofit leader's was surveyed and the outcomes reported that leaders take care extremely regarding learning and actively struggle to model knowledge can distribute within their organizations. And most of the people appeared to be dedicating important resources for this work. The challenge in this report, leader's report, is describing clear goals towards learning, creating sufficient incentives to spend the time it gets to gain and distribute knowledge and designing instinctive processes which help to gain and spread knowledge.

The Goals Gap:

The majority of the leaders were interviewed to develop the knowledge about their leading strategies within organizations stated they were concerned about the learning work culture & how to successfully implement it within the company. However, one leader stated that the senior manager of the company has no organizational goals to be defined. In addition, six leaders among ten have revealed that they skip the metrics towards a learning work culture for

the company (Evans and Waite, 2010; Longoni et al., 2014). In case of insufficiency of metrics and goals, organizing knowledge resources, evaluating progress and controlling the behaviour of employees across the company becomes too hard to be a successful task to accomplish.

The Incentives Gap:

The opportunity of learning within the company which is a strategy provided by the learning work culture is capable of filling the initial gap within the learning cycle. However, creating a culture, which will inspire each member within the company in the aim of acquiring and distributing the required knowledge dynamically, will need a rewards system more than the clarity of a convincing goal – and in this point, half of the nonprofit's leaders were surveyed; in this survey, this issue was raised. In addition, in this survey, many leaders stated the impossibility of providing explanations for incentives towards individuals, for the group, or their whole company.

The Process Gap:

When the leaders are capable of listing clear learning goals which will effectively help the employees and the company to achieve its mission strongly; moreover, it's when the leaders become capable of inspiring the employees and the teams to reach the targeted mission and goals. However, one main question is left for numerous nonprofit staffers: How? What are the procedures which help the employees acquire knowledge, distribute it, and use it as a boosting tool for enhancing their impact? The initial step is the most necessary one where it illustrates the steps to make these procedures instinctive (Longoni et al., 2014). In addition, determining who requires the knowledge, where the best openings lie related to learning, and what structures fit best among the existing working manners of existing workers.

Likewise, the use of other cultures such as competitive and controlled can also be a good way that a firm can use to achieve competitive advantage and sustain its position in the market. Furthermore, as highlighted by Closs et al. (2011) and Evans and Waite (2010) in their research

that the workplace sustainability and the learning work culture, both are the major ways for the firm to sustain in the competitive market and to have a good relationship with its stakeholders. However, it can be said that learning work culture is quite effective for firms to have consistency in their businesses. It aids in creating a large customer base and reducing the employees' turnover, which improves the competitiveness of the firms. Along with this, the use of workplace sustainability ways is also effective for the firm to increase the working effectiveness of the firm and increase the productivity of the employees. It gives a competitive advantage to the organization. So, the learning work culture and workplace sustainability are helpful ways for a company to survive in the evolving market and to build a huge consumer base.

Key Research Gaps:

Throughout this study, numerous research gaps have been identified, and in the following section, the researcher highlights the key research gaps which needs to be addressed in the future. Firstly, research is still acquired in order to provide an examination on the effect of learning work culture and its implementation on the performance of the organization as their might future academic sources which provides better information and clearer explanation of the learning work culture's efficiency on enhancing the environment of the workplace, hence, increasing the performance of the organization. Secondly, future studies should conduct better primary data analysis as the number of interviewees and employees which conducted the research survey could be increased and it could be expanded to another county over the UK, as the researcher has focused on Primark UK, Liverpool branch.

2.3.2 Some common ways to promote workplace learning are:

1. Off-the-job training: under which case studies or classroom training is imparted. Problems solving attitude and skills are taught to meet business objectives.

2. Structured learning (at the workplace): In this training, the help of the external expert is taken in collaboration with the company. Expert guides for using the new technique, which motivates workers to understand new things and culture of motivation is developed within the organization.

3. Informal or grapevine learning: understanding the prevailing activities and problems in informal ways will open up the workers to explain their problems and share ideas for improvements. Informal communication is very effective as workers feel free to express their problems and solutions of which in itself is an improvement (Blok et. al, 2015; Ingenhoff and Fuhrer, 2010).

4. Implementation of human resource development programs, which include career planning, job rotation, etc. In addition, it motivates employees to grow within the organization.

5. Encouragement of participative model: Employees of the companies must be motivated to participate in the decision-making process of the company. Involvement in decision making will help in getting the commitment from employees and making them personally liable for their work. The participative model also encourages learning between employees as they share their views collectively for the success of the organization.

Figure 3: Learning Work Culture and its Outcomes or Benefits

(Source: created by the researcher- November, 2019)

2.4 Learners at the Workplace

It is clear that learning work culture is necessary for the sustainability of the firm. However, the learning work culture totally depends on the learners within the firms. Therefore, without knowledge of the learners in the workplace, it is very difficult to nurture the learning work culture in the workplace effectively. The appreciation of the background of the people at the workplace such as age, education, thought process and other characteristics to promote the learning work culture (Carmeli and Gittell, 2009; Han et al., 2011). The experience and past learning of the employees, their beliefs and perceptions about themselves should be considered while developing the learning work culture at the workplace. Learning of the learners develops over time based on their experience and exposure to the environment. A learning career contributes in the decision-making regarding working career and provides identity to the worker within a specific field at the workplace (Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010; Hager, 2009).

Furthermore, from the analysis of an Australian study, it has found that workers attended maturity or become mature show keen interest in learning. Although they were lacking the self-confidence, they occupied other qualities and skills that compensated the deficiency. This could be effective in managing the learning programs at the workplace (Nussbaum, 2016; Ahmad and Omar, 2010). It is found that the more aged workers show high propensity to have greater work experience with continuous learning at the workplace. However, the mature aged workers feel shy in the classroom learning due to their low literary rate but they could be more interested in task-related learning. The learning and teaching which occurs at the workplace when a trainer teaches the workers. The experienced workers could be trainers for younger workers who would respect them due to their knowledge and experience. As stated by Chirico and Nordqvist (2010), the workplace learning process can be said as a two-way process in which the learners and workplace interacts. The example of structure and agency makes it clear that an individual worker can put effects on the programs developed for learning at the workplace by rebuilding the work culture and by utilizing their skills and knowledge at the workplace for better productivity. The more aged workers have good experience and knowledge, which helps them in developing an effective work culture in the workplace.

As per the finding from the study of learning practices at the workplace in automatic manufacturing companies, workplace learning is the learning of skills, attitudes, and work through training and development program. The change in the environment requires changes in the workplace that is possible through effective learning. As changes in technologies occur in manufacturing sector such as Toyota rules, simultaneous engineering, total quality management, and just in time, new roles and responsibilities are built with required skills and knowledge (Noe et al., 2010; Aasen, et al., 2012). Therefore, learning at the workplace makes it possible for the workers to learn new skills for accomplishing new job roles and responsibilities (Evans and Waite, 2010). The continuous learning develops the skills and

knowledge of the workers at the workplace that improve their productivity and performance. However, the language difference poses challenges in the learning process for the learners. The language of learners may be different from the language of the trainers and that could pose challenges. Thus, translation techniques are used to overcome this communication issue (Hager and Hodkinson, 2009; Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010). But this technique is not effective. Learners feel uncomfortable while learning when the trainer does not physically/face to face involve in training. Workplace learning is becoming very difficult when the teacher-centred approach is replaced with a learner-centred approach.

As the study of the agriculture sector, learners are found resistant to adopt the changes or new integrated management system that include an open communication system, problem-based learning, and open discussion. The tropic fruit growers voted to an older style of learning in which the expert taught them what to do and how to do it. However, learners are moving away from their myths about this and showing their interest in learning new things that determine the success of changes in the management of workers in the agriculture sector (Hsu and Fang, 2009; Awan and Tahir, 2015). The experts intervene to teach them. The experts invested most of their times with learners in working carefully and effectively which helps the learners in understanding the system of pest control. Similarly, various other researchers found that the roles and responsibilities of the employees and employer put an impact on the learning at the workplace. There is a great difference found between the managers and employees in the context of their perception and attitudes, as they play different roles at the same time.

However, the ideal learners can be called to the self-directed one, determines their learning goals, and is engaged with others in learning at the workplace. These employees are productive assets for the employer (Hager and Hodkinson, 2009; Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010). Employers' role is to deploy the workers at the workplace and allocate the resources effectively while the workers are employed to accomplish the tasks to achieve the organizational goals.

Employees think of themselves and the employer thinks about the company, then this difference may put an impact on the learning at the workplace. Learning can never be part of the repertoire of the beliefs of workers. The workers do not choose to learn the activities, which they find meaningless for them. As per the study of coal miners, coal miners were sceptic about the training for work safety. This training aimed to transfer the responsibility of workplace safety to the coal miners from the mine management.

Figure 4: Blended Learning via Word-Based Activities

(Source: Hager and Hodkinson, 2009)

Individual learners at the workplace build a learning organization of learners, where the growth of the organization leads towards the growth and development of individuals. Learning at the workplace can lead the individuals towards career development within the organization through promotion (Spencer, 2002). The enthusiasms among learners for continuous learning and development of learning society and organization is required for developing effective learning work culture within the organization.

Jackson et al. (2011) and Bennette and Vickers (2012) pointed out that there should be democracy system at the workplace that may lead enthusiasm in workers to continue as a learner for life long. Contradictory results from reorganization strategies of the management

and learning at the workplace and pedagogies of the workplace learning may be comprised of the new oppressions and control techniques at the workplace. In various researches, it was found that some experienced workers working for a long time within the organization were paid less even after the exploitation of their learning and their skills (Argote, 2012). Therefore, interpretation of the learning environment at workplace is interpreted in the different form by every individual as no one within the organization share similar objectives and goals. Wiernik et al. (2013) and Baskerville, et al. (2016) pointed out that the interests of the individuals sometimes coincide and sometimes collide too. All the organizations are different from each other and the business rhetoric should not be the same for the organization in the public and private sector. It is because PSUs such as public service, nonprofit organizations, and hospitals are different from the private businesses in the form of capital structure, goods and services, organizational structure, client, bottom lines and others.

Jones and Martens (2009) and Spencer (2002) studied the relationship between teamwork at the workplace and lean manufacturing system where they found that issues in work of the individuals, turnover and absenteeism, and quality issues in work are the issues in teamwork. A few years ago, training, job classification, pay rates, and benefits and protection of the workers build boundaries of job within the organization. But teamwork for the training of the workers for job rotation has dismantled these boundaries. There are different types of training methods and techniques which are used to improve the knowledge and skills of workers at the workplace, as stated by (Carmeli and Gittell, 2009).

Therefore, cross-training of the employees, by providing them with multitask, and using other forms of the techniques of training, the employers can improve the skills and knowledge of the employees that in turn reduces the labour cost of employers (Chen and Tseng, 2012). In the same manner, communication among the workers at the workplace has become the highly valued part of the operation of an organization that determines the success of an organization.

Effective communication among workers helps in constructing solidarity among them. Therefore, training for the workers should be arranged to improve the soft skills of workers that in turn can ensure effective teamwork in an adverse situation.

The workers in the organization are expected to have good communication and problem-solving skills. It is because effective communication and problem-solving skills make them able to embrace the changes, goals of the organization, and policies of employers. However, most of the organizations offer different training programs to the employees to bring improvement in their communication and problem-solving skills (Conrad and Poole, 2012 and Bolman and Deal, 2017). The effective and problem-solving skills may be to convince the team members to put their collective work interest in improving the work condition and performance. As per the finding derived from the study of pulp and paper industry, workers are found reluctant to involve in the learning at the workplace due to conflicts among perspectives of the workers learning new skills under lean manufacturing system that the employers want to implement (Ones and Dilchert, 2012; Argote, 2012). Multi-skilled workers are more flexible and able to accomplish different kinds of the job at the same time. Furthermore, workplace learning is reckoned as an important factor that brings a competitive advantage to organizations. The investment in the development of the workers along with the exploitation of their skills and knowledge assists in improving their flexibility and performance and achieving their commitment.

However, as per the findings of this research study, workplace learning and lean manufacturing are connected. The employer wants effective outcomes from the production function which has to ensure the effectiveness of the workplace learning and lean manufacturing system. The employer has to negotiate with the union regarding decentralization, pay rate, and other matters. According to Closs et al. (2011) and Jones and Martens (2009), there are various determinants of the quality of work and performance of the employees at the workplace. The

workplace environment is deemed to be another most significant determinant of quality in work and performance of the workers. How good the environment is for motivating employees affects the desires of the employees to learn and to perform (Pravin and Kabir et al., 2011). The skills and motivation of the employees may influence error rate, level of innovation, output rate, and collaboration and cooperation at the workplace.

In the view of Wiernik et al. (2013) and Çakar and Ertürk (2010), the workplace environment factors shown above may lead to engagement or disengagement of workers at the workplace. From the survey of employee's engagement in a reputable company, it can be identified how the satisfied employees are showing their engagement in their jobs and works at the workplace. The degree of the engagement of the workers at the workplace depends on the workplace's condition and safety. The level of innovation, work flexibility, and length of service are some factors that have to be considered for ensuring the engagement of the workers. The employer has to consider these factors while ensuring that employees use their skills learned at the workplace in favour of the organization. The structural elements of these factors make the workers able to apply their skills and knowledge towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives in a consistent manner.

Furthermore, most of the organizations nowadays are using new techniques and methods for constructing the office building that would include the consideration of all factors. This attracts new employees, and retains the existing employees within the organization, and improves their productivity as well (Cummings and Worley, 2014; Argote, 2012). In the current scenario, many authors and researchers have suggested that the physical layout of the organization along with the effective management processes may improve the productivity of employees. The effective physical layout reduces the cost and increases the productivity that causes the improvement in the organizational performance.

As per the findings from the research of an independent firm on the environment at the workplace, the firm found that workplace design is rated highly by most of the respondents in the research process. This research was aimed to find the role of workplace design, workplace satisfaction, and productivity in improving the employees' engagement and workplace sustainability (Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010 and Boso et al. (2013). In this research, 90% of respondents and senior officials stated that the workplace design determines the productivity and performance of the employees. Hence, it should be effective and attractive. Apart from this, most of the executives stated that a well-designed workplace structure may contribute more than 22% increment in productivity and performance of the organization. Therefore, the organization should focus on developing an effective workplace environment and creating a design that leads towards the improvement in the productivity of employees.

Closs, Speier and Meacham (2011) and Carmeli and Gittel (2009) pointed out that many of the organizations still do not pay enough attention to the workplace environment and wellbeing of the employees. Based on the fact found from the research, about 40% of employees think that organizations focus on productivity and cost reduction only and do not consider the workplace environment. This leads towards the ineffective layout design and environment at the workplace. The major part of employees revealed that the workplace environment affects their attitudes and perception adversely and that leads the job disengagement and dissatisfaction at the workplace.

An employee continuously develops their understanding and skills about the job and task to get a successful future. It can be used different innovative and creative ideas to effectively and efficiently complete the organizational duties. There are different kinds of technological development at the workplace that can be used by learners to develop their skills and create an attractive environment of the organization (Achtenhagen et al., 2013; Jones and Martens, 2009). In this technical environment, organizational people can develop things about the

workplace environment. In order to provide effectiveness in the workplace environment, the learners play a vital role by developing their skills and knowledge at the workplace. The organizational goals can be effectively achieved by the employee and workers if there is no problem with the employees about their work. If the workplace people face the problems related to the skills and knowledge to complete the task timely, they need a learner.

At the same time, the workers and employees of an organization have an interest in learning a different kind of skills and techniques to provide effectiveness and quality in the occupied task (Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle, 2011; Wilton et al., 2011). For this, the training and development programs can be managed by the top management because the effectiveness in the work quality is necessary for the value of the company. The internal environment of the workplace provides formal learning where an employee learns effective and formal communication to develop the lifestyle. On the other hand, the co-workers in the workplace environment provide a different kind of informal communication to co-operate others. The learning capacities of the people are different because they can learn skills according to their interest, for example- in old age, most of the people do not have interest on the current technological products (Cummings and Worley, 2014). The skills of the employee can speedily develop by the people if they have the interest to complete the task and they enjoy the work. So, it can be said that the learning process at the workplace is a two-way process in which both learner and worker concentrates in the process. The learner has skills to make understanding about the things in the mind of the employee and employee needs to concentrate on the skill. An individual can provide their efforts on tasks according to their past knowledge and skill but the learner can also help them to effectively complete it with quality.

In the study of Conrad and Poole (2012) and Bloom et al. (2012), it is found that organizational people face a different kind of problems in the learning skills at the workplace because they do not have a good trainer. In this situation, if workers want to improve their skills than the

organization has a responsibility to provide an effective trainer who can provide good training. In this learning course, it is necessary to motivate the organizational workers to improve their skills and achieve the objectives. The training should be provided according to creating a learning environment in the workplace. It is because the workers of the company who is not interested in the new skill development, they can also agree on it. The workers should feel familiar in the learning environment so they can easily understand the need for the training (Wilton et al., 2011; Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle, 2011). The learning environment helps people to make a focus on skill and knowledge development. This environment also shows the employee that they are ready for training or not. If they are not ready then find out the reason and mitigate them effectively. The need of the learners should be analyzed to provide the training according to those needs. If the person knows the work than the trainer should not waste the time of organization on the already developed skill, he should provide extra knowledge.

2.5 Factors That Affect the Learning Work Culture and Workplace Sustainability

From the research of Costello et al. (2011), it is found that there is a vital role of the learning work culture for the firm, however various issues and challenges are there which the firms face at the time of developing learning work culture and workplace sustainability. The working culture followed by the organization is with the help of the modern or traditional concept for attaining competitive advantage in the market by satisfying the needs of the buyers and making them loyal to the company. In a similar way, the research of Blok et al. (2015) pointed out that most of the firms face challenges in ensuring the employees' engagement while developing work culture. It is difficult for companies to maintain organizational culture by following the specific policies and standards for a longer duration. In the same concern to this, the research of Wang et al. (2009) and Bolman and Deal (2017) explained that managers encounter challenges in reinforcing the internal environment for attaining the goals on time. The changes in values, ethics and the general framework of managerial concepts affect the learning environment as well as the performance of the employees.

There are different changes that are to be done by the firm to develop the learning work culture and all these changes affect the employees' motivation and perception. It is difficult for the manager to combine the efforts of each individual in a group due to different thinking and perceptual level. It is because adopting the changes in the working environment creates a personal and professional issue for the employees. Due to this, it can be interpreted that the employees' engagement is one of the major issues that is faced by the firm and it affects the learning work culture aspect of the firm.

2.5.1 Producing the Lean Machine: Modification in Structure of Organization and Relationships

Among the core aspects which successfully guided many changes in the organizational structure of firms are the implementation of lean thinking & learning principles, these aspects

aim towards improving the competence of internal developments; moreover, it aims towards decreasing the waste and successfully classifying the customer value. In addition, mobile computing and internet are considered as communication technology & communication & transformation devices which support these changes.

Key organizational changes:

- Reduction of hierarchical structure – Hierarchies is experiencing a lack of fast & instant reaction against demands of the changing market, such as forces for continuous innovation and reducing the cycle-time. Moreover, the hierarchies can be replaced by cross-unit organizational groupings with the aim of a decreased number of layers & a decentralized decision-making system (Costello et al., 2011; Costello et al., 2011).
- Blurred boundaries – In order to enhance the teamwork within the organization, it started implementing an effective strategy which removed boundaries and stopped working as diverse parts of the organization which aims towards enhanced results of teamwork. Moreover, a large number of boundaries have been noticed among the departments and the other job categories such as managers, professionals and technical workers, this has created the requirement of task-sharing knowledge within the firm.
- Teams like basic building blocks – In order to successfully create a continuous effective decision which aims towards decreasing inefficiencies and to raise the work processes in a fast pace, the organization has to implement a team-based structure due to the pressure which occurs in its growth.
- New management perception – The management of the firm aims towards building a strong worker-base which focuses on devoting the employees to achieve the goals and mission of the organization instead of obeying rules and orders for a long period. Meanwhile, the firms' goals are affected by blurred boundaries. For instance, the

employees will have more power and freedom to control over the managers who'll become more as followers instead of leaders within the company.

- Continuous change – It requires the organization to engage more within the cycles of expressing and restructuring its goods and services. The changes to be applied within the organization can be small or big and they are likely to spread within short periods of stability (Blok et al., 2015; Costello, et al., 2011). Among the changes to be applied within organizations, there are three types which can be distinguished such as metamorphosis (far attainment, primary change), migration (shifts for a new form) and elaboration (changes that increase some feature of work) which have been stated by Kling and Zmuidzinis.

2.5.2 Cultural Difference among Employees

In the words of Zheng et al. (2010), it is stated that among the main reasons which create issues within the firm to reach its desired goals and achieve success in managing an enhanced learning work culture and sustainability are the differences in the culture of employees, the complexities of superiority and inferiority among employees, and the negative views and attitudes of employees towards each other. The manager has efforts on the firm by following the top-down approach and neglecting the bottom-up approach to transfer the information within the management affects the long-term performance of the employees. It is because the employees are not free to share their ideas and suggestions with the management for increasing the efficiency of the company. The long level of hierarchy for establishing the communication among the employees, in the management creates difficulty in transferring the urgent information, within a limited time frame. The pre-determination of roles and responsibilities of the workforce acts as an obstacle for generating new ideas and concepts in the organization. On the other hand, the research of outlined factors which affect the learning work culture is

also ascertained by age, gender and education etc. among the employees that hamper the managerial efficiency of the business.

Figure 5: Measuring Cultural Capability

(Source: Zheng, et al., 2010)

The capabilities of the workers are referred by their capability of successfully interacting with other employees who come from different culture and different social and economic surroundings. Where successful employees are the ones who cooperate with individuals from different backgrounds. The cultural capabilities represent an aid for the evaluation of the employee's ability to effectively work with colleagues who refuse to share their native language, to celebrate different holidays, to share their beliefs, principles, or lifestyle with others. Moreover, for the current work environment, it is core to be capable of measuring the cultural capabilities which represent a factor of success for the individuals and the organizations. However, the cultural capabilities are difficult to find among workers within the organizations nowadays (Zheng, et al., 2010). Furthermore, many diversity issues can be shown within the organization, which leads towards a necessary evaluation of the employees' views and opinions about the diversity of cultures and cultural capabilities. Hence, the company needs

to make more efforts in working on cross-cultural skills which are core for the employees' career and for the organization. Among the cross-cultural skills, the following can be listed:

- **Awareness:** which represents the reaction of employees to other employees who are different than them. The employees must be aware of their reactions in such a situation. In case of difficulty in reacting about each other's culture, the organization has to organize programs which would work on changing the employees' views as well as their reactions to create an enhanced and positive working environment.
- **Attitude:** which represents a measurement tool for the cultural unfairness which the employees within an organization might have. It also represents an examination tool to test the acceptance of employees towards cultural diversity. For instance, some people believe that Muslims have bad manners and attitudes or Muslims are not good in comparison to Christians. These kinds of thinking affect the working environment & the work culture for everyone, especially the individuals who come from Islamic backgrounds, and it affects the company as well.
- **Knowledge:** which is defined as the beliefs and values of the employees that are related to equality and it can affect their performance. It has been verified that the employees who acquire discriminations display behaviour which reveals it. Many individuals aren't aware of their discriminative behaviour (Škerlavaj et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2010).
- **Skills:** which are core for enhancing the employees' cultural competencies & to accomplish the assigned working tasks. Among these skills, communication is the most necessary skill which should be improved by the employees in order to successfully interact with his/her boss, seniors and co-workers. The communication has two manners such as verbal and non-verbal communication, and it is core for employees to

have a full understanding of how communication manners and skills differ according to the culture of individuals.

Identifying Cultural Baggage:

In order to reach the desired cultural capabilities, it is core for the employees to determine their cultural baggage. The cultural baggage is defined as the main bag which holds all the beliefs, values, discrimination as well as habits of these employees who are part of the organization. Moreover, the cultural baggage of employees is defined by their work, feelings and liking and disliking.

In addition, it is identified that most employees have their own cultures through which they perform within the organization. This culture affects the employees according to who they are and what they believe (Bhattacharjee, 2013; Cummings and Worley, 2014). For instance, if an employee moves from the south to the north and changes his job, his culture would be different from his co-workers at the new job place.

Identify Different Communication Styles:

The diversity of culture among people leads towards different ways of communicating and diverse communication style. This difference in the way of communicating leads towards misunderstandings during their conversations where sentences can be used differently and can have different meanings when used by someone from a different culture. In this manner, the individuals within the firm can use a circular approach to express their opinions. In order to increase the knowledge regarding the different communication style, it is recommended for firms to develop an understanding of the entire form. It is also cored to understand that cultural diversity might affect the employees. In this concern, it is found that there are five kinds of communication styles which help to cover numerous cultures within the world:

- *Linear versus circular:* Linear communication style reaches the point straight ahead. It includes the telling stories in the circular discussion related to the main point.
- *Direct versus indirect:* In this style, there are direct statement included which are made for the individuals in a direct manner. Among direct communication, suggestions, implications and other cues help to make communication and this communication may be made by the third party, which helps to protect confrontation.
- *Detached versus attached:* This communication style aims to include the feelings and emotions where the attached communicated is the one which includes both, feelings and emotions. While the detached communication takes the side of impartiality (Zheng et al., 2010 and Škerlavaj et al., 2010).
- *Concrete versus Abstract:* The stories, allegories and examples which are used as an understanding tool for the issues under concrete communication. This communication style has a main focus on the specification by implementing theories, principles and data.
- *Intellectual engagement versus relational engagement:* This communication style directly states a disagreement. It involves a relational engagement with respectful feelings and ideas. Moreover, treading softly and being respectful of feelings and emotions which comes under relational engagement.

Essential Cross-Cultural Skills for the Workplace:

Within the organization, it is core to create a development of employee's skills and capability in respect to communicate and efficiently acquire an understanding of their co-workers for the success of individuals' career as well as organization. In the present time, it can be distinguished that diversity is continuously increasing rather than decreasing (Škerlavaj et al., 2010; Farndale et al., 2010). In this way, the factor which affects the people believes, values and work ethics is the endless cultural diversity which is impossible for each individual to

comprehend all other cultures as well as gain skills and knowledge in this world. Developing cultural capabilities increases the chances of accepting cultures but doesn't guarantee to understand all cultures. The developing culture programs aim towards acquiring basic knowledge of difference through the culture and their impacts which affects the people's values, work ethics and believes and work schedule. Hence, the employees and organization might be more understanding and show sensitivity towards them. There are some skills that are needed to be culturally capable within the organization. These skills are as follows:

- *Team building*: Which represents an essential step to achieve the organizational goals collectively. However, most individuals are keen to accomplish their tasks by themselves. Moreover, there are many cultures who prefer teamwork and collaboration. In these cultures, individuals are keen to finish their work by themselves which makes them discover more issues in these tasks. In this case, these individuals always need the company to reach the desired achievement. Therefore, building a strong team represents a great accomplishment for the company.
- *Communication*: The diversity in the communication styles is very helpful for the organization because it is an aid for employees to interact and to overcome issues (Bhattacharjee, 2013; Zheng et al., 2010). Therefore, it is core for organizational employees to learn many communication styles.
- *Time*: In different cultures, individuals tend to have different ideas at the same time as the balancing between their jobs and their social life and families.
- *Calendars and holidays*: Holidays and festivals differ from a country to another. These things are helpful for the organization to accomplish their works in other countries. Hence, organizational employees are required to have a cultural calendar to be aware of the different holidays in different cultures.

Working Through the Language Barrier:

Nowadays, within companies, it can be noticed that a lot of employees and co-workers are fluent in English although they belong to different cultures and countries (Zheng et al., 2010; Eteokleous-Grigoriou, 2009). This difference explains the importance of learning techniques which allows them to overcome the existing language barriers for the organization. Moreover, if a worker is not comfortable with another person's English, another person should adjust his/her English according to the person in which he/she is comfortable. In this situation, employees should be able to make the other person understand exactly what they want to say. For making the other person understand, employees can use simple words in addition to the vocabulary and small phrases which can be easily understood by the person. Although it can be annoying for the employees to adjust their language in order to make others understand better, it will be beneficial for the employees to find more respect for each other (Zheng et al., 2010). It can be the biggest opportunities for organizational employees.

There are various factors such as diversity, engagement, gender difference, communication, trust factor, recognition, leadership style, the structure of the organization, legal, economic, social and technological (Bhattacharjee, 2013). These are some external and internal factors which affect the work culture in the organization and workplace sustainability.

2.5.3 Lack of Role Clarity

In order to perform better and handle all the business operations effectively, developing the learning work culture is one of the major ways that assist the firm to get success in the market. In addition, from the research of Scheeres et al. (2010), it is stated that although developing the learning work culture plays a crucial role in the success of the firm but at the same time, there are different factors that affect the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. In this, lack of role clarity is one of the primary difficulties faced by a company that affects the learning work culture. For this reason, if there is no proper job allocation for the employees as

per their skills and the knowledge then it affects the employees' self-morale and creates the performance issues. In addition, from the research of Schroeder (2013), it is illustrated that every employee within the firm looks for effective and skilled match job and in the absence of this; they don't like to work and look for switching the job. It creates issues for the firm in the development or management of learning work culture and it also creates the workplace sustainability issue. Because of this, it can be determined that a lack of role clarity is the major issue that creates issues in the successful development of the learning work culture.

2.5.4 Lack of Clarity about Accountability

From the research of Singh (2001), it is determined that a lack of clarity about accountability is also one of the major reasons that affect workplace sustainability and the learning work culture. The reason in this is that different works are to be done by the employees during the job due to the increasing level of the competition and the changing need of the purchasers. But at the same time, sometimes employees are not clear about their role and the accountability that can also affect the employees' satisfaction level and their motivation level as well. Because of this, employees avoid having their involvement in the work and the working culture that creates a sustainability issue for the firms. In support of this, from the research findings of Škerlavaj et al. (2010) and Singh (2001), it is determined that lack of clarity about accountability also affects the work and the aim of the firm as well. It is due to the absence of clearance of the accountability which leads towards employees who cannot work and without the accomplishment of the work, firms can't complete its aim and the objectives. So, in regard to this, it can be determined that there are different issues including a lack of clarity about accountability that affect the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability of the firm.

2.5.5 Lack of Transparency

In the research of Škerlavaj et al. (2010) and Tjulin et al. (2010), it is determined that in order to get the success in the business, the transparency in the business and all the business decisions

is a must for the firms as it helps the firm to have good working ethics in the working environment and helps in the workplace sustainability. But at the same time, from the research of Szczepańska-Woszczyzna (2014), it is determined that if there is not any transparency in the business then it affects the decisions of the firm. It also affects the working mindset of the employees towards the working environment and the management as well. Sometimes, it also makes the cause of raising the conflict between the employees and the management that is not effective for the business purpose of the firm. because of this, Tjulin et al. (2010) and Farndale et al. (2010) emphasis the need for the firms and the management department of the firm to have the transparency in the business and all the business-related decisions for successful business management and the learning work culture.

2.5.6 Ineffective recruitment and selection process

In the research findings of Wambui et al. (2013), it is illustrated that for developing an effective learning work culture, there is a major role of the HRM determinant of the firm because of taking all major decisions of the firm. The reason in this is that HRM implements all the decisions according to the need and the effectiveness of the employees and the firm. So, in this, recruitment and selection are also one of the major parts of the HRM department of the firms. In this, the HRM department tries to recruit skilled and knowledgeable employees for better management and sustainable practices. In the same concern of this, from the research findings of Wang et al. (2009), it is defined that if there are any issues in the recruitment and selection, like hiring the wrong and unskilled employees then it creates so many issues such as employees engagement or collaboration etc. that cause to create an ineffective working environment. Because of this, it can be determined that an ineffective recruitment and selection process is one of the major factors that affect workplace sustainability and the learning work culture of the firm well.

Figure 6: Human Resource Plan

(Source: Wang et al., 2009)

Impacts of a Failed Selection & Recruitment System:

The employees represent the main factor to succeed within the competitive environment for every business. Therefore, the hiring process is the most important step within the organization in accomplishing its mission to find the right person for the company. However, there are many situations which can be observed during the selection and recruitment system fail. For instance, hiring the wrong individuals has a negative impact on the organization which leads towards difficulty in practicing the daily business operations and productivity. The lack of productivity of employees leads towards more than losing money. In addition, there are many ways which make the wrong selection process of employees very harmful for the company.

- **Turnover:** Hiring the wrong individuals for the position increases the employee's turnover ratio. If the hired person is not suitable for the position, it is essential for the company to replace him/her after finding out they are in the wrong position. Therefore, the company loses time, money and energy in order to find another candidate who's

more suitable for the job and to train him as well. Wrong selection of employees is maleficent for the organization in many ways including less productivity, frustration due to rapidly retraining and incapability of progressing by initiatives (Wambui et al., 2013; Frese and Keith, 2015).

- **Money:** This can be identified in the report of the Corporate Advisory Board of Washington, D.C. that the wrong selection and recruitment causes an increase in the employees' costs between 50 to 175%. This staff replacement costs cover many expenses such as job posting fees, training fees, wrong person's salary payment till the end of employment. If the organization hires the wrong person in the sales or accounts departments it can lead towards losing revenue and customers.
- **Morale:** Hiring and selecting wrong individuals can hamper the morale of good employees within the organization. They will feel that the company is failing to find suitable individuals for the available roles and the unsuccessful recruitment process of their company. If the wrong selection is done in upper management, other employees might reconsider their tenure. Apart from this, when the selection is done in lower-level employees, this activity will increase the workload for the current employees and decrease their morale (Wang et al., 2009; García-Morales et al., 2012). Wrong hiring also increases the negative attitude of the employees within the organization.
- **Confidence:** If wrong individuals are selected through the recruitment and selection process within the company, this failure impacts the company's employee's confidence negatively. Moreover, good existing employees lose their confidence by noticing the poor recruitment of their management. Meanwhile, a senior member can also lose their confidence in their abilities to select the appropriate individuals for the company.

Problems in Recruitment & Selection:

A successful selection and recruitment strategy will lead towards a high-quality of services & goods delivered by the employees within the company. Furthermore, the recruiting and selection procedure for employees is not an easy task. Therefore, the organization faces many issues such as advertising expenses and recruiting costs of managers.

- *Recruitment Strategy:* In the recruitment strategy, many issues are found to be the reason a recruitment and selection process fails. Therefore, the employers must determine if the selected individuals are the best choice for the organization, before composing the job posting. When the organization decides to hire new individuals, the costs for hiring new employees increases which include the recruitment costs, orient & training costs also. In the case of full-time employees, the labour cost will be more for the organization if it provides additional remunerations (Wambui et al., 2013; Gorla et al., 2010).
- *Expenses:* In case if the company decides to replace the hourly workers, it will be six months wage approximately for the organization. Meanwhile, if the company decides to replace individuals who are earning a salary. at the same time, if the organization decides to replace the person who earns a salary, it will be the one and half year salary for the organization. These estimations are determined based on 2007 figures that were analyzed by the firm of management consultant “The Hay Group”. The recruitment costs contain various factors such as professional membership, college recruiting trips, advertising spaces and job fair (Wang et al., 2009 and Wambui et al., 2013). If any company decides to hire the employee through outsourcing, this can relieve the organization of the responsibilities related to recruiting and training employees.

- *Interviewing skills:* The interview skills are a core factor to hire the appropriate individuals where the lack of interview skills leads towards the wrong selection & wrong recruitment. For instance, if there is a need to hire a manager for the finance department, in this situation, the HR is not able to take interviews of applied candidates for the manager post because there is a need to know about how much knowledge that candidate has in the concerned department. In this manner, the organization should form a panel with few members who know this field to successfully find the right candidate for this manager post.
- *Promotion from within:* If an organization successfully selects a talented individual it means that it is saving money. The favouritism is another issue in the recruiting and selecting process within the organization. Moreover, the senior management shows favouritism at the time of promotion of employees. These activities of the management decrease the motivation of the existing employees, which leads towards wrong behaviour from existing employees during the operations (Wambui et al., 2013).

2.5.7 Attitudes and Perception of the Employees

According to Li (2012), how the employees perceive and think, how are their attitudes, mindset, and temperament, have a direct impact on the work culture. Moreover, the personality of the human beings in the organization affects the learning and establishment of the sound work culture at the workplace. It is elaborated in the research of Wilton et al. (2011) that two people cannot look the same and cannot have the same experience and same attitudes. This affects the work culture at the workplace, which in turn has a great impact on the sustainability of the organization.

In the same concern of this, from the research of Ones and Dilchert (2012), it is stated that employees' stress is also one of the major issues that are also faced by the firm at the time of implementing the learning work culture in the firm. The reason for this is that there are lots of

works which needs to be done by the employees and increase the work stress level on the employees. So, with work stress managing the learning work culture is one of the major issues for the employees that is why it creates the hurdle for the firms to successfully implement the learning work culture. In the support of these findings, it is also stated in the research of Schroeder (2013) and Wilton et al. (2011) that negative attitude of the employees is also one of the major causes in the development of the learning work culture. They also stated that the positive attitude of the employees helps the firm by increasing productivity and by generating new ideas in the business. Because of this, the positive learning attitude is quite necessary for the firm. so, by concerning this aspect, it is stated by Jogulu (2010) and to Li (2012) that the negative attitude of the employees creates the negative feeling towards the work and the job that makes the cause of ineffective implementation of the learning work culture. As well as, employees with negative attitude also creates conflicts and issues among the employees. Because of this, it can be interpreted that the negative attitude of the employees is one of the serious issues for the firm to successfully implement the learning work culture.

With respect to all things, it can be determined that a negative attitude and the perception of the employees affect the working environment and the sustainability practices of the firms.

2.5.8 Decision Making Process

In the words of Çakar and Ertürk (2010), the way of the flow of information across the hierarchy of the organization and decision-making process affects the work culture. A participative decision-making process is more valued among the employees that cause a positive work culture at the workplace.

At the same time, in the research of Chirico and Nordqvist (2010), it is illustrated that low decision-making process of the firm is also one of the major factors that affect the learning work culture of the firm. It is because if the decision-making process of the firm is slow then it affects the work of the firm as well as of the employee also. The delay in the decision-making

process also creates the issue for the firm to successfully implement any policy and the strategy within the firm and also create the business issue for the firm as well. Because of this, it can be interpreted that the low decision-making process of the firm is one of the major issues for the firms that affect the learning work culture of the firm.

Likewise, the research studies conducted by Gorla et al. (2010) and Çakar and Ertürk (2010), also determined that if the decision making power of the firm is low then it affects all the operation of the firm related to marketing, human resources, etc.; and the delay in the decision-making process of the firm makes the cause of low involvement of the employees in the work and it also arises the conflict in the employees as well. Due to this, it can be determined that the low decision-making power of the firm is one of the major issues that are faced by the firm and create a sustainability issue for the firm as well.

The effect of organizational culture on decision making:

Since organizational culture has been defined to employees then it becomes easier to analyse the connection between the decision-making and organizational culture. However, there is no doubt that in organizations every decision is made by the employees as per defined organizational culture which influences the employees. Usually, organizational culture can be divided into two parts such as strong culture and weak culture. According to Çakar and Ertürk (2010), strong organizational culture is an effective cultural environment which influences the organizational decision deeply in contrast to weak organizational culture.

The organization's original culture can be related to the organization's strong culture and weak culture in terms of scalability of organization and employee's liquidity condition. In respect to result, a strong organizational culture can decide how the staff members who pose with unity attitude respond towards the stimulus. On the other side, weak organization culture has a different environment which influences the staff members who have a different attitude

towards the response. This simply states that a similar decision can make a huge difference in two different organizations if there is a difference in organizational cultures.

Cambell and Nash (2010) also stated that with a strong cultural environment, organization decisions are accepted easily in comparison to a weak culture where employees have doubt on the decision and that might develop barriers in the implementation of it. However, the organization culture creates a huge influence over the decision made by its staff members in such a manner that decision might get accepted or rejected. In support to this, Chirico and Nordqvist (2010) and Gorla et al. (2010) added their point of view that when organization manager makes any decision then he/she should consider different points or factors to ensure that decision made can work efficiently or not.

An organization with a strong culture somewhere limits the manager choices and power to make a decision in order to manage the function of management efficiently and effectively. It is very much clear that an organization culture establishes policies and regulation related to responsibilities and duties which employees need to perform and which they don't need to perform. In concern to this, the first hypothesis demonstrates different groups with different degrees of culture environment and this cultural difference is reflected in their general well-being and individual success by attaining their own goals.

But at the same time, in the words of Freeman (2010) and Çakar and Ertürk (2010), it is determined that although decision making is one of the most important aspects of the firm and play a major contribution to its success, at the same time, there are different committees in a company which handles all decision making processes and every firm tries that there should not be any impact of these decision making processes in the business and workplace sustainability of the firm. As well as, there are different committees that are also made by the firm to manage these types of issue and to have good control over the business as well. Due to

this concern, it can be illustrated that there is not any role of the low decision-making process in the workplace sustainability of the firm.

How an organizational culture enhances a company:

The organizational culture represents a core element within the company to enhance its development and performance through developing a working culture which facilitates the growth and the success of the firm. Concerning this, Çakar and Ertürk (2010) Indicate that the organizational culture represents an enhanced tool to facilitate the desirable working environment which boosts the employees' engagement within the organization and to contribute to the success of the company. Meanwhile, Freeman (2010) states the significance of the organizational culture within the process of development of leadership which could make the participation of employees easier within the decision-making and to encourage them to enhance their performance in the aim of reaching the individual and the organizational goals effectively. Moreover, it benefits the company where it can grow the business and achieve high rates of growth. However, Gorla et al. (2010) state that the focus on organizational culture has a lot of advantages for the company in the aim of developing an encouraging environment to make employees share their knowledge & it also enhances the performance of their roles & responsibilities perfectly. Meeting the organizational expectations and achieving the objectives effectively can be very helpful for the firm. In the views of Chirico and Nordqvist (2010), the organizational structure plays a core role within creating the brand image of the firm which identifies the company and shapes how the employees will interact at the workplace. Moreover, healthy work culture is a source of motivation for employees and it increases their commitment and loyalty towards the management, it also develops a strong relationship amongst employees. In addition, creating a healthy work culture creates a healthy competition at the workplace which develops a sense of unity within the firm. Meanwhile, Cambell and Nash (2010) argue

that the appropriate organizational culture is the listed policies which guide the employees to develop a sense of direction within the firm. Moreover, it brings up many opportunities for the employees to enhance their work performance which will encourage them to be engaged within the firm and to contribute to its success.

How can organizational culture undermine decision making?

Based on the study of Business Weekly (2009), the organizational structure implemented within the firm affects the decision-making process of the firm. A strong organizational structure affects the attitude and the behaviour of the employees which also reflect in the decision-making of the firm. However, if the company implements a weak organizational culture, it will affect the decision-making process within the firm because it affects the morals and the engagement level of the employees which leads towards a low decision-making quality. Hence, the different cultures make a difference within the firms in two aspects; the strong culture allows the decision-acceptance easily, whereas the weak culture makes the staff doubt the decisions taken by the firm and face difficulty in implementing decisions. Furthermore, it is possibly mentioned that the organizational culture limits the choices taken by the management and the employees in the aim of making decisions to manage the firm's functions. It is due to the organizational culture which controls the decisions of the firm (Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010; Freeman, 2010).

2.5.9 Leadership Style

Similarly, Jogulu (2010) stated that the management and leadership style at workplace determine the work culture in the organization. Autocratic and participative leadership style affects the performance and productivity of employees differently. The autocratic leadership style creates fear and stress among the employees at the workplace that affects their performance adversely. The participative leadership style creates a friendly environment and improves the work culture and shared value among employees. This improves their

productivity and performance towards the effectiveness and sustainability of the organization. Moreover, in the research project of Wilderom et al. (2011), it is illustrated that leadership plays a major role in the success of the firm because of handling all the work and the employees as well. So, if the leaders of the firms are not effective and notable to handling work properly then it affects the work and the working culture. Because of this, it can be stated that ineffective leadership affects the work of the firm and it also creates issues for the firm to develop a good and effective learning work culture.

Figure 7: Different Leadership Styles

(Source: Gandolfi and Stone, 2017)

Relationship between organizational culture and leadership behaviour:

The organizational culture at workplace identifies the qualities of the work environment. It is core for the employees to fit in the firm's culture. The culture illustrates the surrounding within the firm which identifies and shapes the working enjoyment, work relations and work processes. It also creates an individual's behaviour (Cohen-Meitar et al., 2009; Costello et al.,

2011). According to Closs et al. (2011), culture incorporates assumptions, beliefs, values, attitudes and behaviours which are shared among individuals. It reflects the learning outcomes of previous life experiences which the employees bring to the company. However, when the owner of the firm, the executives and the staff contribute to the decision-making process and the strategic direction, it influences the company's culture significantly. The organizational culture of firms has a powerful effect over the leadership behaviour within the company as the principal values of the company start from the leaders who demonstrate a certain behavior to lead to employees (Jogulu, 2010; Wilderom et al., 2011). The leadership within organizations has a significant role in the development of a successful and strong organizational culture as it represents a guide for the junior workers to follow the given values and beliefs which decide the development of specific organizational culture. For instance, the participative style of leadership in an organization allows the workers to share their opinions about the decision-making process which opens the communication opportunities within the firm's management and it allows the firm to encounter issues and concerns from different opinions and aspects. Hence, it helps to develop an organizational culture which could be supportive and favourable for the employees to share their views and opinions to the management and to help enhance the quality of the decisions taken.

2.5.10 Environmental and Economic Factors

In support of this and with the respect of these findings, in the research of Baker et al. (2010), it is defined that developing the learning work culture and using the different aspects for workplace sustainability, there is a vital role of the employees because any change in the firm starts from the employees and also ends on the employees. The sustainability in the business practices is achieved with the help of environmental, economic and social factors ethically attained by the company. It is because employees are valuable assets for the organization and play an important role in satisfying the needs of the customers. Due to this, if there is lack of

employees' engagement in the development of a learning work culture then it is not possible for the firms to successfully manage the workplace sustainability and develop the learning work culture in the firm. Because of this, it can be determined that employees' engagement is a key factor that affects the learning work culture and workplace sustainability.

Additionally, in the research of Jackson, et al. (2011) and Baker et al. (2010), it is determined that the continuous change in the technology is one of the major issues for the firm in the development of learning work culture. It is because of the unceasing change in the need of the buyers and the way of businesses behave, there is also a continuous transformation in the technology because updated technology provides the additional advantage for the firms and also increases the customer services of the firm. But at the same time, this continuous change in technology makes the cause of creating hurdle in the development of the learning work culture. It is because the technological change in the firm affects the overall working process of the firm and also affects the work of the employees. Due to this concern, it can be stated that technological change is also one of the major issues that affect the learning work culture of the firm.

Advantages of environmentally friendly business:

The individuals' concerns about protecting the environment have increased and it has caused the needs of businesses to consider environmental protection while conducting its operations and activities. They have started focusing on the preservation of environment and natural resources. For instance, the firms can focus on products such as solar hot water systems, rainwater tanks, etc., which can help to reduce the reliance on natural resources. Meanwhile, using recycled materials like recycled plastic and rubber can be very effective in the manufacturing of office products. Moreover, some businesses now engage the environment protection through conducting meetings over the phone and by organizing calls instead of travelling in the aim of reducing air travel and minimizing the effects of the business' activities

on carbon footprint. Such activities which protect the environment and the natural resources are useful in the aim of reducing the operational costs of the company. For instance, recycling the used materials allows the company to decrease the production costs at a remarkable level (Schroeder, 2013; Blok et al., 2015). Meanwhile, focusing on keeping the operations of the company environmentally friendly allows it to develop a good image among the customers which helps increase the buyer attention along with the augmented sales and profitability. In relation to this, Carmeli and Gittell (2009) mention that firms which focus on environmentally friendly products and operations have more consumers than other companies (Trevarthen, 2011). However, Wolf (2013) argues that focusing on the environmental aspects helps increase the attraction of staff and retaining them which is crucial for the business to achieve a high productivity rate and organizational effectiveness. Moreover, the emphasis on the environmental aspects of the business represents a crucial factor for the company to increase its sustainability in the sector. It can also be helpful to achieve a competitive advantage over the competitors due to the low dependence on natural resources and improved handling of rising costs due to climate change in the aim of achieving long-term success.

Supporting to this, Blok et al. (2015) also state that the increasing competition and the changing in the consumer demands empowers the company to create and implement changes in the business and the management operations. In this, change management is also one of the major important parts that are done by the firm to manage the increasing level of the competition. So, as it is a lengthy process because it changes the entire work and the working condition of the firm. Due to this, it can be stated that it is one of the major factors that create the learning work culture of the firm.

But at the same time, an opposite perspective comes from the research of Carmeli and Gittell (2009), it is determined that interesting the current field of the employees is the major factors that affect the learning work culture of the firm and it can create the business and customer

base issue for the firm as well. Additionally, the reason behind this is determined in the research of Carmeli et al. (2010) by illustrating that most of the employees who work in the firm sometime don't feel comfortable due to the job, position, and the rules and regulations of the firm. Because of this, these types of employees create the issue for the firm to develop a good learning work culture and the customer base. That is why; it can be interpreted that the current field of the employees represents one of the major factors that affect the learning work culture of the firm.

Expenses and Management Practices in the Implementation of Learning Work Culture:

In the support of these findings, in the research of Carmeli and Gittell. (2009), it is said that the cost is also the major issue that also affects the learning work culture of the firm. The major reason behind is that to develop the learning work culture, firms need to conduct some programs, etc., that leads towards the extra costs and it affects the other business operations of the firm. Due to this, it can be concluded that the costs and expenses represent a core factor which affects the learning work culture of the firm.

At the same time, in the study of Evans and Waite (2010), it is explained that management practices are also one of the major issues for the firms in the development of a learning work culture. The reason behind this is that in order to successfully develop the organization's working culture; the management of the firm plays a significant impact. So, in case if any miss management and non-effective management practices, it is not possible for the firms to manage or develop the learning work culture. Due to this, it can be interpreted that the management practices are also one of the major causes in the development of learning work culture. In support of this, in the research of Henning et al. (2009) and Carmeli and Gittell. (2009), it is stated that the organizational culture and climate represent a serious issue for the organization to develop a successful learning work culture.

It is because, in the organization, there are different employees those are different in terms of sex, age, culture, value, etc. So, in this concern, in the development of the learning work culture, there is a diversified range of programs and functions used by numerous companies so it is not possible for them to manage all the programs, functions and processes according to every employee. Due to this, it is a considerable issue for the firm to the successful development of workplace sustainability and to develop the learning work culture. So, by concerning all the aspects, it can be concluded that organizational culture is, itself, one of the key problems that create more issues for the companies at the time of developing the learning work culture.

As well as, in the views of Kinman et al. (2011) and Evans and Waite (2010), it is also determined that although, different factors affect the learning work culture at the same time, different factors also affect the workplace sustainability in the firm. It is because the workplace sustainability is also one of the major business practices for developing the business and for this, different ways that are used by the firm. In addition, in the research of Ones and Dilchert (2012) and Carmeli and Gittel. (2009), it is determined that demographic difference in the employees is one of the major serious causes in the workplace sustainability. The reason behind this is that due to difference in the employees as per the demographic regions, the manager of the firm faces the issue to successfully implement different rules and regulation, policies, CSR, etc., that affect the market image of the firm and create the hurdle in the successful business practice.

2.5.11 Staffing Policies of the Organizations

In the same concern of this, it is also determined in the research of Bloom et al. (2012) and Wilton et al. (2011) by illustrating that there are different firms from where there are different policies and the procedures that are used by the firm regarding hiring the employees. Hence, from the research of Gloldin (2014), it is determined that most of the firms consider the male and some of the firms consider the female staff that is why it creates the business issue among

the employees. Because of this, it can be stated that demographic regions are also one of the major factors that affect the learning work culture of the firm and also creates the hurdle for the firm to successfully handle the business.

In the regard to this, in the research findings of Wilton et al. (2011), it is determined that due to the difference in the culture, firms also faced the issues related to the staffing policies. The reason in this is that due to the difference in the culture, firms have to make the strategy and the plan by considering all the cultural values of the employees that are a big challenge for the firm.

Power and Position in the Organization:

On the other hand, from the research of Zheng et al. (2010), it is also stated that there are different employees such as managers, leaders, etc., that has their vital role in the successful development of the learning work culture. So, if all these major key employees of the firm don't play their role effectively in the learning work culture then it also affects the learning work culture and also makes the cause of extra cost for the firms. Because of this, it can be finalized that the role of managers and the leaders are quite important in the success of developing the learning work culture and that is why it is also known as an issue in the development of learning work culture.

Working Environment at the Workplace:

From the research of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) and Goldin (2014), it can be distinguished that the work environment is the main factor which significantly influences the learning work culture. It is also supported by Closs et al. (2011) that the globalization & liberalization have caused the exchange of people across the borders for working in the organizations located across borders. It also caused cross-cultural issues which increase the need for creating an enhanced working environment despite the diversity of cultures. Similarly, Costello et al.

(2011) discuss that relationship with colleagues is also among the core issues which affect the learning work culture of the company. This is due to the availability of a various range of jobs & job-posts in the company that creates the difference in the professionalism of the employees as well as also affecting their working conditions. Hence, enhancing the relationship among employees represents a big challenge for the firm which creates challenges for the company to achieve high growth.

Poor Performance Management:

In the research of Wolf (2013), it is illustrated that the performance of the management decides the successfulness and the unsuccessfulness of the firm. It is because all the success of the entire work of the firms is depended on the performance of the firm. So, if the performance of the firm is not good and effective then it affects the aim and objectives of the firm as well as creates the issue in the development of the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. Similarly, from the research findings of Yeo and Pang (2017) and Wolf (2013), it is determined that despite there are different ways that are used by the firm for managing the performance of the firm but various internal and external issues also affect the performance of the firm and create the sustainability issues. It directly influences the performance of the firm and also the brand image of the firm in the market. Because of this, it can be stated that the poor performance of the firm is also a significant issue that the firm faces in the successful development of the learning work culture and workplace sustainability.

Ineffective Culture Management:

From the research findings of Zheng et al. (2010), it is illustrated that culture is a significant factor that is considered by the firm at the time of managing the business and to expand the business globally. So, culture management is a major aspect for the firms to get success in the market. But in the research of Trevarthen (2011), it is also determined that if there is a lack in

the culture management then it affects the work and the working environment of the firm as well.

2.5.12 Level of the Competition in the Market

Schroeder (2013) explains the competition and the changes required for the customers is increasing regularly considering the challenges which affect the organization's workplace sustainability. Relating, Trevarthen (2011) and Blok et al. (2015) which state that regular focus on the consumer demands in the production causes high-production costs and increases the financial burden which affects the workplace sustainability.

Relating to this, Wolf (2013) research illustrates that the rising level of the competition in the industry also affects the workplace sustainability of a company. This is due to the increasing level of the competition where firms always try to change the price and quality of the products to sustain in the competitive market. This change in the price and the quality creates the workplace sustainability issue for the firm. Due to this, it can be interpreted that increasing the level of the competition in the market and the continually changing consumer requirements are the major hurdles for a company to develop workplace sustainability.

2.6 Factors of Work Environment That Contribute to The Success of An Organization

2.6.1 Effective Long-Term Strategies and Organizational Success:

In the views of Jackson et al. (2011), it can be determined that different factors play a major role in the success of the firm and to increase the customer base in the managerial activity of the firm. In the same manner, Jackson et al. (2011) further stated that formulating the best strategy is one of the key factors that assist the firm to get success in the business and to expand the consumer base. The strategies are the plans formulated by the executives for achieving long-term goals and creating goodwill in the market by gaining a competitive advantage over the competitors.

According to Blok et al. (2015), the strategies are predetermined by the company for providing the action plan to the employees and staff members so that it is easy to accomplish the organizational goal, within the limited time frame. It is because formulating the best business strategy provides a right direction for the firm to achieve the goals and aim of the firm that makes easy for the firm to get success and to successfully implement these strategies in the business. Because of this, it can be stated that developing good strategies for business is one of the major effective ways for the firm to get success.

On the other hand, Carmeli and Gittell (2009) and Jones and Martens (2009) explained that the company, by creating product differentiation in its offering, is able to create distinctive identity in the market. It is because the product differentiation strategy built a competitive edge over the competitors due to innovative and creative ideas. In support of this, from the findings of the Henning et al. (2009) and Jackson et al. (2011), it is illustrated that managing and developing people is one of the effective ways that is used by the firm to get success in the business and to expand the business. The reason behind this is that nowadays, people want growth and learning work culture as well as some liberal rules and regulations in the business. So, by concerning these aspects, it is easy for the firms to get success and to sustain for a long time in the competitive market. Because of this, it can be depicted that managing and developing people is an effective way for companies to become successful in the market besides expanding their consumer base.

2.6.2 Honesty and Loyalty of the Employees:

In like manner, from the research of Carmeli et al. (2010), it has been determined that the good and honest employees are beneficial for the organization to make its functions successful in the dynamic environment. The employees are the assets of any organization and are the key persons, who interact with the customers. The employees are the face of an organization so the managers must keep the employees motivated and aware of the recent practices. The creation

of a decentralized organizational structure with the help of flexibility in terms and conditions assist the employees to play an active part in the crucial decision-making process of the company. The development of voluntary participation of employees in the managerial framework helps in implementing innovative and creative ideas for the success of the organizational functions.

In order to attract talent & retain the qualified & competent employees, it is core to include a healthy and supportive working environment within the firm. Mainly, the desirable working conditions increase the satisfaction of employees and results in their commitment and loyalty towards the management and organization (Carmeli et al., 2010 and Closs et al., 2011). Meanwhile, the loyalty of employees represents a core concern for the companies due to the high investment in recruitment, training and retention of the employees. The loyalty of the employees and the performance with honesty and integrity allows the firm to achieve the best outcomes in terms of performance and quality. The performance's quality is necessary to achieve the desired goals and achievements in personal and organizational level (Chirico and Nordqvist, 2010).

In support of this, the research of Chirico and Nordqvist (2010) determined that honesty, truthfulness, reliability, accountability, obligation, effective leadership, self-esteem, etc., are the key determinant factors at the working environment, which are responsible for making the organization successful. Also, in the research by Closs et al. (2011), it has been depicted that creating a friendly and supporting working environment facilitates in increasing the profit margin because there are effective communication and coordination among the employees.

2.6.3 Optimum Utilization of the Resources

Apart from this, from the research of Costello et al. (2011) and Zheng et al. (2010), it has been stated that better use of existing resources is a remarkable way, which is used by a company to get become successful in the market. It is because the optimum utilization of available

resources facilitates the company to increase its revenue margin by reducing the operational cost. The reduction in the manufacturing cost assists the company to offer the products easily to the customers for making them loyal for a longer period of time. In support of this, it is also elaborated in the research of Schroeder (2013) that the use of existing resources increases the validity of the resources and facilitates the firm by minimizing the production cost of the firm and by managing the risk of the firm in the production process. Due to this, it can be understood that the use of existing resources is one of the major ways that are quite helpful for the firm to get success in the market.

But at the same time, in oppose of this, it has been depicted in the research of Zheng et al. (2010) that although, the use of existing resources is quite helpful for the firm to get success in the market and to increase the market share but at the same time, due to continuous change in the technology, it is not possible for the firm to have continuous use of the existing resources. Because of this, it can be illustrated that the use of existing resources is helpful for a limited period and after this, there is a need for the firm to have some change in the existing resources. In contrast to this, the research of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009) explained that the implementation of new and modern technology, within the working environment assist in making the functions of the company successful in the competitive business environment. The execution of operational activities due to modern technology provides assistance to the manager to complete the organizational target on time by making effective utilization of existing resources.

In like manner, the research of Costello et al. (2011) depicted that modern technology supports the manager to attract more customers because it helps in satisfying the advanced requirements of the customers. However, there is a decline in the production costs of the company by implementing new technology due to specialization in managerial activities. It is because new technology requires experts and professionals in the working environment for making the activities successful in the market among the competitors for attaining maximum profit.

At the same time, from the research of Kinman et al. (2011) and Zheng et al. (2010), it is determined that customer relation is also one of the major ways that are also used by the firm to achieve success and to increase the customer base of the firm. The strong relations with the customers are built by providing superior quality products at an affordable price.

2.6.4 Customer Relationship Management and Organizational Success

In addition, the study of Eteokleous-Grigoriou (2009) illustrated that it is essential for companies to operate their business with the help of customer relationship management. It is because the customers are the kings in the market and the company is able to make its operations successful when they are satisfied with the existing offering. The satisfied customers also increase the sales with the help of word of mouth methods to the people who are close to them such as family, friends, relatives, etc., as stated by Thomas and Brown, 2011. The effective customer base is created by delivering effective after-sale services. The managers by maintaining transparency and fairness in the financial transaction also help in attracting more customers towards the company.

Furthermore, Achtenhagen et al. (2013) confirmed the significance of customer relationship management in developing a sustainable competitive advantage in the market. Which evolves around focusing on CSR which plays a core role in the development of a strong brand image among the customers and it makes them persuade their buying behaviour significantly to develop a large customer base and to compete with the competitors. Moreover, the study conducted by Eteokleous-Grigoriou (2009) and So et al. (2013) illustrates the need of firms to focus on the community development & the environmental protection which is a core factor to increase the customer attraction which will increase revenues and profits.

2.6.5 Ethical Business Practices and Organizational Sustainability

In like manner, the research of Evans & Waite (2010) and Closs et al. (2011) demonstrated that the ethical standards and principals are the major factors in the working environment,

which contributes towards the success of an organization in the ever-changing market. The ethical practices are the corporate ethics that helps in determining the conceptual framework for the company by the governing body. The ethical principles help in safeguarding the interest of associated stakeholders by applying standard rules and regulations in the working activities. In addition, the research of Gould (2009) claimed that the ethical factor in working place helps in developing the trust level of the customers because it assists in making a vital purchase decision of raw material. The ethical structure involves the implementation of fair-trade practices for guarantying the customers that their interest is not cheated and fair value of value money is created. From the views of Hager and Hodkinson (2009), it can be stated that the ethical marketing done by the company with the help of educational brochures, videos, etc., assist in attracting the customers. It is because the customers are able to grasp relevant information and knowledge about the company operations due to marketing medium and methods for making the final purchase decision.

In the same concern of this, in the research of Closs et al. (2011) and Gould (2009), it is also determined that in order to make good customer relations, firms such as Primark provides the quality products at an affordable price that provide the competitive advantage for the firms and also helps the firm by increasing the customer base of the firm. Because of this, it can be determined that customer relation is an effective way for the firms to get success in the firm & to increase the customer segments in the market. But these findings are not supported in the research of Gould (2009) because, in their research, it is identified that in order to make a good customer relation, there are different ways that are used by the firm and all these efforts take so much cost, time and affect the other working operation of the firm. Due to this, it is not an effective way that is ever used by the firm in its business.

Additionally, from the research of M. Wiernik et al. (2013), it can be said that different ways are used by the firm to get success in the market but at the same time, trust is one of the best

ways that is used by the firm to get the success in the business. In the words of DuFour and DuFour (2013) and Closs et al. (2011), it is illustrated that reputation of the company in the community is also one of the major factors that play a major role in the success of the firm and contribute to the success of an organization.

2.7 Checklist for Managing Learning and Development at the Workplace

There are different principles that the organization should follow to effectively manage and control the learning and development at the workplace. These principles are shown in the below framework for managing the learning work culture at the workplace:

Figure 8: Evaluation of Learning and Development

Source: (APSC, 2016)

According to APSC (2016), the management should consider and emphasize these principles for nurturing the effective learning work culture at the workplace. The learning of the employees should be linked to the business growth and operation that could contribute to the effectiveness of businesses. Apart from this, the learning of HR should be in an integrated manner for ensuring effective collective efforts. Employees should be provided with the

opportunities and options for learning in different fields. Furthermore, the management should put efforts to back up the application of the skills and knowledge of the employees at the workplace. Eventually, it should be evaluated so that corrective efforts can be taken.

Main themes	Main writers	Specialism
Work Culture and Learning Work Culture	Wambui et al. (2013) Thomas & Brown (2011) Aasen et al. (2012) Awan and Tahir (2015)	Managing Workplace Diversity A new culture of learning Employee-driven innovation Impact of working environment on employee's productivity
Importance of Learning Work Culture and Workplace Sustainability in the Organizations	Zheng et al. (2010) Cohen-Meitar, et al. (2009) Blok et al. (2015) DuFour and DuFour (2013)	Linking organizational culture, structure, strategy, and organizational effectiveness Workplace to employee creativity Encouraging sustainability in the workplace Learning by doing
Learning work culture and workplace sustainability	Carmeli and Gittell (2009) Closs et al. (2011) Hager and Hodkinson (2009) Ones and Dilchert (2012)	Leadership and employee involvement Sustainability to support value chains The metaphor of transfer of learning Environmental sustainability at workplace
Challenges in the Implementation of Learning Work Culture	Evans and Waite (2010) Longoni et al. (2014) Chirico and Nordqvist (2010) Nussbaum (2016)	Innovation in workplace learning Developing sustainability strategies Dynamic capabilities and trans-generational value creation Democracy and humanities

Learners at the Workplace	Noe et al. (2010) Hsu and Fang (2009) Argote (2012) Jackson et al. (2011)	Learner engagement Intellectual capital and new product development Organizational learning Future directions for HRM
Factors That Affect the Learning Work Culture and Workplace Sustainability	Costello et al. (2011) Wang et al. (2009) Škerlavaj et al. (2010) Bhattacharjee (2013)	Building a respectful workplace knowledge resources and competitive advantage Organizational learning culture, innovative culture and innovations Employee Culture
Factors of Work Environment That Contribute to The Success of An Organization	Henning et al. (2009) Schroeder (2013) Kinman et al. (2011) Eteokleous-Grigoriou (2009)	Workplace health protection and participation HRM in strategic sustainability Emotional labour, burnout and job satisfaction Instilling new learning, work and communication culture

Table 1: Main themes in literature, main writers and their specialism

(Source: Compiled by the researcher- July 2020)

2.8 Thematic content analysis

Figure 9: Thematic content analysis

(Source: Created by the researcher- July 2020)

The figure above illustrates the thematic content analysis of the research where it indicates four core themes of the process of implementing Learning Work Culture. It is distinguished that the Learning Work Culture has high importance such as affecting employee's productivity and enhancing the organisation's performance. In addition, it acquires gaps in the learning cycle of Learning Work Culture where we can identify three main gaps: The Goals Gap, The Incentives Gap, and the Process Gap. Moreover, contributing factors such as effectiveness of long-term strategies and the ethics of business practices. Finally, there is a large number of discouraging factors to implement Learning Work Culture where it is affected by cultural difference, leadership style, and decision making process.

2.9 Conceptual Framework

Figure 10 The Conceptual Framework

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

The figure above demonstrates the conceptual framework of the research where it summarizes the dependent variables of this study which are affected by the learning work culture such as the workplace sustainability, the business competitiveness, and the productivity and performance of employees, etc. In addition, it is significantly remarkable how the learning work culture affects organizational performance, the motivation of employees, and their skills and knowledge to accomplish effective workload and meet the target of the company by providing productive teamwork.

2.10 Chapter Summary

From the analysis, it can be concluded that learning work culture and workplace sustainability plays a vital role in achieving the objective of reaching a competitive advantage. Most of the research has found that workplace learning improves the productivity and the performance of the employees which increases the performance of the organization. The strong learning work culture helps in managing the diverse and dynamic situations at the workplace that leads towards the improvement in the performance of the organization. The learning work culture ensures the engagement of the employees in their job at the workplace that can play a vital role in workplace sustainability. However, there are some factors which affect the learning work culture at the workplace such as honesty, integrity, accountability, and effective leadership.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the research methods used in this research. Research methodology can be defined as the process of selecting a research topic, selecting the research philosophy, research approach and research design, identifying the research variables, selection of kinds of data and methods for data collection, selection of the data analysis methods and representing the findings of the research. The research methodology provides guidelines and frameworks for systematically conducting this research study. The research study has to be controlled, rigorous, valid, verifiable, critical, empirical, and systematic to be effective research that is possible if the proper research methods are used in a research study. The research methodology helps in achieving the primary research objectives of discovering new facts, verifying the identified facts, analysing the problem, and identifying the solution for that problem and others. Apart from this, this chapter analyses different research philosophies, research approaches, research designs, and types of research with data collection methods. Furthermore, the elements found in this chapter have been used in getting the required information with a view to solving the research problem. This chapter includes the methods that have been selected in this research with the proper justification of the reason why particular methods are being used in this research study and stating how those methods helped in achieving the research objectives.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy can be said as the philosophy of research towards the research problem and how it should be analysed. It means the research philosophy is the way the researcher goes through to collect, analyse and use the collected data for solving the research problem (Saunders et al., 2012). Moreover, the research philosophy is beneficial for the researcher to define and specify the research method that is used in its research study. It can also be helpful to evaluate the research strategy. The research philosophy includes pragmatism philosophy, positivism philosophy, interpretive philosophy, and realism research philosophy.

Pragmatism research philosophy:

Pragmatism research philosophy believes that from the single point of view a problem cannot be analysed and solved. Every problem has multiple realities in the world. Therefore, it finds different ways of interpreting the problems going in the world. Pragmatism research philosophy is the combination of both positivism and interpretivism research philosophy (Smith, 2015). Pragmatist researchers are like architects who use whatever required for construction of the building. Similarly, the pragmatist combines the methods to get the answers to questions.

Positivism research philosophy:

Positivism is the research methodology that is helpful for conducting the research by the researcher. Positivism research philosophy involves the concept that is relevant to the research study. It sticks to facts gained through the observation. The data in this philosophy is collected by the objective approach and the data are quantifiable and measurable in the research study. It provides the result based on statistical analysis of the data (Kazdin, 2011). The researcher focuses on the statistical and factual information in positivism research. The positivism research philosophy is adopted to prove the assumption and theories made in previous

researches. It provides results based on the assumption developed from the outcomes of previous researches.

Interpretivism research philosophy:

Interpretivism research is the research philosophy in which the responses of participants in practical research are utilized to arrive at the result. Interpretivism is also recited as interpretivism research philosophy. Moreover, interpretivism research philosophy is based on the naturalistic approach of collecting the data such as interviews and observations. Interpretivism research focuses on the integration of the beliefs and opinions of human beings in the research study (Novikov and Novikov, 2013). This philosophy accepts that the involvement of social construction in the research can lead to access the reality. It uses an inductive approach to integrate the qualitative information in the research.

Realism Research Philosophy:

This depends on the scientific approach to gain the information and to develop the understanding. Realism research philosophy is categorized into direct and critical realism research philosophies. Direct realism uses the personal or human sense to present the world (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). Critical realism believes that the human or person experiences the world. Therefore, the realism research philosophy focuses on reality by putting attention on the idea of a human being in the research process.

This research is based on quantitative and qualitative analysis, so there is a need for involving the research philosophy that involves scientific as well as a subjective approach. Therefore, the researcher in this research study has used pragmatic research philosophy for collecting the correct information and arriving at the reliable and effective results in solving the problems. Pragmatism research philosophy research helps in analysing the research

problem with both qualitative and quantitative data. This research philosophy leads to a better understanding of the learning work culture and its effect on the business' sustainability. It also helps an in-depth analysis of the research problem (Collins, 2010). Furthermore, the pragmatism research philosophy has been chosen over positivism, interpretivism, and realism as it helps the researcher in analysing the effects of learning work culture on the business sustainability of Primark in qualitative and somewhat quantitative aspects. Pragmatism research philosophy is based on the deconstructive paradigm that enables the researcher to use mixed research method to develop better research outcome that for argumentative issues and to bring truth & reality (Smith, 2015). The pragmatism philosophy helps in understanding that how the learning work culture fosters the improvement in the skills and knowledge of employees, how it stimulates the performance of employees, engagement of employees in work job, and how does it foster the innovation at the workplace in Primark. The pragmatism research helped effectively in evaluating the learning work culture effectively at Primark and provided accurate results based on the analysis of samples only (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The positivism philosophy focuses only on the statistical data and information to resolve the research problem. It is highly structured, and it required a large number of samples for analysing the problem. At the same time, the interpretive research philosophy helps in-depth analysis based on a small number of samples, but it uses only qualitative data. Furthermore, realism research philosophy fits subjective research even uses both qualitative and quantitative data (Charmaz, 2011). Therefore, pragmatism research philosophy has been used in this research study to find the impact of the learning work culture on the performance and sustainability of Primark.

3.3 Research Approach

The research approach refers to methods or ways of researching the problem. Apart from this, the research approach is a way to search and analyse the problem (Bryman, 2015). It also involves planning from broad assumption to detailed methods of data analysis, data collection and interpretation. Moreover, there are three concepts of research approaches such as philosophical world views, research methods, and design. The research approach can be categorized into inductive, abductive, and deductive research approach.

Inductive research approach:

In inductive research approach, the fresh data is collected from the field, which aids in developing theories and resolving the concerned research problem. The inductive research approach provides new information that helps in developing theories and generalization of the research. It does not require hypothesis formulation in the research (Bryman, 2015). It begins with the determination of the research aims, objectives and research questions. It is used to answer the questions of how. There is enough time for inductive research that helps in achieving the research aims and objectives effectively (Babbie, 2010). The inductive research process includes various steps such as observation, the topic of interest, collection of data, clustering of data, analysis of data, the emergence of theme, generalization, and disseminating the findings.

In order to collect the data, this approach aims at generating meaningful information from the data which is determined to be collected for evaluating the relationships and patterns for building up the theory. The inductive approach is based on learning from experiences. If the researcher follows the inductive approach then, the researcher needs to develop the generalizations and evaluate the preliminary researches as the researcher progresses through the research. Additionally, the inductive approach is related to qualitative methods. It is also

helpful for the researcher to evaluate easily the qualitative data that produces the reliable as well as valid findings.

Deductive research approach:

Deductive research proves existing theories and assumptions and justifies them through primary research. Along with this, it provides results based on the numerical and quantitative data while the inductive research approach uses qualitative data as well. The deductive approach focuses on and examines the known facts and theories to define their validity. There is a shortage of time for deductive research and the risks are avoided (Bernard, 2011). The following steps are gone through to conduct deductive research such as literature search and theories, selection of research topic, an idea related to the researched theories, formulation of assumptions, data collection, data analysis and testing of hypothesis, confirmation of the hypothesis, and disseminating findings.

Moreover, the deductive approach is also described by the hypothesis that is derived from the theory proposition. It begins with a pattern that is expected as it is being tested against operations. For the research, the deductive approach explores the known theory, phenomenon and tests if in various circumstances the theory is valid. If the researcher adopts the deductive approach for its research then, it would formulate the hypotheses at the beginning of the research. There are various steps in a deductive approach that are being examined such as deducing, formulating, testing, examining and modifying.

Abductive research approach:

Abductive research approach complements the weakness of deductive research approach and inductive research approach. It adopts pragmatism perspective to overcome the weaknesses in deductive and inductive research approach (Levac et al., 2010). However, this approach is not

widely used in the research as it is very hard to understand and handle. This leads towards the prediction from the incomplete observation.

However, in this research study, inductive research has been used for collecting the data and applying towards the research problem. The reason behind selecting inductive research approach is that it has helped in getting insights into the learning work culture that in turn has helped in a better analysis of the aspects of the learning work culture (Gioia et al., 2013). This has aided in generating an effective solution for this problem at the Primark. This is because the inductive research approach leads the descriptive analysis while the deductive approach collects quantitative data and emphasizes on proving or disproving the hypothesis developed based on theories generated based on previous research results. There is enough time available with inductive research that is not possible in the deductive research.

The inductive research helps the researchers in effectively analysing the research problem by using quantitative and qualitative data. The inductive research leads the practical research that in turn has helped the researcher in identifying and evaluating the role of the learning work culture for achieving long term goals and sustainability of businesses in the retail industry of UK. This research approach offers the freedom to the researcher to not to limit the research to only hypotheses and allows exploring that helps to develop effective research outcome. This helps the researcher in understanding the learning work culture, the retail industry of the UK, the importance of learning work culture at the work culture, determinants of the learning work culture at the workplace, learners at the workplace, and other elements of learning work culture (Castro et al., 2010). It has made the researcher able to identify the relationship between the learning work culture at the workplace and productivity, performance, satisfaction, turnover of employees. Apart from this, this has identified the effect of learning work culture on the competitiveness of the organization, and productivity and performance of the organization. At the same time, the researcher rejected the deductive research approach as it fits with positivism

philosophy, which focuses on proving or disproving the pre-established theories and assumptions. The deductive research cannot provide the basic and general understanding of the learning work culture and its effects on the retail industry of the UK for long-term business sustainability (Bernard, 2011).

Justifications for methodological choices

In this research, the methodological choices which are used are the primary data collection through the usage of surveys and interviews with employees of Primark UK in the aim of obtaining fresh data and opinions regarding the problematic of the importance of the implementation of the learning work culture, and how employees from within the company would support or decline the importance of this strategy which contributes in the enhancement of the productivity of the workforce due to the enhancement of the work environment which learning work culture provides. Moreover, the research uses secondary data collection through the usage of academic journals and sources which emphasis the importance of the learning work culture within the workplace and especially within the retail industry as it focuses on Primark UK case study.

Justification of geographic location of shops

In order to collect the primary data which includes surveys and interviews, Primark Liverpool branch was chosen and this choice is due to the location of the researcher and this branch was available to agree on questioning its employees and managers.

Justification of the scope:

In order to provide an efficient and accurate results, this research has adopted the usage of SPSS in order to analyse the results of the interviews and surveys and conclude the outcome of the data collected in order to assess the accuracy of the suggested hypothesis.

Justification for number, type, and roles of respondents

In order to reach a good research participation rate, 200 workers of Primark have been targeted by the researcher in order to collect the data through a survey questionnaire. Most of the employees were below 25 years old, and the greatest majority were male employees. Moreover, the choice of respondents was a mixture of all positions including managers and supervisors. The reason behind these choices is to gain valuable insight from the research and to reach a high level of integrity.

3.4 Types of Research

Types of research mean the format of the research in which the research study has to be conducted. Therefore, the research can be conducted using either qualitative research tools or quantitative research tools.

Qualitative research:

Qualitative research can be termed as the research which focuses on the collection of qualitative data concerned and relevant to the research problem. Qualitative data may be in the form of perception, attitudes, beliefs, opinions, and satisfaction of employees. Qualitative research is the kind of research in which the result is based on the views of the participants in the research. Furthermore, in the quantitative research general questions are asked from the participants and the information is collected in words (Baskerville and Wood-Harper, 2016). At the same time, this research is biased as it is not scientific rather it is behavioural research which measures the attitudes and perception of the participants. It is subjective research as it defines the research problem from the perspective of people who are experiencing the same problem. It best fits the inductive research approach and interpretivism research philosophy to formulate the theories and hypothesis (Saunders, 2011). There is no statistical test for this kind of research to analyse

the information. There are various methods for qualitative information such as focus group, in-depth interview, review of documents, and survey.

Quantitative research:

Quantitative research is just opposite to qualitative research. Quantitative research collects numerical and quantitative data that helps in measuring the performance so that an effective conclusion can be derived from the result. The quantitative data includes height, weight, age, income, and others. This is the kind of research in which the researcher has to decide about what to study throughout the research process (Lodico et al., 2010). The specific questions are asked from the participants and the information is analysed using statistics. The analysis and inquiry in this research are objective and unbiased. It fits best for the deductive approach and positivism philosophy as it collects the quantitative data that can help in proving the existing theories and hypothesis. It is objective and provides information about the effects of the programs on the research problem in the research study. It uses statistical tests to analyse the information for making it meaningful in decision making (Kitchin and Tate, 2013).

In this research study, both (quantitative and qualitative) kinds of researches have been used to gather data in the complete form to make the research effective. This has led the effective analysis of the learning work culture in detail. The qualitative research provides information about the attitudes and perception of participants towards learning work culture at the workplace. Qualitative research helps to offer a detailed understanding of the views of participants as it involves subjective data collection. However, it is very hard to analyse the qualitative information therefore, the quantitative research complemented this weakness of the qualitative research (Kitchin and Tate, 2013). There were some specific options given for each question in the questionnaire in which the participants selected the options easily. This has helped in getting the information about the perception and attitudes of the participants as well

as analysing their response quantitatively by identifying how many participants selected with an option. The qualitative research has helped in collecting the information about the gender of the participants, their perception, and attitudes towards learning work cultures such as effects of learning work culture on their job satisfaction, their motivation, innovation, employee's morale, productivity and performance of employees, and others. At the same time, quantitative research has helped in quantifying the research by providing options in the questionnaire (Padgett, 2016). Apart from this, the researcher read the annual report of the company to know about the performance of the company and the effects of learning work culture on the profitability and productivity of the company. Along with this, qualitative research is individual-level research, therefore, the researcher in this research distributed the questionnaire among the employees where individual employees provided their responses according to what they perceive about learning work culture at the workplace in Primark. Qualitative and quantitative research together can give an effective result. The qualitative research has aided in describing the learning work culture in detail by reviewing the previous documents while the quantitative research helped in quantifying the information to be collected from the participants (Saunders, 2011). The quantitative research helps in supporting the understanding developed through qualitative research. Involvement of both the research method has supported to increase the relevancy of the research finding.

3.5 Research Design

The research design can be defined as the research strategy that provides a framework for conducting the research. The research design is the blueprint for the research. The research design assists in selecting the subjects to be observed in the research process. It also aids in selecting the best data analysis method for effective interpretation. The selection of the research design depends on the aims and objectives of the research study (Creswell, 2013). The research design provides blueprints that help in the selection of research study, deciding about sampling

methods, data collection methods, selection of the research instruments and defining data processing plan and interpretation. The exploratory and conclusive research studies are the two most designs of the research.

Exploratory research design:

The exploratory research is the research focuses on exploring the new and hidden facts in a specific area but does not provide the conclusion and answer to the research questions. Moreover, this kind of research intends to develop the understanding by exploring new facts but not intends to provide a conclusion to the research. It can be said as the fundamental research that can form the base of another conclusive research. This research can be more helpful if there is no research conducted previously on the selected problem (Crowther and Lancaster, 2009). The researchers in exploratory research mostly use the unstructured interview. The research is flexible in the exploratory research design to change the direction of this research. The exploratory research is significantly flexible and adaptable that states that exploratory research can accommodate the change according to the requirement of the situation that helps in ensuring the quality of research result. It aims to generate new insights (Creswell, 2013). It requires relatively less sample size to research the topic that cannot represent the whole population accurately.

Conclusive research design:

Conclusive research design leads the generation of findings that can be utilized to concluding the research. The conclusive research design includes two types of research studies, which are descriptive research and experimental or causal research (Yin, 2013). The descriptive research study describes the relationship between aspects of a research problem in depth that helps in reaching the conclusion. The Descriptive research design helps in getting detail insight into the research problem. The Descriptive research answers why, how, when, and where that leads to

a detailed analysis of the research problem. At the same time, casual or experimental research is the kind of research which emphasizes on identifying the cause and effect relationship between aspects of the research problem (Crowther and Lancaster, 2009). It uses quantitative methods generally to find out the cause and effect relationship.

In this research study, descriptive research has been used. It is because this research helps in developing the understanding of the researcher about the research problem in detail. The researcher has analysed the learning work culture in depth to conclude the research effectively (Green et al., 2012). The exploratory research provides new insight, but it is not conclusive which is why it does not help achieve the research objectives. While the descriptive research described the learning work culture in detail including the concept of learning work culture, importance, and impact of learning work culture, drivers of learning work culture, workplace sustainability, and others. At the same time, the experimental research design finds the cause and effect relationship irrespective of other aspects concerned with the research problem (Zikmund et al., 2013). That affects the conclusion and finding of the research and cannot provide reliable information. Therefore, it can be said that descriptive research design helps in analysing the problem in detail that develops a deep understanding of the learning work culture. At the same time, descriptive research is time-consuming research and is costly somewhat. It required a large sample for analysing the effect of learning work culture at Primark (Creswell, 2013). The descriptive research has helped in describing the learning work culture and the impact of the culture on the productivity and performance of employees, organizational effectiveness, and competitiveness.

3.6 Research Variables

Research variables can be said to be anything that can cause a change in the result of the research. The research variables have to be identified in the experimental research design. However, in the case of descriptive research design, the variables have to be identified that can

affect the research conclusion. The descriptive research design defines the independent variables that may affect the expected business results (Bernard and Bernard, 2012). The research variables may be categorized into dependent variables and independent variables. The number of variables which are included in the research study determines the complexity of research. This research study is about finding the impact of the learning work culture on the sustainability of the businesses. There is an effective interaction between these variables as people in the organization inclined to learn new things and gain new knowledge that adds to their existing knowledge and skills (Bennette and Vickers, 2012). In this research study, the researcher identified the variables such as:

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables
Learning work culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workplace sustainability • Business competitiveness • Productivity and performance of employees • Innovation and creativity • Profitability and revenue • Organizational performance • Cooperation and coordination at the workplace • Improved skills and knowledge • Increased motivation to employees • Reduced turnover and improved retention rate • Effective leadership at the workplace

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective teamwork
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Table 2 The Variables which are included in the research study

Source: (Author, 2020)

The researcher identified that the learning work culture is the independent variable that causes the dependent variables to change accordingly. The researcher identified that the effective implementation of the learning work culture may influence the independent variables such as the performance of the organization, productivity, and performance of the employees, reduced turnover of the employees, workplace sustainability, health and safety working environment, innovation and creativity at the workplace and others (Schwab, 2013).

3.7 Data Collection

Collection of the relevant, complete, and accurate data is a must for achieving the objective of the research. Collection of data is the process which starts from data selection and ends with the collection of data. Hence, primary and secondary are two kinds of data collection methods that can be used to gather the required information.

Types of data:

Data are categorized into primary data and secondary data. Primary data can be termed as the data, which is very fresh, and which is not collected ever before by anyone. This type of data can also be called as the first-hand data that is being collected by the researcher for his research study. Primary data includes a questionnaire, surveys, interviews and observations. On the other hand, the secondary data can be termed as the data, which is already collected and available (Ritchie et al., 2013). Hence, secondary data is also known as second-hand data that is being collected by the researcher through books, internet, articles and annual reports. In this research, both primary and secondary data have been collected for providing a better solution to the research problem. The secondary data has helped in better understanding the concepts

and aspects of the learning work culture and its impact on the organization and employees. The primary data has supported the understanding from the secondary data about learning work culture.

Data collection methods:

Secondary data is ready-made available from different sources such as internet, website, textbooks, newspapers and magazines, census, journals, annual reports, private agencies, and government publications (Time, 2012). At the same time, there are various methods for collecting the primary data such as interview, case study, surveys, brainstorming, observation, and various others.

Primary data collection methods:

There are various methods of primary data collection in descriptive research. It includes qualitative and quantitative research method. In the qualitative research method, the numerical or calculations are not included. It is related to words, feelings and emotions that are non-quantifiable. For example, it includes group, survey, observation, interview, and others (Time, 2012). In the qualitative research method, open-ended questions are involved. On the other hand, the quantitative research method is based on mathematical calculations. In the quantitative research methods, close-ended questions are involved. The researcher in this research has used the survey method to gather the information.

Survey: Survey is the research method in which the researcher does field research. The survey can be defined as the way of collecting the data through questionnaire. Similarly, the questionnaire is also a kind of survey tool. In the questionnaire, some questions to be asked from the respondents are predetermined and structured in a proper sequence. The questions are well relevant to the research topic is assured. The questionnaire consists of different kinds of

questions. At the same time, the survey is similar to the questionnaire except for one difference (Fowler, 2013). The main difference between the questionnaire and survey is that in the survey the researcher fills up the questionnaire based on the responses provided by the respondents. While in the questionnaire the respondents only fill up the questionnaire (O'Leary, 2013). Apart from this, there is a time constraint in the survey as the respondents and researcher have to be present and the survey has to be filled that time only. On the other hand, in the case of the questionnaire, the respondents can answer the questions at their leisure without realizing any location and time constraints.

Interview: In the context of collecting qualitative data, the researcher has increased the concern towards interviewing individuals about the research topic. The interview is the type of data collection where the researcher asks some questions to the respondents. The interview may be structured and unstructured. If the interview questions are predetermined and well-structured in the sequence, then this can be said a structured interview (Mertens, 2014). But if the questions in the interview emerge instantly at the time while the interview is going, this is the unstructured interview.

The researcher in this research study used a survey questionnaire and interview both to gather the information. The questionnaire consisting of rating scale question has been used to collect the information from employees working in Primark. For conducting the survey, 150 employees of Primark UK were selected. The reason behind selecting survey method for this study is that this method has supported to collect the data from a large sample size. Moreover, the survey method is very effective in collecting the actual and reliable information on attitudes and perception of the employees towards work culture at the workplace in Primark that can ensure the quality of research. A survey thorough questionnaire is found helpful in collecting the views of the research participants about the learning work culture and the programs for establishing learning work culture to improve the productivity and performance of the

employees (Taylor et al., 2015). The survey questionnaire helped the researcher in collecting the views of participants through utilising close-ended questionnaire which has supported to conduct quantitative analysis about the learning work culture and its impact on organisational sustainability. It has also supported to collect the views of the participants regarding how they perceive the learning work culture and its effect at the workplace. Moreover, the survey method is less time-consuming methods and allows assessing the research problems from a large sample size (Wilcox et al., 2012).

The researcher at the same time interviewed 6 senior managers and 6 employees to gather information about the performance of the organization after the application of the learning work culture at the workplace (Englander, 2012). The research interview of the senior managers and employees has supported to collect information in a subjective manner which has assisted to achieve research objectives in a better way. Open questions are designed for interview purpose so that in-depth understanding about the views of interview participants can be taken.

At the same time, the survey method helped in finding the information that assisted to understand the learning work culture and its impact on the business sustainability through quantitative analysis and has supported to represent the research findings through tables.

Secondary data collection methods:

There are various sources where secondary data can be collected. These sources can be textbooks, journals, annual reports, newspaper and magazines, articles, scholar articles, private agencies, literature reviews, web site and the internet, and research papers. The researcher in this research study used the textbooks, literature reviews, research papers, and scholarly journals. The textbooks such as organizational behaviour, organizational change and development, and organizational culture are pored over to understand the concept of the work culture and type of work culture (Mackey and Gass, 2015). From the reading of these books

the researcher developed his knowledge and found the kind of culture, the importance of culture, and the effect of the culture on the organizational performance and employees' productivity. The books are easily available in the libraries where the researcher easily accessed. Apart from this, the researcher reviewed the previous research papers and scholarly articles on the topic of learning work culture. The researcher learned that what is learning work culture, the impact of learning work culture on employees' productivity, staff turnover, employees' engagement, organizational competitiveness, productivity and performance of the organization, and the factors, which are determinants to the learning work culture in the workplace (Mahapatra, 2014). The scholarly based articles and research papers are an effective and reliable source of information as these sources include the information previously researched by any researcher. Therefore, the quality of the information included in this research can be said as of a great level. At the same time, the internet and websites are also used to get information about the impact of learning work culture on the productivity and performance of Primark. The researcher found factors affecting learning work culture, kinds of culture, the importance of learning work culture for business sustainability, and various other kinds of information, which helped the researcher in understanding the research problem in depth.

3.8 Data Collection Process

The data collection process is the process that defines how the researcher will go to collect the data. This is required to ensure the effectiveness of the data. The researcher in this research collected the data from employees working in Primark. The researcher met with the employees after their working times at the workplace. Some of the employees were met at the workplace only and some employees caught outside the work or office premise. The respondents or employees to be involved in the research study were explained why this research study is being conducted. The researcher described the aims and objective of the research study (Bryman, 2015). This is a necessary and ethical requirement of the research study that the research

participants should be aware of the purpose of the research. Then the employees asked about providing the answer to the research questions. They were convinced that their identity will be kept confidential. They were assured that the information collected from them will be used for the research purpose only. No misuse of the information will be undertaken throughout the research. The researcher requested the respondents to provide unbiased and correct information so that the effectiveness and quality of result from the research can be ensured (Petty et al., 2012).

Then the pre-structured questionnaire was distributed among the employees personally and via email as well. Then the data was collected regarding the opinions and views of respondents on the effectiveness of the learning work culture at the workplace. The respondent provided their view based on their learning and experience at the workplace. Apart from this, a set of questionnaires handed to the HR manager and other senior managers to get their perspective regarding the effectiveness of learning work culture at the workplace.

In the context of the interview, 6 senior managers and 6 employees were selected through non-probability sampling technique. So, for interview purpose, the researcher has selected only those participants who are knowledgeable and experienced and can share valuable findings. From each participant, 5 questions were asked to develop a better understanding of the learning work culture and its effect on work engagement especially in the context of the UK'S retail industry.

Then the data collected from both the collection method were consolidated for the further research process.

3.9 Sampling

Sampling is the process of choosing the variables from the population or universe which analyse the research problem. Moreover, sampling can be defined as the important phase in the

research process where the researcher draws the sample for studying the research population (Levy and Lemeshow, 2013). This is not possible anyhow to collect the views of the whole population and get the result. Therefore, it is inevitable to take some samples from the population to analyse the research problem. Moreover, various steps are to be considered by the researcher in its research study such as identification of the interest of the population. Then, the other step is to specify the sampling frame of the population (Marvasti, 2012). The third step the researcher has to follow is the determination of sample size. The last but not least step is implementing the plan by choosing all the information of the population in the research.

Total population size:

The population is the group of people who have specific characteristics and attributes that the researcher is interested in studying (Marvasti, 2012). The employees in Primark are the target population of this research study. The total numbers of employees in the Primark are 68000. Therefore, this is not possible to research the whole population. So, samples have been taken that can represent the characteristics and attributes of the whole population.

Sampling frame:

Sampling frame is the predetermined criteria that guide what kinds of samples could be taken from the population. Sampling frame has to be defined as it gives the ideas of which group of people the researcher is going to study. The determination of the sampling frame is necessary for the selection and collection of the sample effectively (Schilling and Neubauer, 2017). Therefore, in this research study, the research has chosen the samples from the employees from different departments at the workplace in Primark.

Sample size:

The sample size is also an important decision in the sampling procedure. The sample size is the sum of samples to be drawn from the population in research. The sample size must be in the amount that can be sufficient for analysing the problem concerned. Over and under-sampled research may affect the result of the research (Kitchin and Tate, 2013). Insufficient or under-sampled research is not able to provide effective result and is not able to present the population effectively. It may cause a standard error in what the population is and in what the samples represent among the population. However, in this research study, samples of 150 workers within Primark have been collected by the researcher. These 150 employees were selected according to the sample size to reach appropriate responses which will be an aid to generate valid outcomes of the research & to accomplish the aim of the research. These participants are selected from a store in Liverpool and two stores in London. To conduct the survey, 50 participants from each store are selected through random sampling. Under what sampling frame, participants who lie between the age group of 18 to 60 are selected who are working in the firm for at least last 1 year. Both male and female participants are given equal opportunity to get selected under-sampling frame. This sampling frame is used in all the three stores to maintain standardisation and to offer equal opportunity to all sample size.

Simultaneously, for conducting the interview 12 participants were selected (6 senior managers and 6 employees). The reason behind selecting a small sample size for the interview is that interview is a time-consuming process as it was conducted through face to face interaction and one by one manner. For increasing the number of targeted customers, advertisement tools are used such as email and social media. These tools helped the researcher target the respondents in minimum and effective time.

Sampling methods:

Sampling methods are the techniques of collecting or drawing samples from the population. Different kinds of sampling techniques are available such as simple random sampling, deliberate sampling, quota sampling, convenience sampling, area sampling, cluster sampling, and other sampling methods (Palinka et al., 2015).

In this research study, the researcher has used simple random sampling for collecting the samples of the survey questionnaire. Simple random sampling is the sampling methods in which the employees and senior managers have been selected randomly without any deliberation and discussion (Hair, 2015). This sampling technique is deemed to be most effective among all the sampling techniques as it provides an equal chance to all the variables in the universe. There is no chance of biasing in the sample collection process through simple random sampling method. The researcher, after approval from the authorities in Primark, selected employees from a different department and departmental managers randomly. This ensures the quality of research and reliability of the result from the analysis of the views of employees (Thompson, 2013). At the same time, the non-probability sampling including quota sampling, stratified sampling, cluster sampling, area sampling and deliberate sampling can be said as biased sampling methods as the researcher in this sampling method draw the samples after proper analysis and discussion. Along with this, the deliberate sampling method can reduce the quality of result as it includes the biased selection that could lead the biased result. The simple random sampling helped effectively evaluating the views of the participants about learning work culture (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Therefore, the researcher used a simple random sampling method to increase the quality and reliability of the research.

At the same time, in the context of sampling for the interview method, the non-probability sampling method is used. The reason behind it is that in this method, data is collected in a

subjective manner which increases the need for involving experienced and knowledgeable participants who can share effective views regarding the selected research topic. Moreover, as the interview is a time-consuming process, so it is conducted on a small sample size. Involvement of experienced participants helps to involve their valuable views in the study. This method helps to ensure the quality of the collected data (Thompson, 2013). The utilisation of non-probability sampling method helps to involve subjective judgement in the study.

From this, it can be discussed that this research has utilised probability sampling method for collecting data from the survey questionnaire and has utilised non-probability sampling method for collecting data from the interview.

Research Instrument:

Research instruments are the tools to be used in the research for collecting the data.

In the context of the survey questionnaire, the researcher has used a close-ended questionnaire to gather information from the participants in the research. Apart from this, the questionnaire is able to collect the information relevant to the research problem (Hagan, 2014). This questionnaire is designed on the basis of the close-ended questionnaire. The information collected through the questionnaire is of great quality and is reliable in taking the decision. The questionnaire has been designed and structured in four parts including demographic profile of the research participants, psychological and behavioural points of view of the respondents regarding the learning work culture at the workplace, factors determining the effective learning at the workplace, and the suggestion to foster the effective learning work culture at the workplace (Zohrabi, 2013).

In the context of the interview, the researcher has given concern towards designing small and concise questions. There is a special concern given towards involving only relevant questions

which can give adequate information about the research problem (Hagan, 2014). The questions are designed on an open-ended basis so that the participants' views do not limit to a particular aspect.

To evaluate the quality of the questions, pilot testing has taken place which has supported the researcher to amend the questions wherever required and has supported to include only relevant questions.

The survey questionnaire is designed while utilising the close-ended question format which has supported to evaluate the primary data in a statistical manner. On the contrary, interview questions are designed while utilising open-ended format as it supports the participants to share their views in a subjective manner and helps to develop an in-depth understanding about the research topic (Hagan, 2014).

Data processing and analysis:

Data processing is the sorting, analysing, and representing the data in the form that would mean in the research study. Moreover, data processing can be said the process of converting the collected raw data into meaning information. It includes the manipulation of the data to generate effective results to resolve the research problems (Miles et al., 2015). Therefore, data processing is made through numbers of stages, which include collection, editing, coding, classification, tabulation, analysis, graphical presentation, and data cleaning, and adjusting. On the other hand, data analysis is the process that involves action, and methods performed on data that explains the facts, detect patterns, as well as a hypothesis is tested. This process includes the assurance of data quality, modelling, and statistical data analysis and interpretation results.

Sorting:

Sorting is the process in which unnecessary and irrelevant data is removed from the data set and remaining data are manipulated to give them a form of data that can be analysed. Moreover, data sorting is the process in which the collected data is arranged in a manner that it could be analysed and interpreted effectively. The data here is categorized, classified, and put into the tabular form to analyse the result that how many respondents in the research give what rank or what opinions about the research problem (Neuman and Robson, 2014). In this research study, both qualitative and quantitative research has been used to collect the data. Therefore, the sorting helped in arranging the qualitative data into alphabetical order while quantitative data into the numerical form. A sorting worksheet has been prepared where the data has been arranged and manipulated to lead the effective analysis of the information.

3.10 Data Analysis

Data analysis refers to the evaluation of the views of survey respondents. Moreover, it is the assessment of the data collected in the research. There are various methods of the data analysis, which are statistical methods (mean, median, mode, standard deviation, range, regression, and correlation), economical tools (F-test, T-test, Z-test, and Chi-square test), SPSS, MS Excel, and others (Gale et al., 2013). However, in this research study, SPSS, statistical tools, and MS Excel have been used for getting an accurate and reliable result for the data that is collected through a survey questionnaire.

Additionally, there are various techniques of data analysis and data mining is one of the data analysis techniques. It mainly focuses on knowledge as well as modelling discovery for predictive purposes. On the other hand, business intelligence is the other data analysis technique that depends upon aggregation as well as focusing on the information of the business. Hence, on the basis of statistical application, the data analysis is categorized into three types

such as descriptive analysis, exploratory analysis, and confirmatory analysis (Gale et al., 2013). In the data analysis, the exploratory concentrates on launching new features. Predictive analysis is based on statistical models. Moreover, the findings of the interview method have also correlated with survey findings to increase reliability. Further, it is also linked with literature review findings.

Content analysis and construct validity:

Content analysis can be said as an important research tool that is used to analyse and validate that every content and information collected in the research study is relevant to the research problem and topic. It is greatly consistent with the research objectives. For checking the scale of relevancy and validity of data, construct validity is used. All the questions included in the research study to collect the information are thoroughly analysed (Peng and Lai, 2012). In this research study, the number of questions used for collecting the information is well concerned and relevant to analyse the effect of learning work culture on skills and knowledge of the employees, the productivity and performance of the employees, efficiency of the employees, overall performance of the organization, staff turnover, innovation at the workplace, competitiveness of the organization, and workplace sustainability (Drost, 2011). The factors that are determinants to the learning work culture at the workplace are identified that could help in better conclusion and define the validity of the research.

Reliability Test:

Reliability test checks the consistency of the items of the scale. The correlation between the total items helped in measuring the consistency of the items (Drost, 2011). The correlation of the total items was computed with all items that helped in ensuring the consistency of the variables. Cronbach Alpha method was used by the researcher in this research study to measure the reliability of each item of scale (Csikszentmihalyi and Larson, 2014). The Cronbach states

the research items reliable if they achieve good to score more than 50%. If the score is 0.60 then the research items can be said enough reliable (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011). It is the higher degree of internal consistency of the responses provided by the participants to the questionnaire in the research study.

Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis is the analysis of collected data through statistical tools. The statistical tools help in codifying the data collected that in turn helps in the better interpretation of the result. All the data in this research study was codified in the excel sheet. The questions were coded based on the responses of the research participants as the questions were Likert's Scale type of questions. The main reason is the usage of Likert's Scale which is an aid for the respondents to provide answers for each question in an effective manner and it also provides support for the quantitative findings. The statistical analysis used a specific package to compute the statistical measures. The statistical tools such as mean, mode, median, standard deviation, range, and correlation have been used in this research study (Kratochwill, 2013). The mean, mode, and median stated the average number of the participants that provided the specific response to each question. Along with this, the standard deviation measured the deviation among the responses of the research participants. At the same time, the correlation evaluated the degree of relationship among the responses coded in the excel sheet.

Correlation and regression analysis:

Correlation is the statistical tools that help in identifying the degree of attachment between the variables of data set. The correlation has been used by the researcher in this research study to measure the relationship between the learning work culture strategies and implementation and the business sustainability (Cohen et al., 2013). Correlation helps in finding the relationship between response variables and explanatory variables. In this case, the dependent variable is the sustainability of businesses and the independent variable is learning work culture. The

correlation measures the relationship between -1 to +1. If the independent variable moves in the same direction, the dependent variable moves, can be said as a positive correlation. Independent variable reacts in the opposite direction when the dependent variable increases or decreases, this can be said as a negative correlation between variables (Mandel, 2012). Therefore, the relationship between the learning work culture and business sustainability is positive.

Similarly, the regression analysis also analyses the relationship between the dependent variable and one or more than one independent variables. It helps in understanding the behaviour of the dependent variables to respond to the variation in independent variables. The regression analysis is the linear relationship analysis that states the degree of deviation (Bendat and Piersol, 2011). The regression analysis showed the relationship between learning work culture and workplace sustainability, employees, job satisfaction, and turnover, productivity and performance of the organization and others through the linear regression graph.

SPSS:

SPSS is a software package which is used for the statistical analysis of the collected data in a research study. SPSS stands for a special package for social science. It was developed actually for social science, but it is being used in almost every field such as data mining, market research, and others fields (Pallant, 2013). The SPSS shows the findings of the research in statistics such as cross-tabulation, charts, and graphs. It helps the researcher in analysing and interpreting the results very effectively through effective presentation of the findings. Apart from this, SPSS helps in saving the time of the data analysis as it is the software package of the statistical analysis that can be used for quick calculation and analysis of the data (Carver and Nash, 2011). At the same time, the location of the variables inputted in SPSS by the researcher in the research study should be clear for the effective result from SPSS. Along with this, the

SPSS has a long list of the statistical analysis that provides the options to the researcher for selecting the best statistical analysis for the concerned research. The outcomes provided by the SPSS are separate from the raw data inputted. Moreover, the researcher used cross-tabs methods to provide an analysis of the strength of the association between variables by interpreting the results of the symmetric measures using Phi, Cramer's V, and Contingency Coefficient. In addition to Chi-Square test which provides an analysis of the availability of an association between the variable by interpreting the results of the expected count which should be equal or less than 20% and it should be less than 5.

NVivo:

NVivo is a software-based program that is used for qualitative as well as mixed research methods such as interviews, focus groups, surveys, etc. It is majorly used for the analysis of unstructured text, audio, video and image data (Timberlake, 2020). It is software that works faster and easier. Moreover, it is powerful and intuitive research software. However, there are few shortfalls of this software too. The reason behind not selecting NVivo in this dissertation for interview purpose is that this software is less reliable and cannot handle tough work. The issue of file corruption is also common on NVivo that creates the issue of data loss. Moreover, utilisation of two software in the research could increase the time and could create the issue towards timely submission.

Factor and Correlation analysis:

The factor analysis can be defined as the statistical approach which can identify and assess the interrelationship among a large number of variables and describes the underlying factors to these variables (McDonald, 2014). Apart from this, factor analysis can be said as the procedure of reduction in the data set and summarization. The main aim of the factor analysis is to identify and assess the underlying factors to the relationship among the identified variables in the given

research. If the value found in the factor analysis is less value than 0.50, then the results from factor analysis cannot be said useful in the research (Mandel, 2012). The value found small value and less than the significance value of 0.05 may be useful in research. Moreover, it also aims at identifying the independent variable. The people who follow the factor analytic method believe that the information gained can be used later for reducing the set of variables. Factor analysis is made of two types such as exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis (McDonald, 2014). On the other hand, correlation analysis is defined as the measure of finding an association between variables (Schober, 2018). For instance, Pearson's correlation coefficient aims towards defining the association of two continuous variables and it provides the measure of the direction and the strength of the association of two variables. In addition, Chi-Square test is among the correlation analysis tools which provides comparison of the outcome of expected measures to meet the conditions of the given hypothesis, in other words, it is used to test to the validity of the hypothesis by providing an outcome regarding the validity of an association among variables. Moreover, the Cross-tabs is a method to provide a quantitative analysis of the strength of the relationship between various variables and it helps researchers eliminate the confusion while interpreting the data using Phi coefficient, Carmer's V, and Contingency coefficient; these variables together determine the strength of the association among variables.

Data representation:

Data representation is the interpretation and presentation of the findings derived from the data through data analysis. This is very important to help the people to understand the result effectively and properly in the same manner. This helps the decision-makers to understand the actual information and findings, which can be used to take an effective decision regarding the research problem (Flick, 2011). Data representation of survey questionnaire has taken place through tables, charts, graphs, pictures, and others. The researcher in this research used

different kinds of charts and graphs to represent and interpret the finding of the research. The researcher used the charts and graphs to show the response of the participants including how many participants gave what rank (Wickham, 2016). Apart from this, tables are used to show the classification of the data over different options in the given questionnaire. This helped in identifying the participants chosen strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree and others. Simultaneously, the findings of the interview are represented through quoted statements to understand the research topic subjectively.

Triangulation Situation:

Triangulation method can be described as a method that is used for multiple operationalizations. It helps to separate the other irrelevancies in the operationalization while utilising multiple measures (Turner, et al., 2017). It allows applying multiple theories, analyses, methodologies and research designs in the study. The utilisation of a single measure for the data analyses has the possibility of error and biases. So, utilization of multiple measures assists in this context to overcome these challenges and to develop more reliable research outcome.

In the context of undertaken research; survey questionnaire, interviews with managers and interviews with workers are conducted which has assisted to develop the research outcome on the basis of triangulation situation as the findings of all the three collected data is focused towards addressing the same topic areas.

Figure 11: Triangulation Situation

(Source: Created by the researcher- July 2020)

Utilization of triangulation situation has supported to develop better research outcome by supporting to see the research outcome from multiple perspectives.

3.11 Time Horizon

Time horizon is also a crucial element of the research study. The time horizon aids in developing the plan and programs for accomplishing the research effectively in time. The time horizon can be categorized into longitudinal time the horizon and cross-sectional Time horizon. The longitudinal research helps in getting views of the respondents in a different time period in order to achieve research objectives (Kushner and Dupuis, 2013). On the other hand, cross-sectional research is the research that gathers the information from the same respondent in a time period such as a day, month, and a week but the information gathered must be on different aspects such as demographic, salary, and age.

Therefore, the researcher in this research has used the cross-sectional time horizon to identify the effects of learning work culture on the development and growth of the employees and

sustainability of the business of Primark in the UK. The researcher had decided to use this time horizon because cross-sectional time horizon or cross-sectional research gathers data on the different aspects of the research problem in a single period of time (Kushner and Dupuis, 2013). The cross-sectional time horizon research has helped the researcher in this research to gather the data regarding different aspects of the research problem such as employees' motivation, workplace sustainability, the satisfaction of employees, development of employees, morale of employees, and productivity and performance of the employees. Apart from this, the cross-sectional time horizon research is cost-effective in nature against longitudinal research that is why the researcher decided to use cross-sectional research.

3.12 Ethical issues

The researcher in this research study has considered all the ethical issues to ensure effective research. The researcher has given the reference of the actual authors whose sources have been used in this research for getting the information about the learning work culture, how learning culture is established, how learning culture is important, how it helps in workplace sustainability and factors affects learning work culture at the workplace (Gray, 2013). This is necessary to provide credit to the author for removing the invalid activities in the research. This proves the research is valid. Apart from this, this researcher has used the information collected from the respondents, only for resolving the research problem (Schutt, 2011). Along with this, the personal information is kept secret and confidential. Therefore, all the ethical points and rules in the research have been complied with.

3.13 Accessibility Issue

The accessibility can be termed as how the researcher accesses to the research participants in the research study to collect the information. In this research study, the accessibility issue may occur as the research is going to research the views of the employees. Every organization is concerned about the internal information and does not want to disclose the information can

cause an unfavourable environment (Stolarski et al., 2014). Therefore, the researcher approached the higher authorities in Primark and got the approval for researching the employees of the organization. The researcher got the consent of the higher authorities surveying the employees by assuring that the employees will not be asked and forced to disclose any unwanted information by the organization.

The higher authorizations were informed about the purpose and benefit of this research. They were convinced that the research may be beneficial for Primark in developing possible actions and strategies to resolve the issues at the workplace. This research may help in ensuring workplace sustainability and the sustainability of the organization in a competitive business environment. A proposal was sent to them for complying with the formalities and procedure of the organization.

3.14 Research Limitations

The research limitation is the possible drawbacks of the research. Every research has some limitations regarding research objectives, scope, selection of methods for data collection, the scope of the discussion, and execution of methods of data collection. Along with this, the limitation may be related to the resources in the research, cost of the research, and time to be consumed in the research. If the research objectives are defined very broadly it reduces the concentration and focus (Shipman, 2014). The objective should be narrow easily focused and achieved. Broad objectives create confusion and make the research complex. Along with this, the selection of data collection methods may limit the research study. Selection of wrong data collection methods may affect the result of the study. If the researcher does not have any experience in the primary research. It can limit the research study in terms of convincing the participants and extracting the information from them.

Similarly, there are some issues in this research study that may affect the effectiveness of the research. The effectiveness of the research may be measured in terms of time, cost, and results.

The major issue may be called as the time constraint. The research is too vast that is somewhat impossible to complete in the given time period. Apart from this, the cost constraint is also one more big issue in this research. The researcher has used the survey methodology for collecting the primary data that may cause budget constraint in the research. The researcher cannot access to a number of participants at one time to fill up the questionnaire. Thus, the researcher used email to distribute the questionnaire among participants. But it may be that the participants ignore the email and do not provide the filled questionnaire. At the same time, there may be a sampling error in the research. The researcher has to take the sample from the employees working in a different department at Primark. However, it is possible that the researcher may be biased in sampling. This can affect the quality and reliability of the research as the result produced is based on the sample analysis which might lead towards the wrong result.

3.16 Hypothesis Development

Implementing a successful Learning Work Culture strategy within organizations and firms is critical nowadays as most companies who provide a learning work culture to their employees have a higher rate of motivation and their productivity significantly increases as they are always subject to learn new skills and develop themselves to serve the company better (Hošková-Mayerová, 2015). This research's main question is what is the relationship between the learning work culture and the performance of the workplace? And this question leads us to a hypothesis of the research (H1) and a null hypothesis of the research (H0) which are explained as follows:

H0- There is no relationship between sustainability and the learning work environment.

H1- There is a significant relationship between sustainability and the learning work environment.

3.17 Chapter Summary

From the above analysis, it can be said that the research methodology is a critical and more valued section in the research study that helps in creating valid and reliable information for solving the research problem effectively. The study of the research methods helps the researcher in developing his or her understanding of the research methods, the importance of the research methods, and procedure of the research methodology that can help in conducting the research effectively and efficiently. Furthermore, it is found that the research methodology comprises of the research methods to be used in the following research. It provides the blueprint in advance that which methods have to be used in the research study.

Along with this, it is found that the researcher in this research study has used pragmatic research philosophy, inductive research approach, descriptive research design, and qualitative and quantitative research type. At the same time, the researcher decided to collect both primary and secondary data in the research. The researcher has used survey questionnaire and interview to collect both primary data. Survey questionnaire helped in collecting accurate and reliable data from the respondents. The survey methodology helped in getting the information required for attaining the research objectives. At the same time, the researcher used various tools such as SPSS, factor analysis, correlation and regression, statistical analysis, and others analysis tools for analysing the data effectively and accurately. Eventually, the researcher has used the graphs and charts to interpret and represent the finding of the research.

Chapter 4: Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter illustrates the analysed and collected data providing meaningful outcomes for the successful completion of the study. The researcher, in this chapter, engages an analysis of both the primary and secondary data. For this research, the researcher conducted surveys with the aim of gathering responses which are presented through tables and graphs with the help of SPSS data analysis. The use of SPSS framework in order to analyse the data enabled the researcher to reach acceptable reliability of the gathered data and provided valid research outcomes. At the same time, this chapter also analyses the interview findings. On the basis of the survey questionnaire and interview data, research findings are developed.

4.2 Survey Analysis

For this study, a number of 200 Primark workers have been targeted by the research in order to collect the data through a survey questionnaire. However, among 200 workers of Primark, only 150 gave their opinion and decided to contribute in the surveys as some of them didn't show any interest and others claimed to have lack of time to answer the research's questions. Hence, overall, the participating rate for this study was rated 75%, which can be said quite effective. The entire data collected was stored in the digital device in a safe manner and it was analysed by using SPSS software on the system to present the findings in tables and graphs as below.

4.2.1 Hypothesis

H0- There is no relationship between sustainability and the learning work environment.

H1- There is a significant relationship between sustainability and the learning work environment.

4.2.2 Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.646	25

Table 3: The Reliability Test

Cronbach's alpha reliability test used to measure the internal consistency that allows evaluating how a set of items are closely related to each other as a group (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011). It is a measure of scale reliability that is not based on the statistical test but on coefficient. It represents a coefficient of reliability or consistency. According to the generally accepted rule of Cronbach's Alpha; the value of α between 0.6-0.95 represents an acceptable level of reliability. However, the values that are higher than 0.95 is not considered as good. Negative Cronbach's alpha represents that coding is inconsistent and there are negative inter-item correlations.

From the above table, it can be interpreted that the reliability test result is the.646 that means the research is useful and collected data is useful and authentic.

4.2.3 Demographic Questions

Table 4 Age Limit

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 25	35	23.3	23.3	23.3
	25-40	83	55.3	55.3	78.7
	41-50	19	12.7	12.7	91.3
	Above 50	13	8.7	8.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 12 Age Limit

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Table 4 demonstrates the employees who responded to the survey in terms of their age limit where the collected data indicates the availability of young professionals which their age varies from 25 until 40 years old. From the above table, it can be interpreted that most of the respondents were 25-40 ages of a group that means the firm rely on to have the young and dynamic people for the business. It is because it helps the firm to effectively change the business and to develop a good business platform. At the same time, it can also be interpreted that some of the respondents were also below 25 ages of the group and some were 41-50 and above 50.

Table 5 Gender Specification

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	90	60.0	60.0	60.0
	Female	60	40.0	40.0	100.0

	Total	150	100.0	100.0	
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(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 13 Gender Specification

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

As per the table above illustrates, the participants in the survey are both male and female who collect the diversified views & get the bias-free results based on gender. Moreover, the males have over numbered the females because it was easier to conduct a survey on males on time.

Table 6 Working Year

Total working EXP					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Last 1 year	30	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2-4 years	75	50.0	50.0	70.0
	5-7 years	19	12.7	12.7	82.7
	More than 7 years	26	17.3	17.3	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- 2020)

Figure 14 Working experience

(Source: Created by the researcher- 2020)

From the above table, it can be determined that in the firm (Primark), there are various employees who have been working since last so many years at the firm. But in like manner, it can also be stated that most of the respondents have been working from last 5-7 years. As well as, some of the respondents have been working from last 2-4 years and more than 7 years also. Because of this, it can be interpreted that there are different employees in the firm who are putting their effort into the success of the firm.

4.2.4 Questions Related to The Research Topic

Table 7 Operate the Business in Different Countries

Business challenges					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	99	66.0	66.0	66.0
	No	51	34.0	34.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- 2020)

Figure 15 Operating the business in different countries

(Source: Created by the researcher- 2020)

When it is asked to the participants that do they think that operating business in different countries is a challenge for Primark then 66% of participants have responded in yes whereas 34% have responded in no. From the above table, it can be identified that there was a positive view of most of the respondents regarding the above question. Because of this, it can be interpreted that there is a positive view of most of the respondents about operating the business in different countries is quite challenging for the firm. It reflects that while dealing in the international market, Primark has to face various challenges.

Table 8 UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries

The UK is the biggest industry					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	73	48.7	48.7	48.7
	Agree	30	20.0	20.0	68.7
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	78.0

Disagree	23	15.3	15.3	93.3
Strongly Disagree	10	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- 2020)

Figure 16 UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

This table illustrates that most of the respondents have strongly agreed that UK Retail industry is one of the fast and growing industry in the UK. There are different retails firms in the UK that are providing their products & service for the customers.

Table 9 Learning work culture is mandatory

Learning work culture is vital					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	42.7	42.7	42.7
	Agree	35	23.3	23.3	66.0
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	75.3

	Disagree	19	12.7	12.7	88.0
	Strongly Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 17 Learning work culture is mandatory

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be stated that most of the respondents strongly agreed on, in order to successfully and effectively manage the business at an international level, there is a need for the firm to have the effective learning work culture.

Table 10 Achieve the Goals and Objectives

Achieve the goals and objectives					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	73	48.7	48.7	48.7
	Agree	30	20.0	20.0	68.7
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	78.0

Disagree	23	15.3	15.3	93.3
Strongly Disagree	10	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 18 Achieve the Goals and Objectives

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be defined that most of the respondents strongly agreed on that learning work culture helps the firm to achieve the goals and the objectives of the firm.

Table 11 Reducing the risks and issue

Reducing risks					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	73	48.7	48.7	48.7
	Agree	25	16.7	16.7	65.3
	Neutral	10	6.7	6.7	72.0
	Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	84.0
	Strongly Disagree	24	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 19 Reducing the risks and issue

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be interpreted that the learning work culture is not only helpful for achieving the goals and the objectives, but it is also helpful for reducing the risk and the issues. In this, most of the respondents stated that they have their positive concern on that learning work culture helps to reduce the risks.

Table 12 Encourage problem solving

Encourage problem-solving					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	42.7	42.7	42.7
	Agree	35	23.3	23.3	66.0
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	75.3
	Disagree	19	12.7	12.7	88.0
	Strongly Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 20 Encourage the problem solving

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be stated that most of the respondents strongly agreed on the fact that learning work culture helps the firm in the problem solving that is quite necessary for the firms to successfully operate the business and to develop a good customer base in the international market.

Table 13 Successfully implementation of CSR

CSR implementation					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	69	46.0	46.0	46.0
	Agree	28	18.7	18.7	64.7
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	74.0
	Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	86.0
	Strongly Disagree	21	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 21 Successfully implementation of CSR

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be determined that most of the respondents were strongly agreed on that learning work culture also helps the firm successfully implement the CSR.

Table 14 Increase the productivity of employees

Productivity Increase					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	73	48.7	48.7	48.7
	Agree	25	16.7	16.7	65.3
	Neutral	10	6.7	6.7	72.0
	Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	84.0
	Strongly Disagree	24	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 22 Increase the productivity of employees

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the above table, it can be interpreted that learning work culture is also helpful in order to increase the productivity of employees that assist the firm to sustain in the market.

Table 15 others

Other					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	64	42.7	42.7	42.7
	Agree	35	23.3	23.3	66.0
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	75.3
	Disagree	19	12.7	12.7	88.0
	Strongly Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 23 others

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that most of the respondents strongly agreed on the successful implementation of CSR increases the productivity of employees, etc., there are some other benefits of using the learning work culture in the firm. In this, it is also stated from different respondents that the learning work culture is also helpful in workplace sustainability, reduce energy and fuel costs, effective communication, etc., that helps the firm to sustain in the market and to develop an effective base of the customer in the international market.

Table 16 Employees' Engagement

Employees Engagement					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	38	25.3	25.3	69.3
	Neutral	8	5.3	5.3	74.7
	Disagree	16	10.7	10.7	85.3

	Strongly Disagree	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 24 Employees' Engagement

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

As per the table above demonstrates, the majority of the participants (approximately 69%) stated their consent regarding the engagement of workers as an obstacle in the development of the learning culture at the workplace which affects the business' performance.

Table 17 Cost

Cost					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	73	48.7	48.7	48.7
	Agree	25	16.7	16.7	65.3
	Neutral	10	6.7	6.7	72.0
	Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	84.0

Strongly Disagree	24	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 25 Cost Frequency

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be interpreted that most of the respondents 73 out of 150 strongly agreed on having the cost as one of the main problems faced by the firm to manage and develop an effective learning work culture.

Table 18 Management Practices

Management practices					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	69	46.0	46.0	46.0
	Agree	28	18.7	18.7	64.7
	Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	74.0
	Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	86.0

Strongly Disagree	21	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 26 Management Practices

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that most of the respondents strongly agreed on the successful implementation of the management practices which represents another major factor that makes the cause of successful implementation of management practices.

Table 19 Organizational culture and climate

Organizational culture and climate					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	38	25.3	25.3	69.3
	Neutral	8	5.3	5.3	74.7
	Disagree	16	10.7	10.7	85.3

Strongly Disagree	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 27 Organizational culture and climate

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be stated that from the different respondents, it is determined that culture and the climate are also the major reason that affects the learning work culture of the firm. In support of this, in the research of Henning et al. (2009), it is defined that in a firm, people are different on the basis of demographic, geographic, etc. So, in order to manage this issue, there are different programs and functions which are conducted by the firm. And, as a result of this, it can be determined that the culture and climate are the major factors that affect the learning work culture.

Table 20 change in the technology

Technology Change					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	34	22.7	22.7	66.7
	Neutral	15	10.0	10.0	76.7
	Disagree	20	13.3	13.3	90.0
	Strongly Disagree	15	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 28 change in the technology

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that there were positive views of most of the respondents regarding that change in the technology is the major factor that affects the learning work culture. Mainly, due to the change in the technology, the firm has to adopt the new technology that causes an increasing cost and some changes at internal and external level. All these changes make the cause of affecting the learning work culture.

Table 21 Increasing level of the competition

Competition level					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	38	25.3	25.3	69.3
	Neutral	8	5.3	5.3	74.7
	Disagree	16	10.7	10.7	85.3
	Strongly Disagree	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 29 Increasing level of the competition

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be stated that most of the respondents strongly agreed on the fact that increasing levels of the competition is also one of the major issues that affect the business and the learning work culture concept of the firm.

Table 22 Other

Other1					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	65	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Agree	40	26.7	26.7	70.0
	Neutral	15	10.0	10.0	80.0
	Disagree	17	11.3	11.3	91.3
	Strongly Disagree	13	8.7	8.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 30 Other

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that there were also different other issues that also affect the learning work culture of the firm. In this, in the research of Schroeder (2013), it is stated that low decisions making power of the firm, employees' stress, negative attitude, etc., are the major reasons that make the cause of affecting the learning work culture of the firm.

Table 23 Formulate the best strategy

Formulate best strategy					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	34	22.7	22.7	66.7
	Neutral	15	10.0	10.0	76.7
	Disagree	20	13.3	13.3	90.0
	Strongly Disagree	15	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 31 Formulate the best strategy

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that the majority of the respondents strongly agreed on the fact that formulating the best strategy is a great way possible that the firm can use to manage the problems that affect the learning work culture and helps in the success of an organization.

Table 24 Managing and developing people

Managing developing people					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	38	25.3	25.3	69.3
	Neutral	8	5.3	5.3	74.7
	Disagree	16	10.7	10.7	85.3
	Strongly Disagree	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 32 Managing and developing people

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that majority respondents strongly agreed on the fact that managing and developing people is the best way that can be used by the firms to manage the workplace sustainability and the learning work culture.

Table 25 Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc.

Honesty integrity trustworthiness etc					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	65	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Agree	40	26.7	26.7	70.0
	Neutral	15	10.0	10.0	80.0
	Disagree	17	11.3	11.3	91.3
	Strongly Disagree	13	8.7	8.7	100.0
	Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 33 Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc.

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that most of the respondents have their positive view on the fact that there are also some other factors like honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, that are also used by the firm to develop the workplace sustainability and to develop a learning work culture.

Table 26 Better use of existing resources

Use of existing sources					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	80	53.3	53.7	53.7
	Agree	22	14.7	14.8	68.5
	Neutral	11	7.3	7.4	75.8
	Disagree	20	13.3	13.4	89.3
	Strongly Disagree	15	10.0	10.1	99.3
	45	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	149	99.3	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.7		
Total		150	100.0		

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that there were positive responses of the different respondents on the fact that the better use of the existing resources can also be helpful for the firm to develop the workplace sustainability and to effectively manage the learning work culture.

Table 27 Implementation of new and better technology

new and modern technology					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Agree	38	25.3	25.3	69.3

Neutral	8	5.3	5.3	74.7
Disagree	16	10.7	10.7	85.3
Strongly Disagree	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 34 Implementation of new and better technology

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be stated that 66 respondents from 150 agreed on the fact that implementing new and modern technology is one of the best and effective way that contribute to the success of the firm.

Table 28 Others

Other2					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	69	46.0	46.0	46.0
	Agree	28	18.7	18.7	64.7

Neutral	14	9.3	9.3	74.0
Disagree	18	12.0	12.0	86.0
Strongly Disagree	21	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Figure 35 Others

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

From the table above, it can be determined that most of the respondents have their positive view of the fact that there are also some other factors such as customer relation, customer relationship management, ethical marketing, etc., that can be used by the firm to get success in the market.

Correlation

Table 29 Correlation Between Variables Using Pearson's Correlation

Correlations							
		learning work culture is vital	achieve the goals and objectives	Reducing risks	Encourage problem-solving	CSR implementation	Productivity Increase
learning work culture is vital	Pearson Correlation	1	.039	-.241**	1.000**	.223**	-.241**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.632	.003	.000	.006	.003
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
achieve the goals and objectives	Pearson Correlation	.039	1	.252**	.039	.071	.252**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.632		.002	.632	.390	.002
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
Reducing risks	Pearson Correlation	-.241**	.252**	1	-.241**	.063	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.002		.003	.441	.000
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
Encourage problem-solving	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	.039	-.241**	1	.223**	-.241**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.632	.003		.006	.003
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150

CSR implementation	Pearson Correlation	.223**	.071	.063	.223**	1	.063
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.390	.441	.006		.441
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
Productivity Increase	Pearson Correlation	-.241**	.252**	1.000**	-.241**	.063	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.002	.000	.003	.441	
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

Based on the first questions, Pearson's correlation was engaged in order to demonstrate the availability of a linear relationship between the variables. From the table above, it can be determined that there is a correlation between different variables. At the same time, there is a positive correlation between learning work cultures and to achieve the goals and objectives. In order to proceed to an enhanced analysis of the data, Spearman's correlation is also adapted where its coefficient is scaled from -1 to +1 (Schober, 2018).

The following table demonstrates the correlation between the various variables of the research study:

Table 30 Spearman's rho Correlation

Correlations								
			learning work culture is vital	achieve the goals and objectives	Reducing Risks	Encourage Problem-solving	CSR Implementation	Productivity Increase
Spearman's rho	learning work culture is vital	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.900*	.900*	1.000**	.900*	.900*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.037	.037	.	0.37	.037
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5
	achieve the goals and objectives	Correlation Coefficient	.900*	1.000	.700	.900*	.700	.700
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.	.188	.037	.188	.188
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Reducing risks	Correlation Coefficient	.900*	.700	1.000	.900*	1.000**	1.000**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.188	.	.037	.	.
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Encourage problem-solving	Correlation Coefficient	1.000**	.900*	.900*	1.000	.900*	.900*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.037	.037	.	.037	0.37
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5
	CSR implementation	Correlation Coefficient	.900*	.700	1.000**	.900*	1.000	1.000**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.188	.	0.37	.	.
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5
	Productivity Increase	Correlation Coefficient	.900*	.700	1.00**	.900*	1.000**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	.188	.	0.37	.	.
		N	5	5	5	5	5	5

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

As per the table above demonstrates, there is a correlation between the various variables which are indicated in the table. Additionally, there is an existence of a positive correlation among learning work culture and the reach of goals and objectives of firms. The usage of Spearman's correlation is correct for Likert scales as the sum of scores is used which convert the scale from ordinal to ratio level of measurement. Moreover, one advantage of using Spearman's rho, is that it doesn't matter whether you believe the Likert scales generate interval level or ordinal level data since Spearman's correlation works for both.

Furthermore, in order to finalize the analysis of the available variables, the Chi-square test will be engaged. The Chi-square is a statistics tool which is used to provide an analysis of group differences when the dependent variables are measured at a nominal level (McHugh, 2013).

Table 31 Chi-Square Test

Test Statistics						
	Table14	Table13	Table12	Table11	Table10	Table9
Chi-Square	81.800 ^a	66.867 ^a	56.733 ^a	81.800 ^a	85.133 ^a	53.800 ^a
df	4	4	4	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 30.0.

The table above represents the Chi-square analysis which was engaged for this research using IBM SPSS Statistics Data Editor indicates Chi-square analysis results for the suggested variables. In the Chi-square test specifically the expected count varies according to the variables chosen with the vitality of learning work culture. However, the actual data and expected data are identical, hence the Chi-square value is 0.

The researcher has conducted an analysis through cross-tabs of all the six variables which are mentioned in the questionnaire (Appendix 2, p.251) where the categorical variables were cross-

tabed with all the likert scales variables; a detailed list of the cross-tabs and the chi-square run is given in the Appendix (Appendix 3, p.254) which illustrates the case processing summary of the cross-tabs application on the entire variables of the research which results 84 tables. After analysing the results of the cross-tabs and analysing all the variables, it is demonstrated that many variables show that there is no significance which indicates a technical problem. Hence, these variables aren't used to demonstrate the significance of the association of variables. However, the researcher has used the 42 tables that satisfy both criteria which demonstrates that the results are highly significant, and they meet the technical requirement of having no more than 20% of the cells with expected count less than 5. These tables are attached to the Appendix (Appendix 4, p.278).

The following figure illustrates four tables of the cross-tab results which are chosen from Appendix (Appendix 4, p.278) to demonstrate the significance of the variables and the results. The tables chosen are (Table 38 p.278; Table 39 p. 281; Table 40 p. 285; Table 41 p. 288); and they are attached below as follows:

Table 38: UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	81.1%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	17	13	30
		Expected Count	18.0	12.0	30.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	56.7%	43.3%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	18.9%	21.7%	20.0%
		% of Total	11.3%	8.7%	20.0%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
	Disagree	Count	0	23	23

		Expected Count	13.8	9.2	23.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	38.3%	15.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	15.3%	15.3%
	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
		Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
		% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150	
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0	
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%	
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)

Pearson Chi-Square	119.306 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	160.850	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	107.275	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		
a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.892	.000
	Cramer's V	.892	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.666	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

According to the table above which demonstrates the cross-tab of UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Gender Specification. As per the table of symmetric measure above demonstrate, the Phi correlation and Cramer's V which indicates the strength of the association between the variables are the same value of 89.2% because of the variable's structure where they are both nominal and dichotomous and they are almost equal to 100%. However, the Contingency Coefficient with the value of 66.6% is smaller than 100% and this is due to the degrees of freedom. These results indicate the presence of a highly significant strength of association among the variables. In addition, the Chi-Square results with the value of 10% meets the requirement criteria where it's less than 20% which have expected count less than 5, which indicates the presence of a highly significant association among the variables.

Moreover, these results indicate the presence of an association between the results and the gender of the interviewee.

Table 39: UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab					
			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	73.7%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	26	4	30
		Expected Count	19.8	10.2	30.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	86.7%	13.3%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	26.3%	7.8%	20.0%
		% of Total	17.3%	2.7%	20.0%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14

		Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	27.5%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
	Disagree	Count	0	23	23
		Expected Count	15.2	7.8	23.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	45.1%	15.3%
	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
		Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	19.6%	6.7%
	Total	Count	99	51	150
Expected Count		99.0	51.0	150.0	

	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	134.551 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	168.750	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	117.563	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.947	.000
	Cramer's V	.947	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.688	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

According to the table above which demonstrates the cross-tab of UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Operate the Business in Different Countries. As per the table of symmetric measure above demonstrate, the Phi correlation and Cramer's V which indicates the strength of the association between the variables are the same value of 94.7% because of the variable's structure where they are both nominal and dichotomous and they are almost equal to 100%. However, the Contingency Coefficient with the value of 68.8% is smaller than 100% and this is due to the degrees of freedom. These results indicate the presence of a highly significant strength of association among the variables. In addition, the Chi-Square results with the value of 20% meets the requirement criteria where it's equal to 20% which have expected count less than 5; which indicates the presence of a highly significant association among the variables.

Table 40: Learning work culture is mandatory * Gender Specification

Crosstab					
			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Learning work culture is mandatory	Strongly Agree	Count	63	0	63
		Expected Count	37.8	25.2	63.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	70.0%	0.0%	42.0%
		% of Total	42.0%	0.0%	42.0%
	Agree	Count	27	8	35
		Expected Count	21.0	14.0	35.0

		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	77.1%	22.9%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	30.0%	13.3%	23.3%
		% of Total	18.0%	5.3%	23.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
	Disagree	Count	0	20	20
		Expected Count	12.0	8.0	20.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	33.3%	13.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
		Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total		Count	90	60	150

	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	124.286 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	164.275	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	109.738	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.910	.000
	Cramer's V	.910	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.673	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

According to the table above which demonstrates the cross-tab of Learning work culture is mandatory * Gender Specification. As per the table of symmetric measure above demonstrate, the Phi correlation and Cramer's V which indicates the strength of the association between the variables are the same value of 91% because of the variable's structure where they are both nominal and dichotomous and they are almost equal to 100%. However, the Contingency Coefficient with the value of 67.3% is smaller than 100% and this is due to the degrees of freedom. These results indicate the presence of a highly significant strength of association among the variables. In addition, the Chi-Square results with the value of 0% meets the requirement criteria where it's less than 20% which have expected count less than 5; which indicates the presence of a highly significant association among the variables. Moreover, these results indicate the presence of an association between the results and the gender of the interviewee.

Table 41: Learning work culture is mandatory * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab					
			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Strongly Agree	Count	63	0	63	
	Expected Count	41.6	21.4	63.0	

Learning work culture is mandatory		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0 %
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	63.6%	0.0%	42.0%
		% of Total	42.0%	0.0%	42.0%
	Agree	Count	35	0	35
		Expected Count	23.1	11.9	35.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0 %
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	35.4%	0.0%	23.3%
		% of Total	23.3%	0.0%	23.3%
	Neutral	Count	1	13	14
		Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	7.1%	92.9%	100.0 %
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	1.0%	25.5%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.7%	8.7%	9.3%
	Disagree	Count	0	20	20
		Expected Count	13.2	6.8	20.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0 %

		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	39.2%	13.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
		Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
		% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150	
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0	
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.862 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.106	4	.000

Linear-by-Linear Association	121.843	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		
a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.986	.000
	Cramer's V	.986	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: Created by the researcher- September 2020)

According to the table above which demonstrates the cross-tab of Learning work culture is mandatory * Gender Specification. As per the table of symmetric measure above demonstrate, the Phi correlation and Cramer's V which indicates the strength of the association between the variables are the same value of 98.6% because of the variable's structure where they are both nominal and dichotomous and they are almost equal to 100%. However, the Contingency Coefficient with the value of 70.2% is smaller than 100% and this is due to the degrees of freedom. These results indicate the presence of a highly significant strength of association among the variables. In addition, the Chi-Square results with the value of 10% meets the requirement criteria where it's less than 20% which have expected count less than 5; which indicates the presence of a highly significant association among the variables.

4.3 Interview Analysis

The interview was conducted on 12 participants (6 managers and 6 employees) who were selected through a non-probability sampling method. The entire data collected through the interview was stored in the digital device in a safe manner which was analysed in a subjective manner.

4.3.1 Interview Analysis of Managers

1. Members in a management team

When it was asked to the participants to reveal the number of participants in the management team, then it is identified that the number of management teams was different from different managers. However, it is also analysed that the minimum team member was 4 and the maximum was 8.

2. Policies regarding the development of learning work culture

When it is asked to the managers that do they follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture then different participants have given different views regarding their policies related to training and development. From the views of the participants, it is analysed that 5 participants have shared their views regarding the policies used by them for developing LWC. For instance, M1 responded that *'In order to develop an enhanced learning work culture, I am entitled to follow a number of various policies such as training & development policy which will boost the employees' levels of skills to be as desired by the business, the employee development policy which contributes to increasing the satisfaction of the current employees & their motivation to give their best for the company, and corporate training programs which enhance the efficiency and the morals of the employees, and it also reduces their weaknesses.'* However, M6 has shown denial from this statement. M6 responded that *'No, we do not follow any policies to develop a learning work culture within the business. During the hiring process, we carefully select the candidates who have enough experience to be able to deliver the*

required performance during their job. Hence, the availability of the experienced staff will eliminate the need for training the amateurs who cannot deal with some issues & cannot find efficient solutions for the business.'

3. Ways that are used by the management department for developing a learning work culture

When it is asked to the managers that what are the ways that are used by their management department for developing a learning work culture, then it is analysed that almost every manager was agreed that their business utilises different ways for developing LWC. For instance, M3 responded that *'The company aims to enhance the learning work culture as it has an immense value to bring for the business. The management department organises events & training for the development of the employees' skills. These training doesn't just bring value for the business but the employees as well; once they feel the value the business has for them, they start doing their best to impress the managers & the directors which will increase the productivity of the employees & it will enhance the performance & the profit of the business.'* However, in the contrary, views of M6 have shown contrary view as he responded that *'Currently, the business doesn't invest in developing a learning work culture.'*

4. Developing learning work culture creates an issue for the management

In the context of the above question, it is identified that 5 participants agreed that developing a learning work culture creates an issue for the management however 1 participant (Manager 3) has shown denial from it. M3 responded that *'No, I do not think that creating a learning work culture will cause any problems for the management department. As a manager, I think that the competitiveness which the learning work culture brings among employees has a positive effect as it will increase their productivity & it can be taken as an advantage to enhance the performance of the business. Moreover, the training to be provided for the employees might cost a bit but it can be caught up from the profit to be made after those employees enhance their skills & bring up more profits for the business.'*

From the views of different participants, it is identified that there are different issues faced by management for creating LWC such as managerial issues, increase in company cost, increase investment of time, increases the competitiveness among employees where each person has the desire to be the most employable & the one employee to get most of the rewards, etc.

5. Role of learning work culture towards firm success

When the participants were asked that do they consider that in the success of their firm, LWC plays a very important role then all the participants have shown consensus from it accept M6. He responded that *'I believe that the company can succeed even without implementing a learning work culture. The only thing it needs to replace it is to wisely select its employees according to the goals assigned to achieve and to the skills as well as the experience of the candidates applying for the jobs. Moreover, once the employee stays long enough in the business automatically increases his experience & manners of dealing with issues & finding effective solutions.'*

4.3.3 Interview Analysis of Employees

1. Job position

In the context of job position, it is analysed that all the selected employees are from different job profile. They are from the Sales assistant, accountant, advertising content writer, digital marketer, manufacture technician and fashion designer.

2. Working Experience

In the context of work experience, it is identified that all the selected employees in the interview were experienced where the minimum experience was 2 years and the maximum was 7 years.

3. Learning work culture helps to sustain in the firm

When the participants were asked to share their views regarding the role of learning work culture to help them sustain in the firm, then 5 participants have shown consensus from the statement. For instance, one of the employees (W5) responded that *'As I am a manufacturing*

technician, it is required for me to keep up with the advanced technologies which help the firm reduce the costs of production & increase the costs of the sales. This is due to the high-quality products which we are supposed to provide as a company; therefore, the learning work culture represents an aid for me to sustain in the company as it provides the opportunity to stay up to date with the knowledge to guarantee an excellent manufacture process which leads towards the goals assigned by the company.' However, 1 employee has shown denial from it (W6) and stated that *'Absolutely not. Building a learning work culture has nothing to do with sustaining in the company. As a fashion designer, I believe that sustaining in the company is related to how talented you are to deliver the best designs & the most innovative products to keep a competitive advantage. And this is what helps me sustain in the company, my talent in the design field which helps the company be ahead of others.'*

4. Learning work culture affects work and engagement

When it is asked to the participants that do the learning work culture affect their work and engagement in the work then 5 employees have shown consensus from it. For instance, 1 participant responded that I personally think that learning work culture which is developed in the aim of enhancing the firms' productivity & profit will also aim towards increasing the engagement of the employees at work. Developing a learning work culture makes us feel empowered, involved & valued, which enhances our motivation & makes us engage with the business to see higher profits due to our skills and motivation & innovative solutions. However, 1 employee has shown disagreement from it (W6) and stated that *'No, as I have previously mentioned the design field is focused on the talents & the visions of fashion styles which I illustrate for the company. My engagement in work is related to the number of styles I can draw & if they will appeal to the owners or not. As a designer, I judge the workers within this department based on their drawing talent & it has nothing to do with the learning work culture around them.'*

5. Learning work culture provides the opportunity to grow and to make a bright future

When it is asked to the participants that do they think that learning work culture provides an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future then it is analysed that 5 participants remain in favour to this statement. In this context, 1 of the participants responded (W3) that *'I believe that a learning work culture is related to my behaviour at work & it teaches me the most suitable manners and reactions when in crisis or when at ease. As an advertising manager, the advertisement market is full of challenges due to the consecutive and fast evolution of technological ways to attract customers & increase the number of sales in a short period of time; therefore, the learning work culture which I gain from Primark increases my understanding of the company's mission & it motivates me to find appropriate solutions & better plans to reach our target within the required time period. Hence, it increases my experience which will benefit me in my future career plans & personal goals.'*

However, on the contrary, 1 participant (W6) stated that *'No, I think that it's the experience, the innovation, and the will of the person, which leads towards a bright future. The learning work culture is not going to push the person towards accomplishing his goals, it will just give him the instructions to follow and it's up to this person to choose which path to take. Hence, growing and acquiring a bright future is in the hands of the employee himself, and it has nothing to do with the learning work culture.'*

4.4 Summary of Key Results

Summary of the key results/findings for the quantitative:

As a result of the quantitative research conducted above, it is significantly demonstrated that the learning work culture is remarkably related to the performance of the employees as it provides the necessary motivation to deliver the best outcomes and the highest productivity. However, not all employees agree on the importance of implementation of learning work culture within organizations as they stated the threat of losing their managerial

position due to the continuous development of staff and their promotion. Nevertheless, the hypothesis that indicates the presence of a relationship between the sustainability and the learning work culture is still supported as the results have demonstrated a positive relationship between the sustainability of the company and the implementation of a successful learning work culture.

Summary of the key results/findings for the qualitative:

The data demonstrated above indicate the presence of a positive relationship between the sustainability of the company and the learning work culture which can be implemented in various ways to provide an enhancement and development of the performance of employees by significantly developing their existing skills and introducing them to new solutions which helps them do their jobs in a the greatest and most innovative manner. Hence, the answer to the previous hypothesis questions is positive as there is a remarkable relationship between the performance and the sustainability of the company, and the implementation of learning work culture within the firm.

Demographic information of interview respondents:

The interview respondents are from different job position: Sales Assistant, Accountant, Advertising Content Writer, Digital Marketer, Manufacture Technician, and Fashion Designer. In addition to different working experience where 30 employees were recently hired and they worked in Primark for less than a year, 75 employees worked from two to four years, 19 employees worked from five to seven years, and 26 employees worked more than seven years at Primark. Regarding the gender of respondents 90 of them were male where 60 of them were female employees, in addition to the age of respondents, the majority of employees were from 25-40 years old where the rest varied from below 25, to between 41, 50 and above.

4.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter demonstrates the data which is collected for the research from the employees of the company through surveys and interviews. In addition to the hypothesis, the reliability test, the demographic questions which includes age limit, gender specification, working year, and questions related to the research topic as per the operation of Primark in different countries and regarding the learning work culture in retail industry. Moreover, a correlation was created to successfully conclude a positive correlation between learning work culture and achieving the objectives of the company. Finally, an interview analysis was engaged for the employees and the managers of Primark where the majority of individuals working for this company highlighted the importance of learning work culture within the firm and how the organization invests in implementing a successful learning work culture strategy in the aim of maintaining its leading position in the retail industry.

Chapter 5: Discussion of Findings

Through the data analysis engaged in this research, it is found that the hypothesis of the research is valid and there is a remarkable impact of learning work culture on the retail firms within the UK. In addition to the positive relationship between the implementation of learning work culture and the efficiency of the employees at the company. These findings are resulted through the primary data collected which demonstrates that groups of respondents aged between 25-40 have positively confirmed that companies rely on recruiting young and dynamic applicants for the business which helps the firm to effectively develop the business and reach its aims and objectives. Moreover, most of the participants of the survey were male which supported to understand that male population show more eager attitude to share their views regarding learning work culture as compared to female. In the context of selected participants, it is found that most of the respondents were working with the organization from last 5-7 years which reflects that due to positive work culture in the organization, there is high retention rate. Regarding the globalisation of the company and operating the business in different countries, it is identified that many challenges are present for the firm. The main reason for these challenges is the different aspects which are considered by the firm to successfully operate the business in any country its planning to expand to; moreover, it creates the issues of successful management for the business as the company should consider implementing advanced strategic methods to enhance the business' operations in order to get the success of the firm in the market and to win a competitive advantage.

Regarding the literature theory which supports the given hypothesis, in the research of Carmeli and Gittel (2009), it is defined that there are various factors such as increasing levels of the competition, market and customers' needs, etc., which creates an obstacle for the company to successfully operate the business globally. Hence, the challenge for the company to manage the business' operations out of the home country could be overtaken with the

implementation of learning work culture as the company's managers will enhance their existing knowledge regarding other cultures and other markets which will help in moving to those markets. Furthermore, it is found through this research that the UK retail industry is one of the leading industries due to the obligation of applying rules and regulations for companies when operating the business locally and internationally; in addition to the consumption level of individuals living in the UK towards retail firms which makes it easier for a retail company to effectively operate their business within the UK. Hence, most of the retail firms look forward to starting or expanding their business into the UK as it will help them get more profit and increase their customer base. In support of these findings, in the research of Carmeli et al. (2010), it is defined that due to the globalization and the free trades of the government, it is easy for the firm to effectively manage the business in and out of the country without facing any problem.

In terms of Learning Work Culture, it is demonstrated through this research that the implementation of a successful learning work culture within the business will open opportunities for the company widely and for the employees to get more success and to cope with different work-related issues and advanced technological solutions implemented within the firm. In addition to reducing the possibility of raising issues due to applying changes within the company's strategies, market plan, etc., as it allows employees to keep on track with the development of the business. Therefore, in order to reach the success of the business it is important to guarantee a successful Learning Work Culture implementation. In the favour of this statement, Jackson et al. (2011) stated that having a continuous change in the business and marketing strategy according to the new market and the customer needs is quite challenging for the firm but it is very rewarding. Hence, implementing Learning Work Culture makes the company reduce the issue of difficulty of employees adapting to the new systems such as change strategy, market plan, etc., and also helps the firm to keep on track the

business. Moreover, the findings of the interviews support the identifications of how Learning Work Culture improves the work's behaviour of the employees and it helps them build and grow opportunities which are highly necessary for creating a bright future.

In terms of the importance of learning work culture and workplace sustainability in the organizations, it is found that research analysis demonstrates that Learning Work Culture allows achieving the goals and objectives of the firm. This is due to the opportunities which learning work culture provides for the employees and it directly helps the firm to successfully operate the business and to achieve effectively its goals and objectives. In support of this statement, in the findings of Kinman et al. (2011), it is stated that in the learning work culture, employees learn the things related to the business that motivates them to put their full potential in the success of the firm and makes easy the firm to achieve the set business goals and objectives. In addition, Learning Work Culture helps to reduce the risks and issues of the business as it increases the chances of new innovative and technological solutions which helps the firm to deal with the current company's issues and challenges in a better way. In the support of this statement, in the findings of McAllister and McKinnon (2009), it is depicted that due to learning work culture, the firm always has new innovative and technological advancement tools that help the firm to grow up and to handle the different issues and the challenges. As a result of this, it can be interpreted that the learning work culture helps the companies to reduce risk and different issues.

Moreover, the interviewees have shown strong agreement to the statement of Learning Work Culture helps them to sustain in the firm as it increases the competitive advantage of the company and it enhances the performance of the employees. Hence, Learning Work Culture is found adequate in encouraging the problem solving which will make it easier and more successful for the company to operate the business in international markets and a successful implementation of the learning work culture within the firm will increase the employees'

motivation despite the cultural diversity; which increases the company's profits and productivity. the favour of this statement, in the research of Rai et al. (2009), it is exhibited that in the learning work culture environment, there are different programs such as skills test, providing the solution test, etc., that are conducted by the firm and all these tests increase the problem-solving skills of the people and mitigate the possibilities of arising any issues. As a result of this, it can be stated that learning work culture helps with problem solving.

In terms of implementing successful Corporate Social Responsibility, Learning Work Culture provide the motivation for the employees and assists the firm to perform better for the environment and for the corporate social responsibility. Therefore, there is a positive view of the respondents regarding that learning work culture helps to develop the CSR activity. In the same concern of this, in the research of Wang et al. (2009), it is determined that the use of learning work culture in the firm enables all the employees to think beyond and also made a positive perception of the employees towards the development of the society. It makes it easy for the firm to successfully and effectively implement CSR activities. However, not all respondents have agreed to this opinion as some of them strongly demonstrated how they believe that Learning Work Culture doesn't contribute to enhance the CSR activity within the society. These respondents justified their opinion by stating how the learning work culture focuses on employees' personal and professional development rather than developing the CSR within the firm. As a result of this, it can be stated that there is a limited role in the learning work culture in CSR development, although few numbers of respondents didn't agree on this point and they stated the necessity of having the effective learning work culture. Furthermore, increasing the productivity of employees is considered as one of the positive aspects of Learning Work Culture as it helps the firms to develop a positive view in the mind of the employees towards the firm. In the support of this, in the research of Wolf (2013), it is illustrated that the learning work culture develops the positive view of the employees

towards the firm and it helps them increase their productivity. Meanwhile, it is also found that there are some other benefits too of using learning work culture in the firm as it grants workplace sustainability, and it guarantees effective communication between team members in order to achieve their tasks successfully; these benefits help the firm to develop an effective customer base in the international market.

Regarding the factors which affects the learning work culture and the sustainability of the workplace, the researcher has found that there is a strong relationship between learning work culture and the employees' engagement as it helps to create a positive engagement of employees towards the changes to apply within the company in order to improve the business environment. The findings of Blok et al. (2015) are also consistent with the findings of the survey where it is required for the organizations to implement several particular policies & standards which might affect the morals and performance levels of the workers, and hence, it can affect the development of the learning work culture. In addition, the interview findings helps us identify that most of the managers agreed to follow policies of development of the learning work culture, especially through different training and development programs, it also revealed that learning work culture improves productivity while improving the work and the engagement of the employees.

Regarding the financial expenses on the implementation of learning work culture and developing it, there are different programs and activities which the company has to organize; these activities might be expensive and it's one of the big factors which affects the company during the implementation of the learning work culture. In support of this, Carmeli and Gittell. (2009) states, in their research, that successful management of all the activities related to the learning work culture requires the firm to spend a specific amount and that's what makes it the cause of high expense of the firm. So, as a result of this, it can be determined that the cost is a major issue which is faced by the firm in the development of learning work

culture. Moreover, it is highly demonstrated that it's required for the company to develop an effective management practices in order to create a learning work culture which could present an issue for the company as its supported by the research of Evans and Waite (2010), it is illustrated that management plays a crucial part in the success of any activity within the firm, which means in case of any miss management, the firm faces the overall business issue. Therefore, it can be clearly interpreted that management practices are the major problems that affect the learning work culture. However, from the interview findings also it is identified that there are different ways used by the management department for developing a learning work culture. Furthermore, the organizational culture and the climate represent two major factors that has an affect on the learning work culture of the company. As it is demonstrated by the research of Henning et al. (2009), it is defined that in a firm, people are different on the basis of demography, geography, etc. So, in order to manage this issue, there are different programs and functions which are conducted by the firm which will enhance the teamwork within the company despite the differentiation among the employees. Moreover, the interview findings supported the statement of developing a learning work culture creates issues for the management such as creating managerial issues, increasing the company's costs, increasing the investment of time, increasing the competitiveness among employees where each individual desires to be the most employable and to get the most bonuses which are promised to be given etc. Simultaneously, it is found that changes in technology and technological innovation represents a major factor which affects the learning work culture of the company as the firm has to adapt to the new technological solutions which causes an increased cost and changes within the internal and external activities.

The finding of the research has also supported a demonstration of the relationship between the increasing level of competition in the workplace and the development of the learning work culture. For instance, the research of Schroeder (2013), described that due to the changing

of the customers and the consumption of the product, the level of competition is also increasing. In like manner, due to continuous change in the customer needs, the firm is also bound to produce the products according to the need of the customer. So, as a result of this, it can be interpreted that increasing the level of the competition represents a major issue in the development of the learning work culture. Moreover, other issues could be listed which are affecting the learning work culture of the firm; the research of Schroeder (2013) supports this statement as it stated that low decisions making power of the firm, employees' stress, negative attitude, etc., are the major reasons that make the cause of affecting the learning work culture of the firm.

Regarding the context of providing the concern about strategies and planning of the firms in the international market, it is found that the best strategy is formulated through implementing an effective development of learning work culture. In the research of Jackson et al. (2011) it is analysed that if the firm has the best and effective marketing strategy then it will help the company earn a competitive advantage and make goodwill in the customers' mind that will help in the workplace sustainability and to develop a successful learning work culture. Moreover, this research has supported an identification of the management and development of individuals within the workplace, and how it is considered as the best method to be used by companies in order to manage the workplace sustainability and the learning work culture. For instance, the research of Henning et al. (2009), defines that if a company has the power and the capability to manage the employees and the positive concern in the develop of the employees then it will be helpful for the company to manage the workplace sustainability. Hence, as a result of this, it can be interpreted that managing and developing people is one of the best ways to develop the learning work culture and workplace sustainability. Furthermore, the research demonstrates how it is analysed that most of the individual have a positive view of the fact that there are also some other factors like honesty,

integrity, trustworthiness, accountability. In support of these findings, Chirico & Nordqvist (2010) stated that honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, etc., are the major factors that help the firm to sustain its position in the industry and develop a good consumer base. It also provides the benefits for the firm in terms of profitability and margin because of this, honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc., are the most important ways that can also be used by the company to manage the learning work culture. The research finding allows the researcher to develop and understanding that an enhanced use of the existing resources can be useful for the company to develop a workplace sustainability and to effectively manage the learning work culture. In addition, the research of Costello et al. (2011), demonstrates that optimum utilization of available resources increases the revenue of the firm and also overcomes the operational cost of the firm. Due to this, it can be stated that a better use of existing resources is an effective way to develop workplace sustainability. Furthermore, the collected data has supported to illustrate that implementing new and modern technology is one of the best and effective ways which contributes to the success of the company as the research of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009), stated that implementing the modern technology assists the firm to get success in the market and to grab the market opportunities. It also helps the firm to provide new and effective products in the market. So, it can be interpreted that the implementation of new and modern technology is a useable and an effective method to reach the desired objectives. In addition, the data which was collected from the interview has supported the finding of a successful implementation of learning work culture leads towards the success of the company as learning work culture plays a very core role. This is due to the majority of participants have agreed and confirmed the significant and positive relationship between implementing learning work culture strategy within the company and the enhancement of the productivity of employees which leads towards higher profits for the firm. However, there are other factors too such as customer relation, customer relationship management, ethical

marketing, etc., that can be used by the firm to get success in the market and win a competitive advantage. For instance, the findings of Hager and Hodkinson (2009) supported this statement by illustrating that all these different aspects assist the firm to manage all the business operations and to increase the productivity of the employees as well as for the firm also. As a result, it can be stated that some other ways can be used by the firm to get success in the business and to develop an effective learning work culture.

Regarding the findings of the correlation, from the table of correlation results it is remarkably found that there is a positive correlation between learning work culture and achieving the goals and objectives of the company. This is due to the help which the implementation of learning work culture's activities and how it helps the employees to learn various things related to the work and the working environment which enhances the employees' performance in the company. Hence, it can be determined that there is a positive relationship between the learning work culture and achieving the goals of the company. However, from the table of the correlation demonstrates how the learning work culture encourages problem-solving through providing activities and learning seminars in order to keep the employees up-to-date with the most recent technological solutions and the recent implemented strategies to be able to adapt with change. This is due to the contribution of the learning work culture in developing the understanding of the employees that help the firm to manage the issues and to overcome the possibilities of the arising issues. The learning work culture also develops the skills of the employees regarding the difference in the culture and it provides for them an understanding of culture values. Due to this, it can be stated that the use of learning work culture is quite helpful for reducing the issues and encourage the employees within the firm to solve the problems related to differentiation of backgrounds and culture in a modern and a respectful manner. In addition, it can also be stated the availability of a positive relationship between the learning work culture and the CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) implementation. The reason

in this is that if the firm implements the learning work culture, then it makes it easier for the firms to complete all the necessary operations of the firm on time and it also assists the firm to make a proper budget for managing other crucial works like CSR. The successful implementation of CSR activities helps the firm to make a brand name in the market. But at the same time, the table of correlation also represents the absence of a positive relationship between the learning work cultures because the correlation value is lower than 1 and it is -.241 that presents the ineffective relationship between the learning work culture and the productivity

Moreover, the Chi-square test and cross-tabulation test demonstrates the presence of a strong association among the existing variables and the existence of a highly significant association among the variables and this provides evidence of the necessity of Learning Work Culture in the firms to provide better management strategy and enhanced productivity of individuals due to the presence of an enhanced work environment. Moreover, From the testing of the hypothesis using Chi-Square and Cross-Tabs, it can be determined that there is a positive relationship between sustainability and the learning work culture. So, Hypothesis H1 is proved.

The following table summarises the outcome and the relationship to research objectives and questions:

Research Objectives & Questions	Outcome
To provide an identification of the factors which improves the implementation of successful learning work culture in the retail organization.	• The employees' engagement as it helps to create a positive engagement of employees towards the changes to apply within the company in order to improve the business environment.

- The financial expenses as development activities might be expensive and it's one of the big factors which affects the company during the implementation of the learning work culture.
- The management practices should be effective in order to create a learning work culture within the company.
- The organizational culture and the climate represent two major factors that has an effect on the learning work culture of the company.
- Low decisions making power of the firm, employees' stress, negative attitude, etc., are the major reasons that make the cause of affecting the learning work culture of the firm.
- The implementation of new and modern technology is a useable and an effective method to reach the desired objectives.
- Customer relation, customer relationship management, ethical marketing, etc., are other factors that can be used by the firm to get success in the market and win a competitive advantage.

<p>To provide an evaluation of the relationship between the workplace performance and the learning work culture in the context of Primark UK.</p>	<p>The researcher and the majority of participants have proved and confirmed that there is a significant and positive relationship between implementing learning work culture strategy within the company and the enhancement of the productivity and performance of employees which leads towards higher profits for the firm.</p>
<p>The significant impact of the learning work culture on retail organizations within the UK.</p>	<p>The implementation of a learning work culture provides a competitive advantage for the company, it enhances the productivity of employees, hence, it increases the profits of the firm and boosts the sales to reach the desired objectives through motivating employees and helping them to adapt with the new implemented strategies within the company and any upcoming change. Therefore, the learning work culture is used as a tool to encourage companies for positive change within their strategy to become more productive and enhance their employees' performance.</p>
<p>The relationship between the learning work culture and the efficiency of the employees at the organization.</p>	<p>There is a significant and positive relationship between the learning work culture and the efficiency of the employees as it improves</p>

	productivity while improving the work and the engagement of the employees.
How can the management of Human Resources improve the learning work culture within retail organizations in the UK?	The learning work culture can be improved within the retail organizations by scheduling activities to develop the personal skills of employees according to the current changes applied to the internal strategy and activities of the company. For instance, these activities can include webinars and trainings for software and modern technology utilization.

Source: (Author, 2021)

The following figure demonstrates the triangulation:

Figure 36: Triangulation Situation

(Source: 'Author's work, July 2020')

5.2. Chapter Summary:

The previous chapter represents the findings of the research where is it remarkably highlighted from the conducted survey and interviews how learning work culture contributes in the workplace sustainability where the proposed theories in this research are supported by academic sources which demonstrates the increase of revenue and performance of companies which implement a learning work culture strategy within the company. Finally, the chapter confirms the availability of a positive relationship between the work culture and the CSR.

Chapter 6- Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

It is a significant chapter that provides the overall view of the thesis in terms of the research outcomes and findings related to the data. This chapter of the research also discusses some recommendations that can be used by further research to conduct the research on the same topic and in an effective manner for producing more valid and effective research outcomes. Along with this, some limitation of this research is also discussed along with the contribution of the research that will help the further researcher to overcome the gap of existing literature on the same topic and to successfully conduct the further thesis.

6.2 Conclusion

On the basis of the findings, it can be analysed in order to sustain in the competitive market, there is a need for the firm to have the learning work culture because it helps to target the customers and to make an effective working environment. In the present working environment, there are lots of changes in terms of change in the technology, change in the customers' need, market scenario, etc., that are occurring and creating the issues for the company. So, to manage all these issues and to create a good business platform, there are different ways, strategies, approaches, etc., that are used by the firms. But at the same time, learning work culture is main and the best manners used by the company according to the presently changing environment. It assists the firm to survive in the industry developing a good base of the customers.

6.2.1 To understand the importance of learning work culture in the retail organization

This research remained highly assistive to offer detailed understanding of the importance of LWC in retail organisations. It has supported to analyse that utilisation of LWC in management remains supportive to increase employee productivity and improve their performance which further leads the retail organisation towards creating competitive advantage and increase the

chances of success. Above study has supported to conclude that implementation of LWC in management allows fostering the learning among employees about the work, colleagues, management and other aspects through introducing different learning and development programs. It also remains highly supportive to manage workforce diversity while creating an effective relationship with employees.

From the research findings of Aasen et al. (2012), it can be concluded that learning work culture is mandatory for the firms for managing the work and the working environment. The reason in this is that there are various advantages for the firm to use the learning work culture. In this, making a strong relationship, boosting productivity, creating motivation, etc., are the major advantages for the firms to use the learning work culture for the firms. At the same time, in the outcomes of the survey through a questionnaire, it is found that there was a positive concern of all respondents regarding the importance of the learning work culture for the firms. Furthermore, from the findings of Chen and Tseng (2012) and Hager and Hodkinson (2009), it can also be concluded that the learning work culture is quite helpful for the firms to achieve the goals and the objectives effectively. The reason in this is that the learning work culture probes the different opportunity for the firm in the business and provides various opportunities for the employees in the firm to get success in their job and to overcome the issues related to the working environment. Therefore, it is evaluated that the learning work culture is quite beneficial for the firm to get success in the industry and to achieve objectives.

In same concern of this, in the findings of Chen and Tseng (2012) and Hager and Hodkinson (2009), it can also be concluded that reducing the risks and issues are the important major works of the learning work culture concerned by the company in the operation. The reason behind this is that following the learning work culture in the firm helps the firm to have the innovation and the technology in the system that helps the firm to improve the service and to

mitigate the challenges and issues related to the work. Due to this, it is determined that it has a significant learning work culture in the success of the firm and to reduce the risks and issues.

In like manner, it can also be concluded with the research findings of Singh (2001) and Thomas and Brown (2011), there is a vital role of the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability in the improvement of employees' morale. It is because different firms are facing the issue due to the low employees' morals and because of this; most of the firms have been losing their customer base as well. So, the learning work culture increases the employees' morals through increasing their knowledge and their understanding regarding their work and then some other aspects of life. It helps the employees to sustain in the competitive market and to enhance their self-morals. Thus, it can be determined that there is a vital role in workplace sustainability and the learning work culture in the success of the firm and to increase the employees' morals.

Along with this, from the consideration of Marsick and Watkins (2015) findings, it can also be concluded that developing the learning work culture is also helpful for the firms to give confidence to the employees and the firms in the problem-solving. The reason for this is that during managing the business at the international level, there are different programs such as cultural diversity programs, employees' motivation programs, etc., that are conducted by the firm. All these programs are directly related to the learning culture because of this it can be stated that learning work culture is quite effective for the firms in the problem-solving process of the firm.

Furthermore, it can also be summarized that the learning work culture is not only helpful for problem-solving, reducing the risks and issues, etc., but at the same time, the learning work culture is also helpful in the CSR activity to survive in the market and to develop a good base of the customers in different countries, there is a need for the firm to use the CSR activities to get the attraction of the local people of that particular country and to develop the brand value

in the market (Marsick and Watkins, 2015; Aasen et al., 2012). So, if there is an issue that the company faces in the CSR implementation, then it will help the firm to get success. Therefore, it is evaluated that the use of learning work culture will be helpful for the firm to have a successful implementation of corporate social responsibility. That is why it can be interpreted that the learning work culture has vital importance for the firms in their success and in the successful management of the business.

Additionally, it can also be concluded that workplace sustainability and the learning work culture are helpful for the firm to make a good public relation and to develop a brand image in the market. It is because there are different issues related to the environment and the products that are faced by the firms and the customers as well. All these create the negative image of the firm in the market and also affect the public relation that becomes a loss of financial situation and the brand image. So, if the firm is doing the sustainability practices and providing the learning work environment for the employees then it will make it easy for the employees to handle all the customer base and to develop a good public relation. So, it can be stated that there is a significant role in the learning work culture and workplace sustainability in the success of the firm.

Furthermore, it can also be concluded that this is not a common task to handle businesses at the global level because many internal issues are found which the firms faced. In addition to this, firms faced another major issue that is the employees' engagement. So, through this research, it can be determined that learning work culture helps the firm to solve these issues and to increase the employees' engagement (Škerlavaj et al., 2010). It is because, in the learning work culture, employees look for the various opportunities for themselves and learn the different new things that assist the employees to sustain for a long time in the firm and to increase their productivity. Additionally, the learning work culture also helps the firm in

developing an enthusiastic view of the employees about the firm that is quite essential to develop an effective business platform and get the success in the market.

From the research of Cohen-Meitar et al. (2009), it can also be concluded that operating the business in different countries is one of the main issues for the organization. The reason in this is that there are different factors such as nature, culture, environment, etc., which influence the operation of the firm in other countries and it creates business issues. Hence, it is concluded that culture can identify the main issue that influences to operate in the market to successfully manage the business in other countries. In like manner, it can also be concluded that in the retail market, UK is one of the best and leading countries that provides various opportunities for the firms in their business and to sustain in the UK market which makes it important to utilise LWC in the UK retail industry. There are different reasons behind this and in this, the liberal policy of the UK government, the high consumption power of the customers is also high that also provides the advantages to manage the business and to effectively handle all the business activities in the UK. At the same moment, Primark is a leading firm in the UK, and it is continuously getting the advantage in the business just because of high consumption level of the customers and the effective rules and regulation of the UK government.

At the same time, it is identified that while dealing in the UK market, it is essential for Primark to have fair work policy and rules in the working environment to deal with the arising the issues and conflict. In this context, the introduction of different culture management programs remains supportive to motivate the employees to deal with unexpected business risks in a better way. Moreover, LWC also helps retail firms to develop global HR policy and to encourage the development of leadership to deal with cultural changes so that a supportive work environment can be designed for effectively dealing with a diverse workforce.

In the support of this and the findings of Evans and Waite (2010), it can also be added that Primark needs to have a focused orientation towards the international market or in the UK. The

market orientation concept is essential with regards to marketing and business management (Kumar et al., 2011). The market orientation gives the customer the prime focus and puts forward the main reason for the company's existence. Hence, the development of market orientation's behaviour is necessary for Primark. Therefore, to sell a product to a global consumer the notion of market orientation can be useful in the UK markets. Due to the increased global economy and more demand from the consumer, the firm can adapt to market orientation behaviour to compete in the market. It can be said that at Primark, market orientation requires a consumer-centred approach for successful product design.

6.2.2 To identify the factors that improve learning work culture in a retail organization

This research focuses on identifying those factors that improve learning work culture in a retail organization. Simultaneously, it also determined that some aspects affect the learning work culture and developing the sustainability issues for the firm. So, in this context, this research has focused on identifying both the factors.

This research has supported to conclude that effective long-term strategies and organizational success help to improve LWC in the retail industry. It allows the firm to design predetermined strategies to provide an action plan to the staff members so that the organizational goal can be achieved in a limited time frame by designing adequate LWC program. Honesty and loyalty of the employees play a vital role in the successful functioning of the organization in a dynamic environment. It helps the firm to create decentralized organizational structure while involving flexibility in terms and conditions so that employees become able to deal with the crucial decision-making process of the company. Honest and loyal employees become able to get indulged with the development of voluntary participation of employees in the managerial framework which helps to increase the success of LWC program and allows improving innovation and creativity in the employees.

In addition to this, it can also be declared that better use of the existing sources is also one of the effective ways that can also be used by the firm for workplace sustainability and to develop a good and effective learning work culture. It is because there are various firms that operate their business at an international level but don't operate effectively due to not using the existing sources effectively. Because of this, there are so many issues that are handled by the firm and this also raises the hurdle in the business management, which is thriving already and to manage the business effectively in the international market. So, it can be concluded that if there is a proper use of the existing resources of the firm, then it can be effective for the firms at international market to develop an effective learning work culture and for the workplace sustainability. Apart from this, it can also be concluded that the implementation of new and modern technology is also one of the best and effective ways for the firms to use at the international level (Trevarthen, 2011). The reason to use these ways is that the use of recent and effective technology provides an advantage for the firms to use the resources effectively, identify the need of the customers as well as for the employees quickly, easy way to manage the different strategies, etc. For sustaining in the competitive environment and the competitive market, the firm must use this type of way. Because of this, it can be stated that the use of existing strategy or the better use of recent technology can be effective for the firms at the international market for developing the learning work culture.

From the above study, it can also be concluded that the workplace sustainability creates a culture where the organizational employees can share the knowledge about the organizational work as well as they can share the organizational resources to improve the productivity and an inquiry for any problem-solutions. In the learning programs, the skills of the employees are also developed for the effective use of the existing organizational resources to more productivity by the use of limited resources. It is identified that most of the organizations can be a success by the use of cost-cutting with profit maximization strategy. The optimal

utilisation of the resources helps the company to effectively operate the business in the international market otherwise the company has to face several challenges. So, it can be said that the company must use existing resources of the company to develop the business at the international level as well as increase the profitability of the company as a comparison of the other competitors. Apart from this, it is also concluded that the organization to focus on the implementation of new and modern technology to get a positive result on success. The most modern and best technology provides a competitive advantage to the company that can develop the business at the international level.

On the other hand, it can also be concluded that there are also some other ways like customer relationship, customer relationship management, ethical marketing, etc., that can also be quite helpful for the firm to develop a learning work culture and for workplace sustainability. In this, it can be summarized that there is an important role of the customer relationship to build the learning work culture. Due to the focus of the firm which is based on the customer relation overcomes the marketing issues for the firm and also increases the production process of the firm with better communication and collaboration. Because of this, in conclusion, it is stated that the customer relationship is one of the best and effective ways to develop the learning work culture.

Furthermore, it can also be summarized that customer relationship management makes it simple for the firm to execute well in the market and to find the competitive advantages that assist the firm in the workplace sustainability and to make a positive view of the customers for the firm (Achtenhagen et al., 2013). This is because; it is easy for the company to develop an efficient learning work culture and to maintain the business in the international area. In addition, it can also be summarized that ethical marketing is also one of the crucial and effective ways that can be useful for the firm and workplace sustainability and the learning work culture. The reason in this is that ethical hacking keeps the company safe from any issues related to the

government and other marketing practices. It directly helps the firm to develop the learning work culture and workplace sustainability.

In addition to this, it is also concluded that the learning culture at the workplace is much helpful for both an organization and employees to improve the performance. An organization can use several techniques to develop the learning work culture for improving the performance of the employees, such as training and development programs, skill development programs, motivational programs, etc. All the provided strategies and programs are helping to provide a sustainable workplace environment to the employees (Carmeli et al., 2010). This sustainable program helps the employee to effectively and easily complete the organizational tasks as well as perform better. Moreover, these strategies of learning work culture are also helpful for an organization by providing well-skilled employees for success at the international level. Well-skilled employees provide innovative ideas to the company so that the firm can survive in the global market effectively.

On the contrary, one of the major important factors is the cost and the issues that are faced by the business to manage and develop the effective learning work culture within the firm. The reason in this is that to develop the learning work culture at international level and to develop an effective business strategy, some different planning and the methods that are used by the firms which raise the issue for the firm to maintain the business and the learning work culture as well as also enhance the cost of the firm as well. The increasing cost of the firm affects the other business operation and creates an ineffective market position and the culture of the firm as well. As a result of this, it can be interpreted that expenditure is one of the major problems that create issues towards the firm concerning the successful management of the learning work culture. In addition, it can also be concluded that some internal business operations can also change by the firm at the time of developing the learning work culture (Scheeres et al., 2010). Additionally, there are also various other activities such as employees' engagement,

employees' motivation, etc., in which firms spend a large amount to effectively manage all these activities in order to develop an effective learning work culture within the firm. So, all the above-mentioned activities create the basis for increasing the firm's cost and affect the other different business activities of the firm along with the learning work culture. That is why, as a result of this, it is concluded that the cost is the major factor that affects the learning work culture's nature of the firm.

In addition to this, it can be concluded that the different rules and the regulations implanted by the different country's government also represents the major issue for the firms in the successful implementation of the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. It is because different rules of the government increase the work pressure on the firm and the employees as well that creates the issue for the employees to be engaged in the other activities. Because of this, it can be stated that following the various rules and the regulations made by the government is one of the major issues in the learning work culture of the firms (Joo, 2010). Furthermore, it can also be concluded that management practices are also the key problems that make the issues for the firm to successfully implement or develop the learning work culture within the firm. The reason in this is that in order to develop the learning work culture, there is a need for the firm to develop the effective and useful management practices in terms of providing the training for the employees, implementing new rules and regulations, consideration of ethical issues, performance management, etc. All these practices raise the firm's cost and also create the issue for the firm at the internal level. So, it can be concluded that due to creating the issues at the internal level and related to the cost, management practices are the major factors for the firm in the successful development of the learning work culture. At the same time, it can also be concluded that some other factors such as employees' engagement, cost, etc., are interconnected with each other and all these are considered in the management practices. So, if any aspect as discussed above create the issue for the firm, then

it directly affects the learning work culture of the firm. That is why the management practices are considered as a big issue for the firms in the development of the effective learning work culture.

Besides from this, from the overall discussion, it can also be concluded that increasing level of the competition creates the issue for the firms in the successful implementation of the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. It is because most of the firms are looking to get a competitive advantage and to perform better for increasing the customer base. That is why firms do not have the time to give the focus on the learning work culture and workplace sustainability and due to this, it is one of the major issues.

In addition to this, it can also be concluded that organizational culture and climate are also the major factors that also affect the development of the learning work culture and the working condition of the firm as well. Moreover, it can also be concluded that organizational culture and climate are also the major problems that also bother the firm at the time of developing the learning work culture within the firm. The reason in this is that at the international level, people are different on the basis of demographic, geographic, etc., as well as it is also different in the language and the communication style of the people. It creates the issue for the firms to effectively implement the learning work culture in the firm and to have collaboration among the employees. As a result of this, it can be concluded that organizational culture and climate change are the major factors that affect the learning work culture in the firm.

6.2.3 To evaluate the relationship between the workplace permanence & learning work culture in the context of Primark UK

In this context, this research has supported to conclude that Primark utilises different policies to develop LWC within the organisation. There are different ways used by the management team of Primark to make LWC effective which is assisting the brand to provide better learning opportunities to the workers. Focus towards this aspect is supporting to increase the effectiveness of the

business too. However, the firm is also facing some issues while developing learning work culture for the management such as cost, competition among employees, changes in organizational culture and climate, etc. but the benefits of LWC is higher than these issues. Due to this reason, LWC is playing a very important role in the success of Primark. LWC is assisting Primark to provide an opportunity for the employees to grow and to make a bright future. It is helping to increase employee satisfaction and development of employee morale and performance which is enhancing the chances of employee sustainability within the organisation. It is also assisting to increase employee engagement which is supporting to improve employee performance and productivity. From this, it can be concluded that there is a strong relationship between the workplace permanence & learning work culture in the context of Primark UK.

However, as Primark deals at a global platform so various factors are needed to be considered to make this relationship effective. In this context, it can be stated that at the international level, there are also lots of differences in the tradition of the people that also affect the business and the market activities of the people. So that, in order to manage this issue along with effective improvement in the global market, the business and marketing strategy of the firm like Primark needs an overall change that also creates the purpose of the firm to develop the learning work culture. That is why climate change and culture are considered as big factors that affect the development of the learning work culture. Furthermore, it can also be concluded that change in technology is one of the key issues which creates problems for the firm to successfully develop the learning work culture. Reason in this is that there is a continuous change in the technology and for sustaining in the competitive marketplace and to build up a good client foundation (Joo and Shim, 2010). But the technological change creates issues for the employees to adopt the changes and to perform well.

It is because these changes create the issues related to the employees' engagement and the motivations as well as some time to make the cause of conflict and the dispute among the employees. Because of this, technological changes are considered as a big factor that affects

the learning work culture of the firm. At the same time, it can also be concluded that due to changes in technology, the firm also faces the issues related to the cost and the time. It is due to the continuous changes in technology, the firm has to spend lots of money that creates an issue for the firm in its financial condition. Because of this, technological change is one of the major hurdles that create an issue for the firm in the development of the learning work culture. Sometimes, lack of knowledge, lack of motivation, lack of leadership, etc., are also the major reasons that also impact the learning work culture of the firm and raise the issue in the successful business management at the international market (Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle 2011).

In like manner, it can also be declared that although there are various aspects such as climate change, organizational culture, technological change, etc., that affect the learning work culture, at the same time, the growing level of the competition is also one of the key issues or the hurdle that also raises the issue for the firm in context to the successful implementation of the learning work culture. It is because the need of the customers and the consumption of level of the customers are continuously increasing due to this; the firm is focusing on the product development and getting the competitive advantages rather than developing the learning work culture. If due to the increasing level of the competition, firms focus on the learning work culture then it will take time for the firm and will also impact the other working activities of the firm as well. As a result of this, it can be concluded that growing levels of the competition is also one of the major problems that affect the development of learning work culture (Aasen et al., 2012). In the same concern of this, it can also be concluded that there are also some other factors such as decisions making power of the firm, employees' stress, negative attitude, etc., are the major reason that also creates the issue for the firm to develop the learning work culture. It is because these are the major ways that assist the firm to increase the productivity of the

employees and to perform better as well. Because of this, it can be described that there are different ways that affect the learning work culture of the firm at an international level.

In addition, it can also be declared that there are also many ways that can also be used by the firms at the international level to manage the issue in the development of the learning work culture and to reach workplace sustainability. Furthermore, formulating the best strategy is also one of the ways that can be used by the firms for the successful development of the learning work culture and for workplace sustainability. Because the use of the best strategy, it is possible to assist the firm to get the advantage of the competition in the market and to develop a strong brand impression in customers' mind at the international market. Because of this, it is an effective way for the firms to develop an effective learning work culture and to reach workplace sustainability.

Furthermore, it can also be concluded that the learning work culture is essential to solve the different problems in the workplace environment. It is identified that there are several problems arising in the workplace that cannot be solved by the organizational employees without skilled employees. The skilled employees help other employees in the learning work culture to solve their problems. In this, the skilled employees provide technical skills as well as operational skills to the different unskilled employees. In addition to this, it can also be concluded that the technical solutions of the problems develop better job relations between the employees and help them to make effective decisions regarding the job and tasks. The ability of the employees can also be increased by presenting workplace sustainability. The enhanced ability of the individual is helpful for them to easily adapt the technical changes and provide a maximum output of the provided tasks (Wiernik et al., 2013).

At the same time, it can also be concluded that managing and developing people is also one of the ways to use for the firm to manage the learning work culture and for workplace sustainability. There are various ways and the strategies that are used by the firms at

international level for managing the people and the culture because it helps the firm to have the effective communication platform in the firm and also help to develop an effective learning work culture as well as workplace sustainability. But in like manner, it can also be summarized that instead of managing and developing the people, there are also various techniques including honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc., that can also be used by the firm for managing the workplace sustainability and to develop the learning work culture. It is because honesty makes the positive image of the employees in the firm that makes easy the firm to develop a learning work culture and workplace sustainability.

It also helps to overcome the dispute and the conflict within the firm and also help the firm to successfully implement any of the marketing and business strategies effectively. Because of this, it can be determined that the honesty in the employees helps the firm to develop an effective learning work culture.

In addition, accountability is also one of the key solutions that also help the firm to develop workplace sustainability and the learning work culture (Sachien, 2010). The reason in this is that accountability helps the firm to handle the different problems related to the culture difference and others and makes it easier for the firm in the successful management of the business. Due to this concern, it can be finalized that accountability is one of the keyways that assist the firm in the successful running of the workplace sustainability and to develop a learning work culture.

6.3 Recommendation

6.3.1 Effective Learning Work Culture

From this research study, it can be recommended that there are different things that should be considered by the managers of Primark for better performance in the international market and to develop an effective learning work culture. In this, it can be recommended that this is a requirement for the firm to use effective and the best marketing and business strategy according

to the existing market and the need of the customers (McGain et al., 2012). The reason in this is that it will be supportive of the firm to sustain in the market for a long period and to get the success. The international marketplace offers a good platform to incorporate international business and marketing strategies to Primark to improve its performance and international market competitiveness.

6.3.2 Better Use of the Marketing Strategy

The organisation should consider international marketing strategies distinct from their domestic market strategy which includes considering the organisational factors as well as external environmental factors (Sheth, 2011). Also, the business strategy needs to take into account the organisation's performance from the perspective of integration and resource sharing. This would also require the organisation to remain responsive to business strategy and flexible with regards to technologies, product and service design, sourcing, regulation in the international market, price changes and exchange rate (Terpstra et al., 2012). Thus, Primark can follow either a low-cost strategy or can engage in activities that develop a higher buyer value to allow the company to ask for premium prices of their products by differentiating themselves from the competitors in the international marketplace. As Primark in the international market needs to be focused on both product and market. It needs to label itself as product-focused to emphasise on the quality of its products and to use improvement to expand its name into the new market segments in the UK. Primark needs to make sure that their products are different and have a competitive edge over all the other related products in the marketplace. The products need to be rich in features and ground breaking (Ingenhoff and Fuhrer, 2010). The company needs to design products with attractive features which capture the market. Primark should utilize the capacity and innovativeness of the global team to create products that are unique and provide a competitive edge in the international market.

6.3.3 Focus on to Produce the Eco-Friendly

As well as, there is also a call for the firm to keep a proper focus on to produce the eco-friendly products because it is becoming a positive concern of the people towards the use of eco-friendly products and the environment also. It will help to get a reasonable benefit and to develop a good client base for the firm. The firm should also use the eco-friendly products in the production process because it will make it easy for the firm to make a positive view of the people towards the products and the firm (Blok et al., 2015). Thus, Primark is recommended to keep a continued follow for green business practices by the use of eco-friendly products in their production process to get benefits for the company and to create an impression of the socially responsible company. This is also advantageous in terms of brand perception in the international market and to gain a positive public response from the foreign market (De Mooij, 2013). This can be helpful for the company to get emission allowance and gain resources to reduce waste and emission and operate in compliance with the international standards. This will also increase the chances of getting any tax incentive for the use of eco-friendly practices (Han et al., 2011). It will reduce the cost of any legal obligations arising out of fines and penalties owing to breach of environmental laws and regulations. The use of eco-friendly practices will also promote the organisation to work as a healthier place to work in the international marketplace (Han et al., 2011). This is an effective step that is suggested to the organisation for its growth, development, and sustainability of its business in the international markets. This will altogether enhance the performance of Primark.

6.3.4 Effective management of the global workforce

It can also be concluded that there is also a need for the firm to use different ways to manage the people and the employees of the firm for better performance and for workplace sustainability. It is because due to operating the business at the international level, there are different issues related to working pressure, change in the culture, etc., that are the issues which

are also faced by the employees and concern the firm as well. This helps in creating effective management of global workforce with a robust global HR strategy in order to get success in the international platform (Farndale et al., 2010).

It is also required by the company to respect the local culture and differences, by focusing on motivation and keeping consideration of labour laws and anti-discrimination policies in hiring the employees across the international markets (Ferraro and Briody, 2017). This suggests the company should develop a global HR policy and to encourage the development of leadership to deal with cultural changes and provide a supportive workplace environment for management of the diverse workforce. It can be added that to build a competent team across the borders the company can address the cultural difference and create a shared understanding among the team members.

Thus, the company can develop a training solution for the multi-cultural teams and build leadership capabilities in potential employees to drive the solution (Ferraro and Briody, 2017). Apart from this, the development of innovative culture can help the company in achieving workplace sustainability (Coccia, 2015). This will be useful for Primark in meeting the environmental obligations and driving the societal dimension in the international markets. So, by using some changes or by using the ways to manage the people and the employees can be the best options for the firm to operate the business at the international market.

Likewise, it can also be recommended that there is also a need for the firm as well as for the managers to develop the honesty, integrity, trustworthiness; accountability, etc., is the major ways that should be developed by the firm in the employees (Ones and Dilchert, 2012). The reason in this is that it will help the firm and the employees perform better and to handle the entire operation of the firm as well. Because of this, it is recommended that developing these skills such as trustworthiness; accountability, etc., will be the better operation for the managers to perform better and to develop a learning work culture. It will also be helpful for the firm in

its workplace sustainability and will also increase the performance of the firm as well. Because of this, these ways are recommended for the managers of the firms to do better performance in the market and to grasp the market opportunities.

Furthermore, in the context of this, it is also recommended that Primark also need to focus on using the resources effectively because it is one of the best options that can give the success for the firm in the minimum time and the workplace sustainability (Clarke, 2011). The reason in this is that the better use of existing resources also overcomes the extra cost of the firm and makes effective operations and marketing departments of the firm. The organisation is required to make effective use of resources. Therefore, it is required to take caution in developing the marketing mix and it needs to identify the factors in the new market that favour the buying decisions of the customers in the global marketplace.

Effective management of resources would be useful for Primark in the deployment of the company resources in an efficient manner of the finances, inventory, information resources, talent management and resources for production (Jormanainen and Kovesnikov, 2012). It can be said that to decide what consumer sights as an immediate requirement, most important concerns or personal choices in the global marketplace is difficult to know (De-Mooij, 2013). This, in turn, allows the firm to focus on developing the product funds on the features that are most in-demand, in the hope of satisfying consumer requirements through their manufactured goods. Primark needs to focus on providing services and support to the consumers for the fulfilment of their needs and requirements. This makes certain consumer satisfaction remains elevated with the firm as a whole and can help to endorse brand loyalty and encouraging word-of-mouth publicity. Thus, resource management would be useful for the company in accomplishing the goals of the company in the marketplace.

Because of this it can be concluded or declared that the use of existing resources will be quite favourable for the firm in the business process and workplace sustainability. At the same point

in time, it is also concluded that there is also a requirement for the firm to give its major focus on the adoption of the use of new and effective technology. It is because the use of new and effective technology can be effective for the firm to produce new and innovative products for the customers and to identify the consumer demands easily and effectively (Kassens-Noor, 2012). It will also be helpful for the firm to be a competitive leader in the market and to create a good client base as well. Because of this, it can be interpreted that the use of the latest, best-in-class technologies can be a great way for the firm to stay stable in the competitive market and to create a good base of the customers.

In addition, it can also be recommended in the concern of Primark that there is also a requirement for the firm to have its proper focus on PR relations. It is because in context to survive in the marketplace and to enhance the customer base, it is crucial for the firm to make effective relations with the customers (Brynjarsdottir et al., 2012). It increases the workplace sustainability of the firm as well as it helps to develop an effective learning work culture. Some other aspects are also considered for the firms such as ethical marketing, fair company rules, and regulation, etc., that can also be helpful for the firm to get success and in the workplace sustainability. Along with this, there is also a need for the firm to follow all required rules and the regulation of the government over and above to make their business and marketing strategy according to the existing law and regulation. It is because it will help the firm to overcome some external issues such as political, economic, social, etc., it will also boost the business and will also make a positive view of the firm in the customer's mind (Hanson, 2010). Because of this, it can be interpreted that following the social aspects and the existing government rules and the regulations will be helpful for the firm to enhance the business management and to perform better in the international market.

6.4 Contribution to the Field

This study has demonstrated the crucial role of learning work culture in enhancing the sustainability of companies and helping them get a competitive advantage and a better productivity to achieve the desired objectives. In addition, this study will contribute for further research in order to analyse and assess in-depth the research topic which is the necessity of implementing a learning work culture within organizations in the aim of reaching long-term sustainability and success. Moreover, it will provide an overview for future research in order to overcome the current gaps found and to develop new and effective research on the same topic. Meanwhile, it is academically demonstrated that this research will be helpful to get a clear understanding about the international business. Additionally, this research will also be beneficial for me to clear my concept and the ideas about the importance of the learning work culture and workplace sustainability in the organizations through establishing competitive advantage in the current market and creating a good customer base at global markets.

There are numerous factors which affects the implementation of a learning work culture successfully within the company and they should be assessed by the management in order to avoid obstacles that leads towards failure of the suggested strategy by the firm i.e. Primark.

Furthermore, this study provides a clear demonstration and explanation regarding the factors which will create issues and obstacles for the companies during the development of a learning work culture which will lead towards failure of reaching workplace sustainability. Moreover, it remarkably helps understanding the strategies and the planning for the firm which can be adopted by the firm in order to enhance the working environment and successfully run and manage the business operations at an international and national level. However, from a market point of view, this research will contribute in helping companies to understand the importance of the implementation of a learning work culture and how it will help them achieve a workplace sustainability.

This study has demonstrated a full understanding of various challenges and factors which will affect the implementation of a learning work culture within companies and how it will affect the management of international operations of the business. In order to overcome these issues, the company should implement a development of a learning work culture strategy in the aim of reaching workplace sustainability. Moreover, this research will be useful for the different firms related to the Fashion industry to get an enhance view about the use of different methods such as formulating the best strategy, managing and developing the people, better use of the existing resources, etc., that can be used by the firm to develop the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability. This research also clarifies the issues for different firms which are related to the development of learning work culture in expanding to international markets. The identification of these issues will also be helpful for the firm to successfully manage the business and for developing an effective customer base.

The research is successful in achieving the aim of the study by concluding that bringing a learning work culture in the organisations would help in achieving efficiency in every operation of Primark. Apart from that, the study has also fulfilled its research objectives by establishing the relationship between learning work culture and organisational sustainability. In addition, the research also highlighted the importance of learning work culture as well as factors proving a competitive advantage in the retail industry as the utilisation of both primary as well as secondary data collection method has supported to improve the data findings. Simultaneously, utilisation of the interview method and survey questionnaire method has supported to offer the contribution of the participants who are actually experiencing the significance of the learning work culture in their life. The research findings of this study can be utilised further for managerial implications not only by the retail industry but also by the companies that are dealing in other industries in the UK. Moreover, this research finding can be used by the firms to develop better opportunity for their business towards creating long-term sustainability.

Furthermore, the utilisation of different figures and conceptual frameworks has supported to provide a conceptual contribution in this study that remained highly assistive to understand the research process in a better way. It has also supported to communicate the fundamental principles of developing a learning work culture and basic functionality of the research system so that study can be easily understood.

6.5 Limitations of the Study

This research has certain limitations which might affect the certainty of the outcome and the usage of the findings in further studies. The reason of this conclusion is that Primark is a British company which is available in 392 locations around UK and Europe; and this research focuses only on Primark Liverpool where a certain number of employees and managers were questioned in order to identify the validity of the proposed findings and to answer the questions of the research. In addition, the number of respondents to the interviews and surveys was very limited due to the availability of the staff working in the company as the researcher tried to approach the largest number of employees and managers who agreed to contribute in this research by providing their opinion regarding the learning work culture and how it will enhance the productivity of the company and its effect on the workplace sustainability. Moreover, the research was conducted within one year which proposes a time limitation as it's not enough to analyse the issue in real depths and find out about the validity of the hypothesis within a short period of time especially that Primark is a local and global leading retail company within the retail industry. Furthermore, the size of the sample has also been kept limited to managing time and other research related resources effectively. However, the researcher has made all attempts for reducing the impact of these limitations to a minimum level. In addition, the research could benefit from future development regarding the location of interviews and conduction of surveys; this attempt of development will be beneficial but time consuming as the company has an international existence and the culture of the workplace varies according to the location

of the company and the ethnicity of the employees. The strategy of learning work culture to be proposed for retail companies should be based on in-depth research as the current research demonstrated the necessity of an implementation of a positive learning work culture, and different methods that helps increase the productivity of the workplace and the employees, and the various factors which affects this implementation. Moreover, further research could be done which will benefit of long-time research, and larger number of interviewees and employees to questions regarding their opinion on the matter which will provide better detailed results of the validity of the hypothesis suggested that states the significant importance of the learning work culture implementation.

6.6 Managerial Implications of the Research

The research is very useful for managers for implementing ways for making their organisation a learning one. The research also highlights the importance of learning organisations which would help managers in making their decisions in favour of creating a learning culture within the organisation. In this age of competition and rapidly changing market conditions learning culture is the key in the hands of management to have an edge over other competitors and to grow the business to new avenues.

6.7 Future Research

The research has covered the topic of learning culture in the organisation in detail. It has provided various advantages associated with such a culture in the organisation. However, the focus of the study was the retail sector and this situation further research could be performed in other industries. Also, in future, a study related to problems in implementing learning culture could be undertaken for providing more practical exposure to the implementation of such culture and issues faced by employees.

6.8 Achievement of The Aim and The Objectives

From the overall findings, it can be determined that this research is successful because of providing valid and effective outcomes from the result. In addition, the survey that is conducted by the researcher was effective and helpful for the researcher because all respondents participate effectively and helped the researcher to achieve the aim of the research. The findings of the research were effective and as the topic of this research is “to define the significance of learning work culture in the UK’s retail industry for long term business sustainability” in the context of PRIMARK. So, this topic is successfully researched and for this, different issues are identified that can create the issue for the firm (PRIMARK UK) in the successful management of the learning work culture. As well as, along with the importance of the learning work culture, the ways were also defined that can be helpful for the firm to improve the learning work culture and all the issues in the learning work culture. So, it can be stated that the research study under consideration was successfully completed and produced the valid outcomes of the research.

6.9 Chapter Summary

The previous chapter provides an overall view of the thesis where it highlights the research outcomes and findings related to the data. In addition, it represents a conclusion of the research where it clarifies how the research objectives are reach and how this research contributed in providing an understanding of the importance of learning work culture in the retail organization, an identification of factors which improves the learning work culture in retail organization, and an evaluation of the relationship between the workplace permanence and learning work culture in Primark UK. Moreover, this chapter provides recommendations regarding the implementation of an effective learning work culture within firms who are keen to increase their revenue and enhance their performance, and to use a better marketing strategy to increase the brand awareness and attract more customers. In addition to recommendations for the company to apply an effective management of the global workforce, and to enhance the

contribution to the field. These evaluations and recommendations are supported by academic resources where numerous researchers handled the same proposed issues in different manners. Finally, the previous chapter has introduced the limitations of the study, the managerial implications of the research, and how the future research could be improved to provide a better understanding of the proposed issues and theories. Moreover, this chapter has determined the success of the conducted research and how it successfully completed and reached the objectives of the research.

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Appendices

Interview

In this research, interview is also conducted that helped the researcher to get the detailed information about the research questions. It also helped the researcher to ask the detail questions from the respondents. With the help of interview, it was easy for the researcher to know the personal views and the opinion of the respondents for the better result of the research. Interview is quite time consuming that is why researcher targeted the only 6 managers and the 4 employees of the firm. It was enough for the researcher to complete the research on time and to get the desired outcomes.

Appendix 1: Interview Questions

Management team:

Manager 1:

1- How many members are in management team?

We are 7 members in the management team.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

In order to develop an enhanced learning work culture, I am entitled to follow a number of various policies such as training & development policy which will boost the employees' levels of skills to be as desired by the business, the employee development policy which contributes to increasing the satisfaction of the current employees & their motivation to give their best for the company, and corporate training programs which enhances the efficiency and the morals of the employees, and it also reduces their weaknesses.

3- What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?

In order to develop the management of the business, the management department invest more in evaluating the learning levels of the employees; it also provides better learning opportunities for the workers to increase their effectiveness within the business. Moreover, it handles an effective learning experience within the company by providing training & development plans accompanied with timely feedback.

4- Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?

Yes, I believe that developing a learning work culture within the business can possibly create managerial issues. These issues include effecting the costs of the business which will increase due to the trainings provided for the employees, the management practices which might be affected by the learning opportunities to be given at the work place, it also increases the level of competition among employees & it changes the organizational culture and climate.

5- Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.

Yes, the learning work culture has a remarkable role in the success of the firm as it is a core tool which leads towards enhanced performance and it helps in achieving the goals & objectives of the firm. Furthermore, it helps reduce the risks and issues which might face the management of the business by increasing the productivity of the employees & by the aid it provides to engage a successful implementation of CSR within the firm.

Manager 2:

1- How many members are in management team?

The management team in this branch holds 5 members.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

Absolutely, I am required to follow many policies regarding the development of learning work culture including trainings & development of employees to enhance their skills and abilities to meet the needs of the business in the aim of increasing the performance of the employees which leads towards higher profits.

3- *What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?*

As a manager, I am entitled to evaluate and assess the productivity of the employees along with their performance. According to the results of this evaluation, I schedule trainings & development opportunities for the workers in order to improve their weaknesses & why not eliminate them completely. Moreover, I am also responsible on ensuring a core focus of company's culture to provide a better understanding of the goals to be achieved by the employees.

4- *Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?*

Yes. Unfortunately creating a learning work culture might create issues for the managers & the management department. As this step will lead towards high competitiveness between employees & which might affect their attitude & the management practices. The trainings to be provided for the employees will also cost the business which might cause financial difficulties in the future.

5- *Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.*

Yes, the learning work culture is an essential element which contributes to the success of the business. As it will give the company an opportunity to explain better its goals & planned achievement for the employees. Along with providing a positive working environment which enhances the employees' skills & motivation to give-out their best

for the success of the firm. Hence, in order to achieve a positive learning work culture in the work-place, as a manager, I am supposed to encourage teamwork & raise the morals of the employees which will increase their productivity and reduce the stress.

Manager 3:

1- How many members are in management team?

In this particular branch, we are 8 managers.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

As a manager, I must follow certain policies which enhance the learning work culture development such as providing the required training for new and existing employees in order to enhance their skills to the next level, to meet the needs of the business; these trainings include the customer service, the morals of the employees & a better understanding of the business' goals in the aim of a increasing the performance of the employees.

3- What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?

The company aims to enhance the learning work culture as it has an immense value to bring for the business. The management department organises events & trainings for the development of the employees' skills. These trainings doesn't just bring value for the business but the employees as well; once they feel the value the business has for them, they start doing their best to impress the managers & the directors which will increase the productivity of the employees & it will enhance the performance & the profit of the business.

4- Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?

No, I do not think that creating a learning work culture will cause any problems for the management department. As a manager, I think that the competitiveness which the learning work culture brings among employees has a positive effect as it will increase their productivity & it can be taken as an advantage to enhance the performance of the business. Moreover, the trainings to be provided for the employees might cost a bit but it can be caught up from the profit to be made after those employees enhance their skills & bring up more profits for the business.

5- Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.

Yes, I strongly agree that the learning work culture influences the success of the firm. A positive workplace won't only record high profits but it will build up a strong competitiveness over its employment & it retains & binds individuals to the company. For instance, no matter how good the salary is, no one would choose to work in a toxic environment where he'll be bullied. Therefore, the work culture also provides an understanding of the employees' value which pushes them towards doubling their efforts to proof themselves & their capabilities.

Manager 4:

1- How many members are in management team?

Currently, the firm holds a number of 4 managers.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

Yes, among the policies which I am required to follow in the aim of developing a learning work culture is the trainings & self-development which should be provided for

employees to enhance their skills & to close all the gaps which might be available in the work they deliver. Moreover, these trainings programs don't just benefit the workplace but the employees as well.

3- *What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?*

In order to develop a learning work culture, the management department which I take part of organises programs to give the employees the desired learning opportunities in the aim of increasing their performance & productivity which will benefit both the workers who'll feel more valuable & the company which will reach its goals in a faster pace. These learning programs will be selected according to the assessments engaged by the managers in the aim of identifying the weaknesses of the employees; these programmes are created to eliminate those weaknesses.

4- *Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?*

Yes, creating a learning work culture might create a variety of managerial issues such as the increase of competitiveness within the company; it also effects the costs of the company as it will invest in the employees' development & their training programmes. Furthermore, creating a learning work culture might have an effect over the company's organisation & climate.

5- *Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.*

I strongly believe that the learning work culture plays a core role in leading the firm towards success and achieving its goals in a fast pace. The learning work culture provides the employees with strong confidence because it eliminates their weaknesses

& allows them to improve their available skills to meet the requirements of their position in the company. It also provides a positive environment which will boost the employees' performance & it will increase their productivity along with increasing their motivation to deliver their best for the business.

Manager 5:

1- How many members are in management team?

The number of managers which the firm currently holds is 6.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

In order to develop the company's learning work culture, as a manager, I follow certain policies including the training & development policy which focuses on enhancing the skills of the employees in the aim of eliminating their weaknesses, the employee development policy that delivers the desired learning opportunities for workers which increases their satisfaction & hence they get motivated and give out their best for the company, and finally the corporate training programmes which have an efficient effect in reducing the weaknesses of the employees by filling the existing gaps in their performance.

3- What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?

My management department focuses on evaluating the performance of the employees, this evaluation will lead towards assessing their weaknesses & their skill levels. Afterwards, training programmes will be developed according to this assessment and evaluation in the aim of enhancing the employees' performance & to increase their productivity. These training programmes include the professional training, coaching &

mentoring in order to improve the management within the company, personal development for employees to enhance their abilities to the next level & the development of soft skills.

4- Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?

Yes, developing a learning work culture creates multiple problems for the managers of the businesses because it increases the competitiveness among employees where each person has the desire to be the most employable & the one employee to get most of the rewards. Moreover, it can cost the business to organize & provide the desired trainings & learning opportunities for the employees.

5- Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.

Yes, I totally agree that learning work culture is a core item which leads towards a success for the business. The learning work culture improves the morals of employees & it motivates them to be engaged in many tasks within the business, showing them value improves their performance & productivity. Moreover, it encourages the employees to strive to learn & develop new skills to perform better & to adapt better to the changes if any are applied in the organisation.

Manager 6:

1- How many members are in management team?

There are exactly 6 managers in this branch, including myself.

2- Do you follow any policies regarding the development of learning work culture?

No, we do not follow any policies to develop a learning work culture within the business. During the hiring process we carefully select the candidates who have enough

experience to be able to deliver the required performance during their job. Hence, the availability of the experienced staff will eliminate the need of training the amateurs who cannot deal with some issues & cannot find efficient solutions for the business.

3- *What are the ways that are used by your management department for developing a learning work culture?*

Currently, the business doesn't invest in developing a learning work culture.

4- *Do you think that developing a learning work culture create an issue for the management?*

Investing in developing a learning work culture costs a lot for the company as it has to evaluate the performance of the employees individually & it has to organize events & training programmes in the aim of enhancing their existing skills & to help them enhance their knowledge about the field as well. It also causes lots of stress for the managers due to the competitiveness it creates among employees.

5- *Do you consider that in the success of your firm, the learning work culture play a very important role? Justify your answer.*

I believe that the company can succeed even without implementing a learning work culture. The only thing it needs to replace it is to wisely select its employees according to the goals assigned to achieve & to the skills as well as the experience of the candidates applying for the jobs. Moreover, once the employee stays long enough in the business automatically increases his experience & manners of dealing with issues & finding effective solutions.

Employees:

Employee 1:**1- What is your position in this firm?**

I am Sales assistant.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I have been working in Primark from last 2 years.

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

I strongly believe that acquiring work culture enhances my performance as a sales assistant & it increases my opportunity of being more productive. Being part of training & learning opportunities enhances my skills & abilities which benefits me as a person first & it benefits the company as well. Moreover, the learning work culture increases the self-confidence in workers which motivates them to give their best for their jobs.

4- Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?

Yes, I believe that learning work culture affects my motivation and hence it effects my work & my engagement in the workplace. Furthermore, the learning work culture takes my skills to the next level where it focuses on eliminating all my weaknesses which increases my self-confidence as well, and this itself makes me more comfortable at work & it helps me engage better with any issues; it also enhances my capability of taking decisions.

5- Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?

I trust that developing a learning work culture in companies benefits the employees as much as it benefits the firm itself. For instance, the training programs giving at the

company aims towards filling the gaps which the employees have in terms of skills & knowledge. Moreover, it makes them more confident & helps them gain more experience which leads towards growing a bright future & a remarkable career progress.

Employee 2:

1- What is your position in this firm?

I am an accountant.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I am working from last 4 years

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

During my work in Primark, there has been lots of learning work culture events & programs. And from my experience within the company, these programs have significantly contributed in increasing my productivity & enhance my performance as well. Hence, it made me a core member within the company which was an immense aid for me to sustain in this company & get promoted to better position.

4- Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?

Yes, learning work culture has already affected my performance at work & how I engage with other employees. As an accountant, developing a learning work culture has increased my confidence & helped me lead better, guide better & perform better. As the programs provided by the company in terms of enhancing the work culture makes the employees more aware of their weaknesses in the aim of eliminating them, it helped me reduce my weaknesses & it increased my performance & productivity.

5- Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?

Yes, I believe that building a work culture helps the employees & the firm as well. As an accountant, the learning work culture is an opportunity of organized trainings & programmes which will enhance my skills & it will give me more knowledge & experience to be capable of delivering better performance & to take better decisions. It also enriches my CV to shape a better career in the future.

Employee 3:

1- What is your position in this firm?

I am Advertising content writer.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I am working from last 5 years.

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

I believe that learning work culture builds a strong culture for the firm which helps us, the employees, to have a better understanding of the goals of the company. This understanding leads towards a better understanding of how to reach this goals & in some cases it makes the employees create the most suitable plans for the business to enhance its profits & to increase its productivity. Hence, I strongly believe that a learning work culture helps me sustain in the company because it teaches me how to engage better & it enhances my connection to the company's goals.

4- Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?

I personally think that learning work culture which is developed in the aim of enhancing the firms' productivity & profit will also aim towards increasing the engagement of the employees at work. Developing a learning work culture makes us feel empowered,

involved & valued, which enhances our motivation & makes us engage with the business to see higher profits due to our skills & motivation & innovative solutions.

5- Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?

I believe that a learning work culture is related to my behaviour at work & it teaches me the most suitable manners & reactions when in crisis or when at ease. As an advertising manager, the advertisement market is full of challenges due to the consecutive & fast evolution of technological ways to attract customers & increase the number of sales in a short period of time; therefore, the learning work culture which I gain from Primark increases my understanding of the company's mission & it motivates me to find appropriate solutions & better plans to reach our target within the required time period. Hence, it increases my experience which will benefit me in my future career plans & personal goals.

Employee 4:

1- What is your position in this firm?

I am Digital Marketer.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I am working from last 3 years

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

As a Digital marketer I believe that learning is a core aspect within company's culture as it supports the innovative ideas & plans which will lead towards better progress. In addition, the learning work culture has enhanced the market adaptation strategies suggested by myself. This is due to the organized trainings & learning opportunity

which are necessary for success in this era of innovations & technological race; especially in marketing where our engagement as employees is necessary to promote for the products of the company & to increase the number of customers. Reaching these two points will absolutely help me sustain in the firm, which is due to the help of the learning work culture.

4- *Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?*

Yes, I believe that the learning work culture has an immense impact on my work & how I engage with my tasks and the other employees. As a Digital marketer, learning work culture has taught me the benefits of enhancing the satisfaction of the employees which will make them loyal as well. For instance, remembering our birthdays & showing how much we are appreciated in the company leads towards big rewards & higher profits. Moreover, the learning work culture makes me feel more appreciated which increases my engagement in the work & it motivates me to find more solutions for the company & help it achieve its assigned goals.

5- *Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?*

I personally think that learning work culture provides the required self-development trainings & lessons which enhances the personal skills of employees & eliminates their weaknesses completely. Therefore, it does provide me the opportunity to go further with my career because it gives both, experience & knowledge.

Employee 5:

1- What is your position in this firm?

I am manufacture technician.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I am working from last 7 years

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

As I am a manufacture technician, it is required for me to keep up with the advanced technologies which helps the firm reduce the costs of production & increase the costs of the sales. This is due to the high-quality products which we are supposed to provide as a company; therefore, the learning work culture represents an aid for me to sustain in the company as it provides the opportunity to stay up to date with the knowledge to guarantee an excellent manufacture process which leads towards the goals assigned by the company.

4- Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?

The learning work culture effects my work in a way & my engagement in it in another. As a manufacture technician, it is my responsibility to make sure all the equipment is up to date & its maintenance is accepted to avoid any tragedies due to undesired accidents. The learning work culture helps me understand the machinery to be used in the company & to personally engage with the other employees in this department to guarantee their standards to be high & to make sure their safe.

5- Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?

Yes, building a strong work culture within an organization helps its employees to grow & get further with their career. As it will provide them with the experience & knowledge to be capable of solving many field-related issues & to give-out their best to avoid

disappointing the company. Moreover, the work culture provides an opportunity for employees to create a bright future due to the confidence they gain during the trainings & the learning sessions provided by the company.

Employee 6:

1- What is your position in this firm?

I am fashion designer.

2- From how many years you are working here?

I am working from last 6 years

3- Do you think that learning work culture helps you to sustain in this firm?

Absolutely not. Building a learning work culture has nothing to do with sustaining in the company. As a fashion designer, I believe that sustaining in the company is related to how talented you are to deliver the best designs & the most innovative products to keep a competitive advantage. And this is what helps me sustain in the company, my talent in the design field which helps the company be ahead of others.

4- Do you consider that learning work culture affect your work and your engagement in the work?

No, as I have previously mentioned the design field is focused on the talents & the visions of fashion styles which I illustrate for the company. My engagement in work is related to the number of styles I can draw & if they will appeal to the owners or not. As a designer, I judge the workers within this department based on their drawing talent & it has nothing to do with the learning work culture around them.

5- Do you think that learning work culture provides you an opportunity to grow and to make a bright future?

No, I think that it's the experience, the innovation, and the will of the person, which leads towards a bright future. The learning work culture is not going to push the person towards accomplishing his goals, it will just give him the instructions to follow & it's up to this person to choose which path to take. Hence, growing & acquiring a bright future is in the hands of the employee himself, and it has nothing to do with the learning work culture.

Appendix 2: Survey Questionnaire

Demographic Questions

1. Age

- Below 25
- 25-40
- 41-50
- Above 50

2. Gender

- Male
- Female

4. From how many years, you are working here?

- Last one year
- 2-4 years
- 5-7 years
- More than 7 years

Professional Questions

6. Do you think that operate the business in different countries is a challenge for the firm (Primark)?

- Yes
- No

7. Are you agreed on that the UK retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral

- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

8. Do you consider that in order to successfully manage the business, it is mandatory for the firm to have the learning work culture?

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

9. Provide your concern about importance of the learning work culture and the workplace sustainability in the organizations? List the below mention importance:

(1. Strongly Agree 2. Agree 3. Neutral 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree)

- Achieve the goals and objectives
- Reducing the risks and issue
- Encourage the problem solving
- Successfully implementation of CSR
- Increase the productivity of employees
- Other

10. Provide your concern about the factors that affect the learning work culture and workplace sustainability? List the below mention factors:

(1. Strongly Agree 2 Agree 3. Neutral 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree)

- Employees Engagement
- Cost
- Management practices

- Organizational culture and climate
- Continuous change in the technology
- Increasing level of the competition
- Other

11. Provide your concern about strategies and planning of the firms in the Chinese market? List the below mention factors:

(1. Strongly Agree 2 Agree 3. Neutral 4. Disagree 5. Strongly disagree)

- Formulate the best strategy
- Managing and developing people
- Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, commitment, effective leadership, morale
- Better use of existing resources
- Implementation of new and modern technology
- Other

Appendix 3: Cross Tabs Case Processing Summary

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Learning work culture is mandatory * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Learning work culture is mandatory * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Learning work culture is mandatory * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Learning work culture is mandatory * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Reducing the risks and issue * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Reducing the risks and issue * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Reducing the risks and issue * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Reducing the risks and issue * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Encourage problem solving * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Encourage problem solving * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Encourage problem solving * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Encourage problem solving * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Successfully implementation of CSR * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Successfully implementation of CSR * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

Successfully implementation of CSR * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Successfully implementation of CSR * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increase the productivity of employees * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increase the productivity of employees * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increase the productivity of employees * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increase the productivity of employees * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Employees' Engagement * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Employees' Engagement * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Employees' Engagement * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Employees' Engagement * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

Cost * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Cost * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Cost * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Cost * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Management Practices * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Management Practices * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Management Practices * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Management Practices * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Organizational culture and climate * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Organizational culture and climate * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Organizational culture and climate * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Organizational culture and climate * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
change in the technology * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
change in the technology * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
change in the technology * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

change in the technology * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increasing level of the competition * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increasing level of the competition * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increasing level of the competition * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Increasing level of the competition * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Formulate the best strategy * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Formulate the best strategy * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Formulate the best strategy * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Formulate the best strategy * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Managing and developing people * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

Managing and developing people * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Managing and developing people * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Managing and developing people * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Better use of existing resources * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Better use of existing resources * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Better use of existing resources * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

Better use of existing resources * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Implementation of new and better technology * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Implementation of new and better technology * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Implementation of new and better technology * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Implementation of new and better technology * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Age Limit	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Gender Specification	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Working Year	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%
Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries	150	100.0%	0	0.0%	150	100.0%

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Appendix 4: The results of Cross-Tab analysis

Crosstabs

Table 32 UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	81.1%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	17	13	30
		Expected Count	18.0	12.0	30.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	56.7%	43.3%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	18.9%	21.7%	20.0%
		% of Total	11.3%	8.7%	20.0%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0

	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	23	23
	Expected Count	13.8	9.2	23.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	38.3%	15.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	15.3%	15.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	119.306 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	160.850	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	107.275	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.511	.046	7.668	.000
		UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries Dependent	.299	.052	5.212	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.783	.053	8.273	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries Dependent	.310	.033		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.795	.007		.000 ^c

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.892	.000
	Cramer's V	.892	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.666	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 33 UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		
			Yes	No	Total
UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	26	4	30
		Expected Count	18.7	7.3	26.0
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	73.7%	0.0%	48.7%
% of Total		48.7%	0.0%	48.7%	

	Expected Count	19.8	10.2	30.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	86.7%	13.3%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	26.3%	7.8%	20.0%
	% of Total	17.3%	2.7%	20.0%
Neutral	Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	27.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	23	23
	Expected Count	15.2	7.8	23.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	45.1%	15.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	15.3%	15.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0

	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	19.6%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	134.551 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	168.750	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	117.563	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.547	.044	7.668	.000
		UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries Dependent	.299	.052	5.212	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.922	.038	8.273	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	UK Retail industry is one of the biggest and leading industries Dependent	.293	.028		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.897	.039		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.947	.000
	Cramer's V	.947	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.688	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 34 Learning work culture is mandatory * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Learning work culture is mandatory	Strongly Agree	Count	63	0	63
		Expected Count	37.8	25.2	63.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	70.0%	0.0%	42.0%
		% of Total	42.0%	0.0%	42.0%
	Agree	Count	27	8	35
		Expected Count	21.0	14.0	35.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	77.1%	22.9%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	30.0%	13.3%	23.3%
		% of Total	18.0%	5.3%	23.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20	

	Expected Count	12.0	8.0	20.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	33.3%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	124.286 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	164.275	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	109.738	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.490	.040	8.182	.000
		Learning work culture is mandatory Dependent	.230	.045	4.804	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.867	.044	8.921	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Learning work culture is mandatory Dependent	.255	.024		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.829	.035		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.910	.000
	Cramer's V	.910	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.673	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 35 Learning work culture is mandatory * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Learning work culture is mandatory	Strongly Agree	Count	63	0	63
		Expected Count	41.6	21.4	63.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	63.6%	0.0%	42.0%
		% of Total	42.0%	0.0%	42.0%
	Agree	Count	35	0	35
		Expected Count	23.1	11.9	35.0
		% within Learning work culture is mandatory	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	35.4%	0.0%	23.3%

	% of Total	23.3%	0.0%	23.3%
Neutral	Count	1	13	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	7.1%	92.9%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	1.0%	25.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.7%	8.7%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	13.2	6.8	20.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	39.2%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Learning work culture is mandatory	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.862 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.106	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	121.843	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.507	.040	7.859	.000
		Learning work culture is mandatory Dependent	.230	.045	4.804	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.020	8.412	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Learning work culture is mandatory Dependent	.268	.015		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.972	.025	.000 ^c
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- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.986	.000
	Cramer's V	.986	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 36 Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Achieve the Goals and Objectives	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	81.1%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	17	13	30

	Expected Count	18.0	12.0	30.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	56.7%	43.3%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	18.9%	21.7%	20.0%
	% of Total	11.3%	8.7%	20.0%
Neutral	Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	23	23
	Expected Count	13.8	9.2	23.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	38.3%	15.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	15.3%	15.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0

	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	119.306 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	160.850	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	107.275	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.511	.046	7.668	.000
		Achieve the Goals and Objectives Dependent	.299	.052	5.212	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.783	.053	8.273	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Achieve the Goals and Objectives Dependent	.310	.033		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.795	.007		.000 ^c

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.892	.000
	Cramer's V	.892	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.666	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 37 Achieve the Goals and Objectives * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		
			Yes	No	Total
Achieve the Goals and Objectives	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	26	4	30
		Expected Count	19.8	10.2	30.0
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%

	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	86.7%	13.3%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	26.3%	7.8%	20.0%
	% of Total	17.3%	2.7%	20.0%
Neutral	Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	27.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	23	23
	Expected Count	15.2	7.8	23.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	45.1%	15.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	15.3%	15.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	19.6%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%

Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Achieve the Goals and Objectives	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	134.551 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	168.750	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	117.563	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.547	.044	7.668	.000
		Achieve the Goals and Objectives Dependent	.299	.052	5.212	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.922	.038	8.273	.000

Goodman and Kruskal tau	Achieve the Goals and Objectives Dependent	.293	.028		.000 ^c
	Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.897	.039		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.947	.000
	Cramer's V	.947	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.688	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 38 Reducing the risks and issue * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Reducing the risks and issue	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within Reducing the risks and issue	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	81.1%	0.0%	48.7%

	% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
Agree	Count	17	8	25
	Expected Count	15.0	10.0	25.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	68.0%	32.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	18.9%	13.3%	16.7%
	% of Total	11.3%	5.3%	16.7%
Neutral	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	14.4	9.6	24.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	40.0%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%

Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.333 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.560	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	115.773	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.555	.043	8.220	.000
		Reducing the risks and issue Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.867	.044	8.921	.000

Goodman and Kruskal tau	Reducing the risks and issue Dependent	.326	.032		.000 ^c
	Gender Specification Dependent	.849	.021		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Reducing the risks and issue * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Table 39 Reducing the risks and issue * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Reducing the risks and issue	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within Reducing the risks and issue	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%

	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	73.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
Agree	Count	25	0	25
	Expected Count	16.5	8.5	25.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	25.3%	0.0%	16.7%
	% of Total	16.7%	0.0%	16.7%
Neutral	Count	1	9	10
	Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	10.0%	90.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	1.0%	17.6%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.7%	6.0%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	15.8	8.2	24.0

	% within Reducing the risks and issue	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	47.1%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Reducing the risks and issue	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.989 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.809	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	128.067	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.578	.042	7.911	.000
		Reducing the risks and issue Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.020	8.412	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Reducing the risks and issue Dependent	.319	.026		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.973	.023		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.987	.000
	Cramer's V	.987	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Encourage problem solving * Gender Specification

Table 40 Encourage problem solving * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Encourage problem solving	Strongly Agree	Count	64	0	64
		Expected Count	38.4	25.6	64.0
		% within Encourage problem solving	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	71.1%	0.0%	42.7%
		% of Total	42.7%	0.0%	42.7%
	Agree	Count	26	9	35
		Expected Count	21.0	14.0	35.0
		% within Encourage problem solving	74.3%	25.7%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	28.9%	15.0%	23.3%
		% of Total	17.3%	6.0%	23.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
		% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
	Disagree	Count	0	19	19

	Expected Count	11.4	7.6	19.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	31.7%	12.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.7%	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	122.143 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.000	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	108.242	1	.000

N of Valid Cases	150		
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a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.479	.040	8.065	.000
		Encourage problem solving Dependent	.221	.045	4.664	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.850	.046	8.790	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Encourage problem solving Dependent	.255	.025		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.814	.032		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.902	.000
	Cramer's V	.902	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.670	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 41 Encourage problem solving * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Encourage problem solving	Strongly Agree	Count	64	0	64
		Expected Count	42.2	21.8	64.0
		% within Encourage problem solving	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	64.6%	0.0%	42.7%
		% of Total	42.7%	0.0%	42.7%
		Agree	Count	35	0
	Expected Count	23.1	11.9	35.0	
	% within Encourage problem solving	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	35.4%	0.0%	23.3%	
	% of Total	23.3%	0.0%	23.3%	
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0	
	% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	27.5%	9.3%	
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%	
	Disagree	Count	0	19	19

	Expected Count	12.5	6.5	19.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	37.3%	12.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.7%	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Encourage problem solving	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	150.000 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	192.311	4	.000

Linear-by-Linear Association	122.401	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.511	.038	8.065	.000
		Encourage problem solving Dependent	.221	.045	4.664	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	1.000	.000	8.790	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Encourage problem solving Dependent	.273	.014		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	1.000	.000		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.000	.000
	Cramer's V	1.000	.000

Contingency Coefficient	.707	.000
N of Valid Cases	150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 42 Successfully implementation of CSR * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Successfully implementation of CSR	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	41.4	27.6	69.0
		% within Successfully implementation of CSR	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	76.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
	Agree	Count	21	7	28
		Expected Count	16.8	11.2	28.0
		% within Successfully implementation of CSR	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	23.3%	11.7%	18.7%
		% of Total	14.0%	4.7%	18.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
% within Successfully implementation of CSR		0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
% within Gender Specification		0.0%	23.3%	9.3%	
% of Total		0.0%	23.3%	9.3%	

	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	12.6	8.4	21.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	35.0%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	128.125 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.413	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	113.771	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.525	.040	8.300	.000
		Successfully implementation of CSR Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.883	.041	9.053	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Successfully implementation of CSR Dependent	.293	.028		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.854	.030		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.924	.000
	Cramer's V	.924	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.679	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Successfully implementation of CSR * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Table 43 Successfully implementation of CSR * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries			
		Yes	No	Total	
Successfully implementation of CSR	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	45.5	23.5	69.0
		% within Successfully implementation of CSR	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	69.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
		Agree	Count	28	0
		Expected Count	18.5	9.5	28.0
		% within Successfully implementation of CSR	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%

	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	28.3%	0.0%	18.7%
	% of Total	18.7%	0.0%	18.7%
Neutral	Count	2	12	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	14.3%	85.7%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	2.0%	23.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	1.3%	8.0%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	13.9	7.1	21.0
	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	41.2%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0

	% within Successfully implementation of CSR	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	142.361 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	180.827	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	123.318	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.530	.042	7.668	.000
		Successfully implementation of CSR Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.961	.028	8.056	.000

Goodman and Kruskal tau	Successfully implementation of CSR Dependent	.286	.022		.000 ^c
	Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.949	.028		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.974	.000
	Cramer's V	.974	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.698	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 44 Increase the productivity of employees * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Increase the productivity of employees	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within Increase the productivity of employees	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	81.1%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	17	8	25
		Expected Count	15.0	10.0	25.0
		% within Increase the productivity of employees	68.0%	32.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	18.9%	13.3%	16.7%
		% of Total	11.3%	5.3%	16.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	10	10
		Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
		% within Increase the productivity of employees	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
		% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18	

	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	14.4	9.6	24.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	40.0%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.333 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.560	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	115.773	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.555	.043	8.220	.000
		Increase the productivity of employees Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.867	.044	8.921	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Increase the productivity of employees Dependent	.326	.032		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.849	.021		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 45 Increase the productivity of employees * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Increase the productivity of employees	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within Increase the productivity of employees	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	73.7%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
	Agree	Count	25	0	25
		Expected Count	16.5	8.5	25.0
		% within Increase the productivity of employees	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	25.3%	0.0%	16.7%
		% of Total	16.7%	0.0%	16.7%

	% of Total	16.7%	0.0%	16.7%
Neutral	Count	1	9	10
	Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	10.0%	90.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	1.0%	17.6%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.7%	6.0%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	15.8	8.2	24.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	47.1%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Increase the productivity of employees	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.989 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.809	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	128.067	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.578	.042	7.911	.000
		Increase the productivity of employees Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.020	8.412	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Increase the productivity of employees Dependent	.319	.026		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.973	.023	.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.987	.000
	Cramer's V	.987	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 46 Others * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	64	0	64
		Expected Count	38.4	25.6	64.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	26	9	35
		Expected Count	21.0	14.0	35.0
		% within Others	74.3%	25.7%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	28.9%	15.0%	23.3%
	% of Total	17.3%	6.0%	23.3%
Neutral	Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	19	19
	Expected Count	11.4	7.6	19.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	31.7%	12.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.7%	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Others	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	122.143 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.000	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	108.242	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.479	.040	8.065	.000
		Others Dependent	.221	.045	4.664	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.850	.046	8.790	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.255	.025		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.814	.032		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.902	.000
	Cramer's V	.902	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.670	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 47 Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total	
		Yes	No		
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	64	0	64
		Expected Count	42.2	21.8	64.0
	% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	64.6%	0.0%	42.7%	
	% of Total	42.7%	0.0%	42.7%	
	Agree	Count	35	0	35
Expected Count			23.1	11.9	35.0
% within Others		100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
% within Operate the Business in Different Countries		35.4%	0.0%	23.3%	
% of Total		23.3%	0.0%	23.3%	
Neutral		Count	0	14	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0	

	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	27.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	19	19
	Expected Count	12.5	6.5	19.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	37.3%	12.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.7%	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Others	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	150.000 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	192.311	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	122.401	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.511	.038	8.065	.000
		Others Dependent	.221	.045	4.664	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	1.000	.000	8.790	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.273	.014		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	1.000	.000		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	1.000	.000
	Cramer's V	1.000	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.707	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 48 Employees' Engagement * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Employees' Engagement	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Employees' Engagement	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	24	14	38
		Expected Count	22.8	15.2	38.0
		% within Employees' Engagement	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	26.7%	23.3%	25.3%
		% of Total	16.0%	9.3%	25.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	8	8

	Expected Count	4.8	3.2	8.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	13.3%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	9.6	6.4	16.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	26.7%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	36.7%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.158 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	151.887	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	103.048	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.472	.045	7.547	.000
		Employees' Engagement Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.767	.055	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Employees' Engagement Dependent	.259	.029		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.754	.018		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.869	.000
	Cramer's V	.869	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.656	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 49 Employees' Engagement * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries			
		Yes	No	Total	
Employees' Engagement	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Employees' Engagement	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	66.7%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
		Agree	Count	33	5
	Expected Count	25.1	12.9	38.0	
	% within Employees' Engagement	86.8%	13.2%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	9.8%	25.3%	
	% of Total	22.0%	3.3%	25.3%	

Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	5.3	2.7	8.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	15.7%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	10.6	5.4	16.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	31.4%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	43.1%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Employees' Engagement	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	130.650 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.718	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	116.168	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.72.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.504	.044	7.547	.000
		Employees' Engagement Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.902	.042	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Employees' Engagement Dependent	.257	.024		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.871	.043		.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.933	.000
	Cramer's V	.933	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.682	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 50 Cost * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		
			Male	Female	Total
Cost	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	43.8	29.2	73.0
		% within Cost	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	17	8	25
		Expected Count	15.0	10.0	25.0
		% within Cost	68.0%	32.0%	100.0%
			48.7%	0.0%	48.7%

	% within Gender Specification	18.9%	13.3%	16.7%
	% of Total	11.3%	5.3%	16.7%
Neutral	Count	0	10	10
	Expected Count	6.0	4.0	10.0
	% within Cost	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	16.7%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	6.7%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Cost	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	14.4	9.6	24.0
	% within Cost	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	40.0%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Cost	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.333 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.560	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	115.773	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.555	.043	8.220	.000
		Cost Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.867	.044	8.921	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Cost Dependent	.326	.032		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.849	.021		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 51 Cost * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total	
		Yes	No		
Cost	Strongly Agree	Count	73	0	73
		Expected Count	48.2	24.8	73.0
		% within Cost	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	73.7%	0.0%	48.7%
		% of Total	48.7%	0.0%	48.7%
		Agree	Count	25	0
	Expected Count	16.5	8.5	25.0	
	% within Cost	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	25.3%	0.0%	16.7%	
	% of Total	16.7%	0.0%	16.7%	
Neutral	Count	1	9	10	
	Expected Count	6.6	3.4	10.0	

	% within Cost	10.0%	90.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	1.0%	17.6%	6.7%
	% of Total	0.7%	6.0%	6.7%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Cost	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	24	24
	Expected Count	15.8	8.2	24.0
	% within Cost	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	47.1%	16.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	16.0%	16.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Cost	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.989 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	185.809	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	128.067	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.578	.042	7.911	.000
		Cost Dependent	.312	.053	5.345	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.020	8.412	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Cost Dependent	.319	.026		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.973	.023		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.987	.000
	Cramer's V	.987	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 52 Management Practices * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Management Practices	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	41.4	27.6	69.0
		% within Management Practices	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	76.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
	Agree	Count	21	7	28
		Expected Count	16.8	11.2	28.0
		% within Management Practices	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	23.3%	11.7%	18.7%
		% of Total	14.0%	4.7%	18.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14

	Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0
	% within Management Practices	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Management Practices	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	12.6	8.4	21.0
	% within Management Practices	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	35.0%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Management Practices	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	128.125 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.413	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	113.771	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.525	.040	8.300	.000
		Management Practices Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.883	.041	9.053	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Management Practices Dependent	.293	.028		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.854	.030		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.924	.000
	Cramer's V	.924	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.679	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 53 Management Practices * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		
			Yes	No	Total
Management Practices	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	45.5	23.5	69.0
		% within Management Practices	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	69.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
		Agree	Count	28	0
	Expected Count	18.5	9.5	28.0	
	% within Management Practices	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	28.3%	0.0%	18.7%	
	% of Total	18.7%	0.0%	18.7%	

Neutral	Count	2	12	14
	Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
	% within Management Practices	14.3%	85.7%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	2.0%	23.5%	9.3%
	% of Total	1.3%	8.0%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0
	% within Management Practices	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	13.9	7.1	21.0
	% within Management Practices	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	41.2%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Management Practices	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	142.361 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	180.827	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	123.318	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.530	.042	7.668	.000
		Management Practices Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.961	.028	8.056	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Management Practices Dependent	.286	.022		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.949	.028	.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.974	.000
	Cramer's V	.974	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.698	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 54 Organizational culture and climate * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Organizational culture and climate	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Organizational culture and climate	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%

Agree	Count	24	14	38
	Expected Count	22.8	15.2	38.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	26.7%	23.3%	25.3%
	% of Total	16.0%	9.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	4.8	3.2	8.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	13.3%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	9.6	6.4	16.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	26.7%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	36.7%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.158 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	151.887	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	103.048	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.472	.045	7.547	.000
		Organizational culture and climate Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.767	.055	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Organizational culture and climate Dependent	.259	.029		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.754	.018		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.869	.000
	Cramer's V	.869	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.656	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 55 Organizational culture and climate * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries			
		Yes	No	Total	
Organizational culture and climate	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Organizational culture and climate	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	66.7%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	33	5	38
		Expected Count	25.1	12.9	38.0
		% within Organizational culture and climate	86.8%	13.2%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	9.8%	25.3%
		% of Total	22.0%	3.3%	25.3%
	Neutral	Count	0	8	8
		Expected Count	5.3	2.7	8.0
		% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	15.7%	5.3%
		% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%

Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	10.6	5.4	16.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	31.4%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	43.1%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Organizational culture and climate	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	130.650 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.718	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	116.168	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.72.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.504	.044	7.547	.000
		Organizational culture and climate Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.902	.042	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Organizational culture and climate Dependent	.257	.024		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.871	.043		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.933	.000
	Cramer's V	.933	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.682	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 56 change in the technology * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
change in the technology	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within change in the technology	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	24	10	34
		Expected Count	20.4	13.6	34.0
		% within change in the technology	70.6%	29.4%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	26.7%	16.7%	22.7%
		% of Total	16.0%	6.7%	22.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	15	15

	Expected Count	9.0	6.0	15.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	12.0	8.0	20.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	33.3%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.0	6.0	15.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within change in the technology	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	120.588 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	160.709	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	107.171	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.486	.042	7.960	.000
		change in the technology Dependent	.238	.046	4.804	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.833	.048	8.660	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	change in the technology Dependent	.262	.027		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.804	.027		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.897	.000
	Cramer's V	.897	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.668	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 57 change in the technology * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries			
		Yes	No	Total	
change in the technology	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within change in the technology	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	66.7%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
		Agree	Count	33	1
	Expected Count	22.4	11.6	34.0	
	% within change in the technology	97.1%	2.9%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	2.0%	22.7%	
	% of Total	22.0%	0.7%	22.7%	

Neutral	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	13.2	6.8	20.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	39.2%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0
	% within change in the technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within change in the technology	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.675 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	183.288	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	120.098	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.10.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.519	.040	7.960	.000
		change in the technology Dependent	.238	.046	4.804	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.019	8.660	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	change in the technology Dependent	.272	.018		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.971	.027		.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.985	.000
	Cramer's V	.985	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 58 Increasing level of the competition * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Increasing level of the competition	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Increasing level of the competition	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	24	14	38

	Expected Count	22.8	15.2	38.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	26.7%	23.3%	25.3%
	% of Total	16.0%	9.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	4.8	3.2	8.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	13.3%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	9.6	6.4	16.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	26.7%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	36.7%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0

	% within Increasing level of the competition	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.158 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	151.887	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	103.048	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.472	.045	7.547	.000
		Increasing level of the competition Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.767	.055	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Increasing level of the competition Dependent	.259	.029		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.754	.018		.000 ^c

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.869	.000
	Cramer's V	.869	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.656	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 59 Increasing level of the competition * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Increasing level of the competition	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Increasing level of the competition	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	33	5	38
		Expected Count	25.1	12.9	38.0
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%

	% within Increasing level of the competition	86.8%	13.2%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	9.8%	25.3%
	% of Total	22.0%	3.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	5.3	2.7	8.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	15.7%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	10.6	5.4	16.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	31.4%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	43.1%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%

Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Increasing level of the competition	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	130.650 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.718	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	116.168	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.72.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.504	.044	7.547	.000
		Increasing level of the competition Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.902	.042	8.145	.000

Goodman and Kruskal tau	Increasing level of the competition Dependent	.257	.024		.000 ^c
	Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.871	.043		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.933	.000
	Cramer's V	.933	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.682	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 60 Others * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	65	0	65
		Expected Count	39.0	26.0	65.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	72.2%	0.0%	43.3%
		% of Total	43.3%	0.0%	43.3%
	Agree	Count	25	15	40

	Expected Count	24.0	16.0	40.0
	% within Others	62.5%	37.5%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	27.8%	25.0%	26.7%
	% of Total	16.7%	10.0%	26.7%
Neutral	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.0	6.0	15.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	17	17
	Expected Count	10.2	6.8	17.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	28.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	13	13
	Expected Count	7.8	5.2	13.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	21.7%	8.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	8.7%	8.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Others	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	110.938 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	148.978	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	98.290	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.428	.043	7.391	.000
		Others Dependent	.200	.043	4.379	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.750	.056	8.018	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.240	.027		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.740	.017		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.860	.000
	Cramer's V	.860	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.652	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 61 Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total	
		Yes	No		
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	65	0	65
		Expected Count	42.9	22.1	65.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	65.7%	0.0%	43.3%
		% of Total	43.3%	0.0%	43.3%
		Agree	Count	34	6
	Expected Count	26.4	13.6	40.0	
	% within Others	85.0%	15.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	34.3%	11.8%	26.7%	
	% of Total	22.7%	4.0%	26.7%	
	Neutral	Count	0	15	15
		Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0

	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	17	17
	Expected Count	11.2	5.8	17.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	33.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	13	13
	Expected Count	8.6	4.4	13.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	25.5%	8.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	8.7%	8.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Others	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.273 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	158.494	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	108.837	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.42.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.456	.042	7.391	.000
		Others Dependent	.200	.043	4.379	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.882	.045	8.018	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.235	.021		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.848	.044		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 62 Formulate the best strategy * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Formulate the best strategy	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Formulate the best strategy	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	24	10	34
		Expected Count	20.4	13.6	34.0
		% within Formulate the best strategy	70.6%	29.4%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	26.7%	16.7%	22.7%
		% of Total	16.0%	6.7%	22.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	15	15

	Expected Count	9.0	6.0	15.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	12.0	8.0	20.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	33.3%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.0	6.0	15.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	120.588 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	160.709	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	107.171	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.00.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.486	.042	7.960	.000
		Formulate the best strategy Dependent	.238	.046	4.804	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.833	.048	8.660	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Formulate the best strategy Dependent	.262	.027		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.804	.027		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.897	.000
	Cramer's V	.897	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.668	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 63 Formulate the best strategy * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Formulate the best strategy	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Formulate the best strategy	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	66.7%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
		Agree	Count	33	1
	Expected Count	22.4	11.6	34.0	
	% within Formulate the best strategy	97.1%	2.9%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	2.0%	22.7%	
	% of Total	22.0%	0.7%	22.7%	

Neutral	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	13.2	6.8	20.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	39.2%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	15	15
	Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Formulate the best strategy	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	145.675 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	183.288	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	120.098	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.10.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.519	.040	7.960	.000
		Formulate the best strategy Dependent	.238	.046	4.804	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.980	.019	8.660	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Formulate the best strategy Dependent	.272	.018		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.971	.027		.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.985	.000
	Cramer's V	.985	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.702	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 64 Managing and developing people * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Managing and developing people	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Managing and developing people	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
	Agree	Count	24	14	38

	Expected Count	22.8	15.2	38.0
	% within Managing and developing people	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	26.7%	23.3%	25.3%
	% of Total	16.0%	9.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	4.8	3.2	8.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	13.3%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	9.6	6.4	16.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	26.7%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	36.7%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0

	% within Managing and developing people	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.158 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	151.887	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	103.048	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.472	.045	7.547	.000
		Managing and developing people Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.767	.055	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Managing and developing people Dependent	.259	.029		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.754	.018		.000 ^c

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.869	.000
	Cramer's V	.869	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.656	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 65 Managing and developing people * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		
			Yes	No	Total
Managing and developing people	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Managing and developing people	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	Agree	Count	33	5	38
		Expected Count	25.1	12.9	38.0
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%

	% within Managing and developing people	86.8%	13.2%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	9.8%	25.3%
	% of Total	22.0%	3.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	5.3	2.7	8.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	15.7%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	10.6	5.4	16.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	31.4%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
	% within Managing and developing people	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	43.1%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%

Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Managing and developing people	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	130.650 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.718	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	116.168	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.72.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.504	.044	7.547	.000
		Managing and developing people Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.902	.042	8.145	.000

Goodman and Kruskal tau	Managing and developing people Dependent	.257	.024		.000 ^c
	Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.871	.043		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.933	.000
	Cramer's V	.933	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.682	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 66 Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	Strongly Agree	Count	65	0	65
		Expected Count	39.0	26.0	65.0
		% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	72.2%	0.0%	43.3%
	% of Total	43.3%	0.0%	43.3%
Agree	Count	25	15	40
	Expected Count	24.0	16.0	40.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	62.5%	37.5%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	27.8%	25.0%	26.7%
	% of Total	16.7%	10.0%	26.7%
	Neutral	Count	0	15
Expected Count		9.0	6.0	15.0
% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc		0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
% within Gender Specification		0.0%	25.0%	10.0%
% of Total		0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree		Count	0	17
	Expected Count	10.2	6.8	17.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	28.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
		Count	0	13

Strongly Disagree	Expected Count	7.8	5.2	13.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	21.7%	8.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	8.7%	8.7%
	Total			
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	110.938 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	148.978	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	98.290	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.428	.043	7.391	.000
		Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc Dependent	.200	.043	4.379	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.750	.056	8.018	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc Dependent	.240	.027		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.740	.017		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.860	.000
	Cramer's V	.860	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.652	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 67 Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	Strongly Agree	Count	65	0	65
		Expected Count	42.9	22.1	65.0
		% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	65.7%	0.0%	43.3%
		% of Total	43.3%	0.0%	43.3%
		Agree	Count	34	6
	Expected Count	26.4	13.6	40.0	
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	85.0%	15.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	34.3%	11.8%	26.7%	
	% of Total	22.7%	4.0%	26.7%	
	Neutral	Count	0	15	15
		Expected Count	9.9	5.1	15.0
		% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	29.4%	10.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.0%	10.0%
Disagree	Count	0	17	17
	Expected Count	11.2	5.8	17.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	33.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	13	13
	Expected Count	8.6	4.4	13.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	25.5%	8.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	8.7%	8.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.273 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	158.494	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	108.837	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.42.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.456	.042	7.391	.000
		Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc Dependent	.200	.043	4.379	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.882	.045	8.018	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Honesty, integrity, trustworthiness, accountability, etc Dependent	.235	.021		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.848	.044		.000 ^c

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 68 Better use of existing resources * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Better use of existing resources	Strongly Agree	Count	80	0	80
		Expected Count	48.0	32.0	80.0
		% within Better use of existing resources	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	88.9%	0.0%	53.3%
		% of Total	53.3%	0.0%	53.3%
	Agree	Count	10	12	22
		Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
		% within Better use of existing resources	45.5%	54.5%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	11.1%	20.0%	14.7%
	% of Total	6.7%	8.0%	14.7%
Neutral	Count	0	11	11
	Expected Count	6.6	4.4	11.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	18.3%	7.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	7.3%	7.3%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	12.0	8.0	20.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	33.3%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	17	17
	Expected Count	10.2	6.8	17.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	28.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.273 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	171.587	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	112.077	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.40.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.538	.049	7.095	.000
		Better use of existing resources Dependent	.286	.054	4.804	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.833	.057	6.847	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Better use of existing resources Dependent	.373	.034		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.848	.008		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.921	.000
	Cramer's V	.921	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.678	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 69 Better use of existing resources * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Better use of existing resources	Strongly Agree	Count	80	0	80
		Expected Count	52.8	27.2	80.0
		% within Better use of existing resources	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	80.8%	0.0%	53.3%
		% of Total	53.3%	0.0%	53.3%
	Agree	Count	19	3	22
		Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
		% within Better use of existing resources	86.4%	13.6%	100.0%

	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	19.2%	5.9%	14.7%
	% of Total	12.7%	2.0%	14.7%
Neutral	Count	0	11	11
	Expected Count	7.3	3.7	11.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	21.6%	7.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	7.3%	7.3%
Disagree	Count	0	20	20
	Expected Count	13.2	6.8	20.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	39.2%	13.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	13.3%	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	17	17
	Expected Count	11.2	5.8	17.0
	% within Better use of existing resources	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	33.3%	11.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	11.3%	11.3%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0

	% within Better use of existing resources	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	138.454 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	174.785	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	123.288	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.74.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.562	.042	7.741	.000
		Better use of existing resources Dependent	.286	.054	4.804	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.941	.033	8.402	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Better use of existing resources Dependent	.335	.031		.000 ^c

Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.923	.034	.000 ^c
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a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.961	.000
	Cramer's V	.961	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.693	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 70 Implementation of new and better technology * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Implementation of new and better technology	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	39.6	26.4	66.0
		% within Implementation of new and better technology	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	73.3%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%

Agree	Count	24	14	38
	Expected Count	22.8	15.2	38.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	63.2%	36.8%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	26.7%	23.3%	25.3%
	% of Total	16.0%	9.3%	25.3%
Neutral	Count	0	8	8
	Expected Count	4.8	3.2	8.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	13.3%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	9.6	6.4	16.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	26.7%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	13.2	8.8	22.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	36.7%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	113.158 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	151.887	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	103.048	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.20.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.472	.045	7.547	.000
		Implementation of new and better technology Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.767	.055	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Implementation of new and better technology Dependent	.259	.029		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.754	.018		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.869	.000
	Cramer's V	.869	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.656	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 71 Implementation of new and better technology * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

			Operate the Business in Different Countries		Total
			Yes	No	
Implementation of new and better technology	Strongly Agree	Count	66	0	66
		Expected Count	43.6	22.4	66.0
		% within Implementation of new and better technology	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	66.7%	0.0%	44.0%
		% of Total	44.0%	0.0%	44.0%
		Agree	Count	33	5
	Expected Count	25.1	12.9	38.0	
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	86.8%	13.2%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	33.3%	9.8%	25.3%	
	% of Total	22.0%	3.3%	25.3%	
	Neutral	Count	0	8	8
		Expected Count	5.3	2.7	8.0
		% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	15.7%	5.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	5.3%	5.3%
Disagree	Count	0	16	16
	Expected Count	10.6	5.4	16.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	31.4%	10.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	10.7%	10.7%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	22	22
	Expected Count	14.5	7.5	22.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	43.1%	14.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.7%	14.7%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Implementation of new and better technology	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	130.650 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	162.718	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	116.168	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.72.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.504	.044	7.547	.000
		Implementation of new and better technology Dependent	.262	.048	5.078	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.902	.042	8.145	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Implementation of new and better technology Dependent	.257	.024		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.871	.043		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.933	.000
	Cramer's V	.933	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.682	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 72 Others * Gender Specification

Crosstab

			Gender Specification		Total
			Male	Female	
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	41.4	27.6	69.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Gender Specification	76.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
		Agree	Count	21	7
	Expected Count	16.8	11.2	28.0	
	% within Others	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%	
	% within Gender Specification	23.3%	11.7%	18.7%	
	% of Total	14.0%	4.7%	18.7%	
	Neutral	Count	0	14	14
		Expected Count	8.4	5.6	14.0

	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	23.3%	9.3%
	% of Total	0.0%	9.3%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18
	Expected Count	10.8	7.2	18.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	30.0%	12.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	12.6	8.4	21.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	0.0%	35.0%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	90	60	150
	Expected Count	90.0	60.0	150.0
	% within Others	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
	% within Gender Specification	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	128.125 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	170.413	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	113.771	1	.000

N of Valid Cases	150		
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a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.60.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.525	.040	8.300	.000
		Others Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Gender Specification Dependent	.883	.041	9.053	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.293	.028		.000 ^c
		Gender Specification Dependent	.854	.030		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.924	.000
	Cramer's V	.924	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.679	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Table 73 Others * Operate the Business in Different Countries

Crosstab

		Operate the Business in Different Countries			
		Yes	No	Total	
Others	Strongly Agree	Count	69	0	69
		Expected Count	45.5	23.5	69.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	69.7%	0.0%	46.0%
		% of Total	46.0%	0.0%	46.0%
	Agree	Count	28	0	28
		Expected Count	18.5	9.5	28.0
		% within Others	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	28.3%	0.0%	18.7%
		% of Total	18.7%	0.0%	18.7%
	Neutral	Count	2	12	14
		Expected Count	9.2	4.8	14.0
		% within Others	14.3%	85.7%	100.0%
		% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	2.0%	23.5%	9.3%
		% of Total	1.3%	8.0%	9.3%
Disagree	Count	0	18	18	
	Expected Count	11.9	6.1	18.0	
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	35.3%	12.0%	

	% of Total	0.0%	12.0%	12.0%
Strongly Disagree	Count	0	21	21
	Expected Count	13.9	7.1	21.0
	% within Others	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	0.0%	41.2%	14.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	14.0%	14.0%
Total	Count	99	51	150
	Expected Count	99.0	51.0	150.0
	% within Others	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%
	% within Operate the Business in Different Countries	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	66.0%	34.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	142.361 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	180.827	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	123.318	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	150		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.76.

Directional Measures

			Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Lambda	Symmetric	.530	.042	7.668	.000
		Others Dependent	.259	.049	4.942	.000
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.961	.028	8.056	.000
	Goodman and Kruskal tau	Others Dependent	.286	.022		.000 ^c
		Operate the Business in Different Countries Dependent	.949	.028		.000 ^c

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on chi-square approximation

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.974	.000
	Cramer's V	.974	.000
	Contingency Coefficient	.698	.000
N of Valid Cases		150	

(Source: 'Author's own work, September 2020')

Bibliography

Conceptual diagram:

